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One Path, Many Activities, One Pattern:
Rhetorical Internationalization Towards Understanding the Internationalization
of Argentine Public Universities

By: Mariano Martín Pérez

A Thesis Submitted to:

The Board of the Discipline of Culture and Religion Sciences
of The Jagiellonian University in Kraków in fulfillment
of the requirements for the Ph.D. degree in Cultural Studies

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This thesis is directed by:

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I started this trip a long time before finding my way to Poland. It is difficult to leave a record of all the people who in their own way helped me get to know new things and get to know myself, not to mention pre-visualize this moment and feel that it was indeed possible to carry out this journey doubtlessly.

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Structure of this Doctoral Thesis

This doctoral thesis consists of an introduction, five chapters, and a summary. The introduction includes the work's basic assumptions, the main research problem, and the selected subject's research status¹.

The first chapter provides a theoretical introduction to the issues analyzed in the thesis. The basic theoretical approaches and concepts of the process of higher education internationalization are discussed, while explaining the analysis developed and presented in the thesis. This work examines several concepts of the internationalization of higher education which have been constructed by various authors who were considered exponents at the time of publication of their works (e.g. , Davies, 1992, 1995; de Wit, 1995, 1997, 2001, 2005, 2007, 2010, 2011, 2013; Knight, 1994, 1997, 2001, 2002, 2003, 2004, 2008, 2011, 2012, 2015; Brandenburg & Federkeil, 2007; Hudzik, 2011, 2014; etc.) The first chapter also analyzes the process of internationalization through different European Union (EU) lenses (mainly, through the history of Erasmus Mundus), myths, and misconceptions of the internationalization, as well as the construction of the concept of internationalization among Argentina's public universities and the conceptual foundations of Erasmus Mundus Action 2 (EMA2), in a broader context of internationalization policy.

The concept of "rhetorical internationalization" and its particular terminology invokes its close connection with the national and institutional culture. As the above-

¹ The PhD dissertation was written following examples from the PhD seminars from the Centre for Higher Education Internationalisation (CHEI) at Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore in Milan, Italy. APA style format was used for citation.

mentioned publications prove, the internationalization of higher education in general and higher education institutions (HEIs) in particular is not only the result of some political decisions accompanied by adopted regulations. As the Author aims to prove in this thesis, the actual outcomes of internationalization are based on culture rather than on organizational framework alone. Therefore, the justified approach in analyzing internationalization must be based on the achievements of cultural studies, overcoming the deficiencies of analyses based exclusively on a political science approach (i.e., objective, rational, and systematic manner).

The following section focuses on the model used by the Author to analyze the internationalization process with methodological issues, accurately demonstrating the process of collecting all the material, data, and necessary information based on the research undertaken and providing the evidence for this thesis. Here, the Author explains the shift from developing a case study to transforming it into a grounded theory (GT).

The main source of information used in this thesis is public information provided by higher education institutions (HEIs) with special attention being given to their respective websites. The Author also initiated the open survey aimed at all public universities (PUs) in Argentina. Whenever possible, interviews were also conducted and later analyzed in the context of the existing body of literature on internationalization, with a particular focus on Argentina's case.

As a consequence of the above, a specific contextual review of the international relation offices (IROs) of all the PUs was carried out in order to obtain the greatest amount of data referring to the actual composition of PUs, the institutional location of IROs, personal and organizational charts, the missions, visions, strategies, and targets of PUs, among other aspects related to the internationalization activities PUs as indicated by the PUs themselves. Once the contextualization of all of Argentina's IROs was completed,

an inspection and filtering process was carried out in order to specify the case study, while specifically observing and analyzing the PUs that participated in any of the eight Erasmus Mundus Action 2 (EMA2) projects. In order to have a pertinent dataset for the sake of comparison, the same work of collecting information was carried out in European HEIs, which were EMA2 Project's co-coordinators in conjunction with Argentina.

The results of this thesis research work are presented in Annex 1 and Annex 2. Within the aforementioned framework, and with a foundation in grounded theory, the insights of Cohen et al. (2014) were essential for facilitating the advancement of the proposal that was analyzed. The information collected complied with the parameters of qualitative investigation as well as the required accuracy concerning the research needed for this thesis.

In the second chapter, a wider context of policies for the internationalization of higher education in Europe is presented as the basis to contextualize the Erasmus Mundus Program Action 2 (EMA2). Within this framework, EMA2 was part of a strategy to strengthen the internationalization of higher education in Europe with the aim of strengthening European HEIs. The result is not solely a contextualized revision of the EMA2 Program from the EU perspective, but rather an in-depth search for the objectives of non-EU states regarding HEIs and their internationalization.

In particular, each EU call for proposals on the internationalization of HEIs is analyzed in a detailed way, with an examination of all the pertinent documents (i.e., general information, aims, and guidelines). The main purpose of this step was to understand the general EU policy concerning the Internationalization of Higher Education.

The subsequent sections review each of the eight EMA2 projects, which were approved to be carried out jointly between European and Argentine HEIs. Within the

projects, one can observe: 1) which logical bases were used, 2) what the objectives were, and 3) what results were presented in Argentina in 2013.

For the purpose of this PhD research, the Author applied the perspective of the participating higher education institutions. Towards this end, the study was aimed at gathering more details from the Education, Audiovisual and Culture Executive Agency (EACEA), which is an agency of the European Union located in Brussels, Belgium. Unfortunately, the EACEA has not provided any other information except the public information about the finances of the projects (which is already publicly available via their website).

The third chapter addresses the Argentinean context of the selected period. It begins with the examination of the scant existent body of literature, with the aim of generating conceptualizations which incorporate the Argentinean reality regarding the internationalization of HEIs. The starting point is 2005, given the first set of definitions which emerged from the World Bank's publication, which took up the challenge of describing the context and situation of internationalization in Latin America, in general, and in Argentina more specifically.

The third chapter also analyzes the Argentinean national first call for projects for developing or strengthening the international relations and cooperation areas of public universities (PUs) in 2006, and the second call for a strategic plan for the development of international relations in 2010. These two were calls made to strengthen the competencies of the PUs responsible for carrying out the internationalization process. Beginning with a review of the available published information on Argentina's internationalization process, the author intends to observe and delimit it as one entity for the PUs. Within this approach, an attempt is made to understand the internationalization process by contextualizing the contributions made by the national authorities through both calls in

order to generate, strengthen, and/or improve the dynamics of internationalization within HEIs. To the best of our knowledge, this information is not already defined in any specific way, nor is it already transformed into any measurable element within the International Cooperation Network of National Universities (RedCIUN is the Spanish acronym), the Argentine network of PUs responsible for internationalization.

Having defined the state of research in Argentina, the next section describes and analyzes Argentina's first national contribution to generating and/or strengthening the institutional units in charge. As Aerden (2014, p. 25) wrote: 'the international office is probably the most visible institution-wide instrument for internationalisation'.

On the one hand, this section does seek to understand: 1) the 2006 first call implications, which was launched for PUs to submit a development project to reinforce their international relations offices (IROs) or equivalent areas to be executed during 2007; 2) the main goal regarding expectations which result in "outcomes"; and 3) the first call's apparent results, in accordance with the call itself. On the other hand, this section reviews the results of a survey carried out by Agnese (2011), which represent a second estimate of the status of those who were responsible for carrying out the Argentine PUs' internationalization process.

The next section focuses on the second call and its results. The author reviews the existing scant data regarding the second call results. Unfortunately, to our knowledge, there is no specific report or reflection of ex-post analyses carried out as part of the national funding agency's activities; there are no other elements that allow to measure the actual results, especially reflecting the differences between first and second call. This is the reason why in this research thesis each participating HEI is observed in detail.

The third chapter as a whole is a survey of what occurred, in what sense it occurred, the results of the occurrence, the number of students involved, and the staff

involved, while maintaining a list of the number of participants and terms of reference which were selected at the beneficiary institutions. In short, the aim is to reconstruct the path and provide a working tool with which to measure the level of rhetorical internationalization within the current process. During this research, observation of the activities in a grouped way, through the strengthened/created organizational managerial unit that was sought within the calls, led this Author to construct the present status which stemmed from the PUs. This was a different situation from the anticipated situation with respect to the support obtained for the period.

The fourth and final chapter presents and details the characteristics of the model used to identify and explain the aforementioned term “rhetorical internationalization”, the concept which is one of the constituent elements of this research thesis. The first section of the fourth chapter explains the model created by the Author and the way it can facilitate comparisons of the analyzed HEIs. The first section presents and explains each section contained in the graphic model, which was primarily constructed based on internationalization analysis models such as the Reactive Model and the Proactive Model in Rudzki (1995, 1998), Davies (1992, 1995), and Hunter and De Wit (2013).

The contextual framework developed by de Wit (2001) was based on Knight (1994, p. 12). Six elements from Knight’s internationalization cycle ‘which a HEI would move through at its own pace’ (i.e., 1st element: Awareness, 2nd element: Commitment, 3rd element: Planning, 4th element: Operationalization, 5th element: Review, and 6th element: Reinforcement) were combined with three elements from Van der Wende (1996) - Analysis of context, Implementation, and Long-term effects. The result was modified version of the internationalization cycle of Knight (1994). The internationalization cycle is thus presented by de Wit (2001) in three new stages: 1st stage: Analysis of context; 6th

stage: Implementation, and last but not least - at its heart, even though it is placed outside the circle: the 9th stage: Integration effect.

Note: In all phases address both the institutional- and department- specific aspects and the relation between the two

Figure 1.1.1.1 Internationalisation circle
Source: de Wit 2001, p. 127

Furthermore,

it is possible to see internationalization as a strategy in itself, without a conscious and deliberate strategy to integrate it into the “teaching, research and service functions. In most cases, internationalization is assumed to have an effect; it is not primarily judged on that effect, but on its own merits. However, in those cases where the main emphasis on internationalization”, i.e., internationalization as a strategy becomes a key factor in the overall strategy of an institution and/or department, the internationalization circle becomes part of an “overall planning circle, with the integration phase as the central link”. In this way, internationalization is no longer part of an external relations policy, but, as Van der Wende (1996, p. 195) also advocates, internationalization is an integral element of educational development and innovation (de Wit, 2001, p. 126).

This is independent from the contextual situation observed when generating and perfecting the internationalization circle and the process's characteristic steps, beyond particular situations or definitions which are present or absent regarding agents with whom the process is working. In conclusion, the process moves forward through each of these stages.

In the second section of the fourth chapter, the absence of time is analyzed as a factor influencing the process of internationalization, as described above, in order to make an observation that would contemplate it comprehensively. In Hudzik terms, comprehensive internationalization "shapes institutional ethos and values and touches the entire higher education enterprise It is an institutional imperative not just a desirable possibility" (2014, p. 7). This led the Author of this research thesis to reflect upon the rhetorical cases of internationalization in HEIs, which met certain macro-contextual and internal characteristics. Hence, it can be asserted that, under a specific timeline (i.e., 2005-2015), HEIs were in the same or similar situation to the process presented by Knight.

Both situational perspectives of the internationalization cycle - Knight's perspective complemented by de Wit's - are considered within the organizational level as well as within relevant external levels and factors. It is noteworthy that, in this section and the rest of the research thesis, agents and drivers are used as synonymous. This is in response to direct intervention by either the EU, the government, or the university rector and whether or not it was a planned intervention - in the framework of the presented model, or an intervention which had already taken place at the time of contemplating and observing past and present situations for this research thesis. This is in order to realize the existing reality of a state of affairs from outside the HEI, whether to self-evaluate, compare the present situation with past situations, monitor or free the analysis from intra-

institutional interests; and to carry out comparative analyses between different HEIs, whether or not they are from the same country.

The model for the Argentinean case is applied in the subsequent section. Here, the author applies the model and presents the first conclusions. In a concrete way, it groups - according to the state of the situation it considers - the HEIs at different levels, depending upon the specific situation of their IROs. The contributions received from the international context within this analysis, up to the national level, are taken into account in the 10-year period that is used as a measurement timeline.

The conclusions presented in this chapter are a possible starting point for future analysis of the particular situations of each of the studied HEIs, and perhaps with the aim to observing them from an internal perspective, and to focus on some of the stages that Knight (1994) or de Wit (2001) identify from the internationalization circle. To this might also be added the factor of Time and the Rhetoric that accompanies the process, regardless of the strategy of Davies (1995) which we identify with HEI states.

Notwithstanding, internationalization should always be understood as a process that is managed, as Brandenburg and Federkeil (2007) point out, and driven towards a better situation than the present one. It can be assumed that both present and future situations are linked to: 1) whoever will manage or carry out the process; 2) whoever it is carried forward for; and 3) the amount of time necessary to make decisions that measurably modify the degree of commitment the HEI has with respect to the internationalization process. The search for the response to this assumption is what motivated this research thesis.

There is no one way to undertake an interpretive approach in any qualitative inquiry. There is the interpretive bricoleur (who aims at recognizing how we actively construct our knowledge) in all of us while we are in the Present day working against the

Past times as we move into a politically charged and challenging Future (Cannella et al., 2016, p. 35).

“Science is universal, and truth is factual everywhere”.

Bernardo Houssay.

Introduction

The paradox with internationalization today is that people other than scholars are moving more swiftly towards generating theories that are able to explain international flows (i.e., global cultural flows). Unfortunately, theories by themselves cannot be measured by using simple arithmetical additions or subtractions of people going abroad. Even if one measures the activities of these individuals in order to theorize over the internationalization process, the results and impacts are not clearly linked to the process occurring within the Higher Education Institutions (HEIs).

Over the last two decades, different postulates, theoretical approaches, and study cases have been developed, researched, and presented in order to create a perfect fit for the term of ‘Internationalization’. This word can represent the complexity of a process which promotes a growing interest, not only on the part of scholars, but also on the part of politicians, managers, rectors, international academic associations, international organizations, professors, students, among others.

The purpose of this research thesis is to analyze Erasmus Mundus Action 2 (EMA2) projects as a means to reflect upon why internationalization has not been taken on properly in Argentinean public universities (PUs). Even though EMA2 has provided the Argentinean PUs with money, mobility – consisting of scholars, staff, students – inputs, expert knowledge, know-how, collaboration, and international partnerships, but to the best of our knowledge nothing significant within the institutional process has happened as a result to date.

On the other hand, PUs were funded by Argentina's national government, both in 2007 and again in 2010, in order to improve efforts to create an internationalization strategy or to reinforce their own internationalization paths through their International Relations Offices (IROs). This was done whether the PUs already had such offices or if they created new ones for such purposes.

The way universities are organized and managed has always been deeply rooted in culture. Customs and traditions play so important a role in defining identities of higher education institutions that they can jealously protect long-time forgotten historical names, as it was the case of Princeton University bringing the case against the use of its old name "College of New Jersey" by another institution (Thelin, 2004). Modern universities compete for prestige, students and money and such competition becomes more and more internationalized. Not only European universities struggle to get extra funds from national and international research agencies and to attract promising international students.

The problem of the culture of an academic institution reveals the complex and complicated nature of the term culture. On the one hand, culture understood as "role of values, expectations, and assumptions" still plays an important role in everyday activities of any university, because "[c]ulture in academic organizations . . . , informs stakeholders, both inside and outside, about the values and goals to which the institution and its members attach greater or lesser importance" (Bess and Dee, 2012, pp. 362-363). On the other hand, however, academic culture represents an intellectual challenge to every researcher, since

[c]ulture, for many organizational members, is (to borrow a cliché) like water to the fish that swim in it—usually unobserved and accepted as a fact of life. But the profound influence of culture on behavior cannot be underestimated. A culture with a strong value of trust in others, for example, can result in dramatically different motivational forces

and resultant behaviors from those of a culture based on fear and suspicion (Bess and Dee, 2012, p. 362)

One of the main aims of this dissertation is to appreciate the role of informal norms that shape everyday activity of any given university, also affecting its strategic decisions towards international collaboration and its willingness to devote necessary resources to internationalization. Many decisions concerning international collaboration are mainly made because of the cultural environment influencing people's behavior while regulations and policies (both national and institutional) play an astonishingly less significant role.

One of the reasons why culture remains a key factor shaping modern universities is deeply rooted in their complexity. As Melissa Laufer (2021, p. 168) observes,

The university is a composition of cultures; these cultures are created around specific tasks (administration, academics) and practices (disciplines/departments). This diversity is reflected in the varied meaning systems across the university as well as in the production of independently minded individuals with their own domains of responsibility and influence. Implementing change within this context requires communicating to different actors spanning across numerous communities.

According to this observation, no positive change can be implemented if the university leadership and management do not take conflicting cultures into consideration.

Marvin Bartell was even more radical in his conclusions (2003, p. 45), as for him any feasible plan to change the university must provide

adequate recognition to the power of the cultures in which planning occurs. (...) if they (planners) help to establish an institutional culture with a shared vision, a willingness to understand the organization and its environment, and trust, they gain access to the efforts and enthusiasm of all participants in transforming the institution.

Without proper understanding of the role that culture plays any university shall fail while introducing strategic culture management for an effective internationalization process (Bartell, 2003, p. 66).

Although university as such is one of the oldest, institutions (except for the Roman Catholic Church), it has become the arena of dynamic changes and blurring boundaries. University is no longer just a place to teach and conduct research, it has become a so called “third space”, thus enabling complex collaboration. Moreover, it is hard to think of more complex university collaboration than that involving cross-border, international cooperation and/or exchange.

The concept of the University <<*third space*>> describes the process and the outcome of blurring the boundaries between professional identities and cultures of academic and professional Staff and the emergence of new types of university professionals – <<*third space professionals*>>. A number of diverse types of professionals that can be included in this dense definition, namely <<*blended professionals*>>, professional staff appointed to operate across these academic and professional domains; <<*unbounded professionals*>>, professional staff who work on complex organisational projects or solutions that presuppose the border-crossing between various university constituencies in the course of their work; and academic staff working across academic and professional domains.(Veles et al., 2018, p. 3)

The presented dissertation shows that the influence of university culture is not diminishing. The realities of internationalization of higher education are a perfect illustration that these are not only regulations and policies that shape modern universities. The rhetoric of internationalization is not the same as the practice of internationalization. The success of some institutions (and failures of others) depends more on cultural factors than economic or political ones.

The case of higher education internationalization is yet another proof that one cannot understand modern world and universities (especially, universities as social

institutions) without taking culture into consideration and taking it seriously. This dissertation is an attempt to employ the cultural approach while researching the complexity of higher education in general and higher education internationalization in particular.

Thus, the field facts for PUs in Argentina are the focus of this research thesis. At the end of the Erasmus Mundus experiences which were researched nothing of the above appeared to be embedded in Argentine public institutions. The Erasmus Mundus experiences simply ended up being projects occurring between colleagues and nothing else.

To demonstrate the existence of either positive or negative aspects from this situation the theoretical approaches to clarify the aspects were shifted. A conceptual model was created to enable comparison and explain why after so much external support (not to mention national internal support) the PUs were not able to move forward in their internationalization process between 2007 and 2014. A link was found between what was happening on a theoretical level and real-time patterns.

Chapter I: Theoretical assumptions

This chapter provides a basis for the theoretical framework for the analyses provided in the rest of this research thesis. Indeed, theoretical approaches and concepts of the higher education system in Argentina, were developed and applied in the research which is the fundamental the basis of this doctoral thesis. It is necessary to discuss some conceptual frameworks on internationalization; approaches and rationales for the process; strategies for internationalization; internationalization in Higher Education Institutions in Argentina through the activity of International Relations Offices (IROs), among others.

The research on higher education internationalization has always been multidisciplinary. Presenting a picture or explanation of this phenomenon from the perspective of just one field, would not reflect the complexity of the reality of 21st century processes of internationalization. Through a thorough review of the literature published by scholars who have been investigating the topic for the last 25 years, a basic framework of theoretical internationalization concepts was created during this doctoral research. The combination of multiple lenses is also aimed at strengthening this study's credibility in accordance with the work of Pasque and Rex (2010).

This is also undertaken by examining the rationales behind the concepts analyzed, the cross-examination of different understanding of the concept itself, the features of the process of internationalization, and **models** of internationalization which have been previously presented; e.g. Davies (1992, 1995); de Wit (1995, 1997, 2001, 2005, 2007, 2010, 2011, 2013); Knight (1994, 1995, 1997, 2001, 2002, 2003, 2004, 2008, 2011, 2012, 2015); Brandenburg and Federkeil (2007); Hudzik (2009, 2011, 2014); among others.

The internationalization models include internalization through the EU's lenses through the history of Erasmus Mundus, internationalization's myths and

misconceptions, the construction of the idea of internationalization in Argentina's public universities, and the EMA2 in the context of a broader internationalization policy.

I.1 Conceptualizing Internationalization

In defining the concept of the internationalization of higher education we begin with some widely accepted concepts and, in turn, describe the internationalization process. The works of Brandenburg and Federkeil (2007, p. 7) as well as Knight (1994, p. 3) describe the process while providing a concept that allows to observe and analyze real implementation of internationalization, either at the institutional level - both at the micro-levels of a department or research institute and at an HEI's macro-level - or nationally. This generates the possibility of making comparisons between HEIs in a simpler and more homogeneous way.

The term 'Internationalization' is here understood "*as the process of integrating the international dimension into the teaching, research and service functions of an institution of higher education which the HEI manages in a more or less steered cycle, from an actual status of internationality at time X towards an envisioned status of extended internationality at time X+N*", while the term 'Internationality' describes either HEI's current status or the status discernible at the time of data acquisition with respect to international activities.

After having clarified the conceptual position on which this doctoral thesis was constructed it is convenient to describe the journey made in order to arrive at the aforementioned theoretical approach. Qiang, quoting Knight (1993), wrote that "internationalization of higher education is the process of integrating an international/intercultural dimension into the teaching, research and service functions of

the institution, known nowadays as the basis for any study carrying out research on internationalization as a process” (2003, p. 249).

Knight (2012) later listed how the terminology reflected priorities and phases of internationalization over the past 50 years or more, illustrated by Table 1.1.1

Generic Terms			
Last 10 years	Last 20 years	Last 30 years	Last 50 years
Regionalization Planetization Globalization Global citizenship Knowledge enterprise Green Internationalization Global rankings	Globalization Borderless education Cross-border education Transnational education Internationalization ‘abroad’ Internationalization ‘at home’	Internationalization Multicultural education Intercultural education Global education Distance education Offshore or overseas education	International education International development cooperation Comparative education Correspondence education
Specific Elements			
Last 10 years	Last 20 Years	Last 30 years	Last 50 years
Regional education hubs International competencies Degree mills Visa factories Joint, double, combined degrees Branding, status-building	Education providers Corporate universities Liberalization of educational services Networks Virtual universities Branch campus Twinning and franchise programs	International students Study abroad Institution agreements Partnership projects Area studies Bi-national cooperation	Foreign students Student exchange Development projects Cultural agreements Language study

Table 1.1.1 Evolution of International Education Terminology
Source: Knight (2012, p. 29).

In describing the differences in the meaning of internationalization for people inside or outside the field, Knight (1994) started a pathway of highlighting definitions developed by Arum and Van de Water (1992) – definitions favored by the concept proposed by Harari (1972) – her own 1993 definition (Knight, 1993), and de Wit’s work in defining internationalization as “rhetorical” for international educators. Knight started a path 25 years ago in aiming to build a definition by using a historical pattern.

Furthermore, when Knight (1994, p. 3) returns to the suggestions of Harari (1989) she states that international education “must encompass not only the curriculum, international exchanges of scholars/students, cooperative programs with the community, training, and a wide array of administrative services, **but also distinct commitments, attitudes, global awareness, [and] an orientation and dimension which transcends the entire institution and shape[s] its ethos**”.

Establishing an internationalization definition was a core topic almost from the very start and was visualized during the last 25 years, and this has not, to our knowledge, appeared to change since then. This is so due to its dynamic, the actors involved in it, the weight of the stakeholders or policymakers, and even the scholars searching for the very best definition to describe it with “one term fits all cases”. It is worth remembering the thought of Knight (2012) that “HEI strategic plans, national policy statements, international declarations, and academic articles all indicate the centrality of internationalization in the world of higher education, even though it is appropriate to remember that there will never be one universal definition.” And clearly there is no one universal definition.

Thus, one must review some of those definitions in order to understand the one definition selected for the purpose of this research thesis.

I.1.1 Reviewing definitions of international education

The general public quite often mistake “higher education internationalization” for “international education”. To avoid further confusion a short survey of definitions is appropriate. Ralyk (2008, pp. 5, 6) notes that “international education refers to a more developed form of international dimension such as program and/or organization; and

internationalization is accepted as an extension of it and refers to a more strategic process approach as de Wit (2001) had explained.”

Regarding the term “international education” Arum and Van der Water (1992, p. 202) suggested a definition referring to the multiple activities, programs, and services that fall within international studies, international educational exchange, and technical cooperation. Furthermore (pp. 196, 197):

- international education is an all-inclusive term encompassing three major strands: a) international content of the curricula, b) international movement of scholars and students concerned with training and research, and c) arrangements engaging U.S. education abroad in technical assistance and educational cooperation programs, as noted by Harari (1972);
- the term “international education” usually refers to activities involving more than one such major area, and, often, it encompasses all of them. A preliminary definition could simply state that international education consists of all educational activities of any kind involving people of two or more nations. It should be noted that “international education” as a comprehensive, umbrella-like term for all international activities has been evolving from before the 1963 lament of Stephen Bailey regarding the confusion over terminology.

Having clarified the perspective referring to international education, which is closer to the vision held within this research thesis, some developed concepts will be reviewed in order to define internationalization. We should take into account that internationalization has developed in an important way when it comes to being conceptually defined. However, to date, a sufficiently comprehensive and unequivocal concept, thus allowing it to advance from this theoretical perspective regarding its wealth and the variability it contains which is yet to be investigated, has not been observed.

When Qiang (2003) indicates that “Knight identified internationalization of higher education as the process of integrating an international/intercultural dimension into the teaching, research and service functions of the institution” (p. 249), he not only

uses the term as comprehensive but as a pillar to proceed with his search for a conceptual framework of internationalization.

Knight (1994) was responsible for giving a set of meanings to the term internationalization, noting that in 1993 the Task Force of the British Columbia Centre for International Education (BCCIE) recommended “clarification of the definition of internationalization, both in the context of the post-secondary system as a whole, and at the individual institutional level”, suggesting that a working definition is a process that prepares the community for successful participation in an increasingly interdependent world (p. 3).

Knight continues with the definition presented by Arum and Van de Water (1992), which supported the international education term proposed by Harari (1972) – presented before in this thesis. International Education refers to the multiple activities, programs, and services that fall within international studies, international educational exchange, and technical cooperation (p. 3).

Qiang (2003, p. 249), quoting Van der Wende (1997), argues this in his definition, since no further goal of the process is indicated. Kalvemark and Van Der Wende (1997, p. 19) state:

She describes internationalization as “the process of integrating an international dimension into the research, teaching and services functions of an institution of higher education”. We agree very much with both the process approach and the broad range of functions concerned. At the same time it should be noted that the term “integrating” refers in our view more to an effort that is undertaken in the context of institutional strategies and policy than to one undertaken by national government

The European Association for International Education (EAIE, 1992) aims at providing a general definition, by giving a list of activities, later cited in Knight and De Wit (1995, p. 15): “internationalisation being the whole range of processes by (which)

education becomes less national and more internationally oriented”. In more recent years, the Council of the European Union (EU) defined “internationalization as the development of international cooperation activities between EU higher education institutions and those in third countries” (Council conclusions, 2010).

As Hudzik (2011) noted, in commenting for the Association of International Educators (NAFSA), internationalization is not a new concept, although applied to higher education institutions (HEIs) it has many possible **operational** meanings. Varying in scale and scope and depending upon purpose, institutional missions, institutional starting – ongoing – stage, the following can be said regarding the programmatic frame of reference and target groups. ‘This is true now and it is likely to be so in the future’ (p. 8).

In fact NAFSA (2008, p. 1) indicated that:

A task force of NAFSA members appointed in early 2008 was asked to create a definition of internationalization that NAFSA could use to guide its work and to provide recommendations...Internationalization is the conscious effort to integrate and infuse international, intercultural, and global dimensions into the ethos and outcomes of postsecondary education. To be fully successful, it must involve active and responsible engagement of the academic community in global networks and partnerships.

The above description is noteworthy as a working definition of an ongoing process which should be analyzed, debated, and updated from time to time, as also noted by many of the scholars working within the sphere of internationalization of higher education institutions.

Knight (1999, p. 23) claims that different paths exist – or in other words: different discourses discussing the HEI internationalization reality - to describe the initiatives selected to drive forward internationalization, such as: activities, elements, components, procedures, or strategies. *Strategy* should be the term to analyze because of the inherent

notion of planned direction and the fact that it can be applied to academic types of activities as well as organizational types of procedures and policies.

Astur and Larrea (2011, p. 1) explain the Argentinean perspective within this process:

internationalization is understood as a process aimed at “institutional strengthening and projection, improving the quality of teaching, the increase and transfer of scientific and technological knowledge, and the contribution to cooperation for development.” (translated by the Author of this thesis).

Astur and Larrea deliver a final reflection on the concept: “the internationalization of higher education is a process across all areas and functions of HEIs, and as such, a privileged means to contribute to the improvement of the quality of higher education.” (Astur and Larrea, 2011; translated by the author of this thesis). It is noteworthy that the internationalization of higher education is more an expression of desire - even of rhetoric - than a verifiable reality, as can be seen in the chapter on conclusions in this research thesis.

Clearly, with reference to the style of speech used when one aims to advance in the use of the concept, with respect to its debate and analysis, as well as to its multiple references to the body of literature, it is important to highlight that caution must be exercised when using a single definition in the terminology and then considering it to be finalized, closed, or indisputable.

As Whitsed and Green (2014 p. 109) explain:

Goodman (2007) cautioned in the context of a critique of the deployment of “internationalization” (*kokusaika* is the translation to the Japanese language) in Japanese higher education: “As academics, we need to be very sensitive to the way actors use multivocal policy instruments such as the rhetoric of internationalization. We need to examine in what context who is using the rhetoric, how and for what purpose” (p. 86).

Failure to do so, ... will only contribute to the further “mystification” of “internationalization” at the conceptual level.

It is not the aim of this PhD research to start a new debate of this nature, but it is necessary to remember that the search for a single and irrefutable definition is futile and unnecessary. Whitsed and Green (2014) note that the relationship between words and actions is fundamental to describe the presence or absence of actions beyond the discourse of “rhetorical internationalization”, although one should research the body of literature in the field of internationalization before seriously applying such terminology.

For the purpose of this PhD research, we refer to de Wit (2001, p. 78), who indicates that “Rationales can be described as motivations for integrating an international dimension into higher education... Different rationales imply different means and ends to internationalization.” Knight (1997) described the four main rationales that might be used for comprehensive research on the internationalization of higher education (i.e., academic, social/cultural, political and economic). It is our belief that it was Qiang (2003) who was able to best present an organized conceptual and organizational framework for the internationalization of higher education via a debate on the term’s meaning and definition. Qiang also describes various rationales and approaches to internationalization and an analysis of strategies for integrating the international dimensions of HEIs.

Knight (2012) returns to her conceptualizations and interpretations of internationalization in the OECD (1999)² publication, where she reminds us that (p. 32):

rationales are the driving force for why an institution ... wants to address and invest in internationalization. Rationales are reflected in the policies and programs that are developed and eventually implemented. Rationales dictate the kind of benefits or

² OECD (1999), *Quality and Internationalisation in Higher Education*, (pp. 17-21) where she makes a synthesis in the analysis of them from the HEIs’ perspective.

expected outcomes. Without a clear set of rationales, accompanied by a set of objectives or policy statements, a plan, and a monitoring/evaluation system, the process of internationalization is often an ad hoc, reactive, and fragmented response [one could call it rhetorical internationalization] to the overwhelming number of new international opportunities available.

This is an interesting proposal to remind us that both the definition and the selection of the concept that guides the process can also be a part of the rhetoric of the rationales.³

The reader is referred to Table I.1.1.1, which lists the categories and levels of rationales as compiled by Knight et al. (1999, 2008).

Four Categories of Rationales (1999)	Two Levels of rationales (2008)
Academic	Institutional
International dimension to research and teaching	International branding and profile
Extension of academic horizon	Income generation
Institution building	Student and staff development
Profile and status	Strategic alliances
Enhancement of quality	Knowledge production
International academic standards	National
Economic	Human resources development
Revenue generation	Strategic alliances
Ecompetitiveness	Commercial trade
Labor market	National building
Financial incentives	Social cultural development
Political	
Foreign policy	
National security	
Technical assistance	

³ For a deeper analysis see Knight (1997, 1999, 2004, 2012); de Wit (2001 pp. 77-94) Chapter Five, Rationales for Internationalisation of Higher Education

Peace and mutual understanding	
National identity	
Regional identity	
Social	
National cultural identity	
Intercultural understanding	
Citizenship development	
Social and community development	

Table I.1.1.1 Change in Rationales Driving Internationalization
Source: Knight et al. (1999, 2008); Knight (2012, p. 33).

In a clear reference to the four categories mentioned in Knight (1997), Lamarra (2014, p. 41) argues that “Internationalization is a challenge that involves the commitment of the country and institutions to rethink the articulation of higher education processes in the face of new economic, social, political, cultural, and productive demands.” (translated by the author of this thesis).

Currently, as has also been the case in the last 10 years, internationalization is much more than merely a discursive term for a debate which crosses all borders - and institutional rhetoric - in the global field of higher education. But it is an element that intersects all HEIs and as such is analyzed starting with the rationales and approaches that Knight used (1994, 1995, 1999, etc.), as well as the postulates of de Wit’s (2001) to enter the reality of HEIs, where speech should be transformed into a reality; or as noted in this research thesis: it is still a part of the rhetoric in the sphere of internationalization.

As de Wit established (2001, p. 111) in an approach to the process, the many different activities identified as key components of internationalization are divided into two major categories: program strategies and organizational strategies.

There are different examples in Table I.1.1.2 - which is not an exhaustive list - of the types of activities that we can observe within the two categories in terms of strategy.

Types of activity Program activities	Examples
Academic programs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Student exchange programs • Foreign language study • Internationalized curricula • Area or thematic studies • Work/study abroad • International students • Teaching/learning process • Joint/double degree programs • Cross-cultural training • Faculty/staff mobility programs • Visiting lecturers and scholars • Links between academic programs and other strategies • Area and theme centers
Research and scholarly collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Joint research projects and publications • International conferences and seminars • International research agreements • Research exchange programs • International research partners in academic and other sectors
Domestic and cross-border activities	<p>Domestic</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community-based partnerships with NGOs or public/private sector groups • Community service and intercultural project work • Customized education and training programs for international partners and clients <p>Cross-border</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International development assistance projects • Cross-border delivery of education programs (commercial and noncommercial) • International linkages, partnerships, and networks • Contract-based training and research programs and services • Alumni abroad programs
Extracurricular activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Student clubs and associations • International and intercultural campus events • Liaison with community-based cultural and ethnic groups • Peer support groups and programs
Organizational Strategies	<p>Governance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Commitment by senior leaders • Active involvement of faculty and staff • Articulated rationale and goals for internationalization • Recognition of international dimension in institutional mission/mandate statements and in planning, management, and evaluation policy documents

Operations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrated into institution wide and department/college level planning, budgeting and quality review systems • Appropriate organizational structures • Systems (formal and informal) for communicating, liaising, and coordinating • Balance between centralized and decentralized promotion and management of internationalization • Adequate financial support and resource allocation systems
Services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support from institution wide service units (student housing, registrar, fund raising, alumni, information technology) • Involvement of academic support units (library, teaching and learning, curriculum development, faculty and staff training, research services) • Support services for incoming and outgoing students (orientation programs, counseling, cross-cultural training, visa advice) • Recruitment and selection procedures that recognize international expertise
Human resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reward and promotion policies to reinforce faculty and staff contributions • Faculty and staff professional development activities • Support for international assignments and sabbaticals

Table I.1.1.2 Institutional-Level Programs and Organizational Strategies for Internationalization
Source: Knight (IN: de Wit, 2005 pp. 23, 24).

With reference to the work of de Wit (2001, p. 111), an analysis of the actions-activities aimed at ensuring the integration of the international dimension within the HEIs themselves can be pursued. In particular, one can analyze the existence or development of policies, within a specified period of time X, that allow the institution to advance in this dimension, as is developed in this thesis. In this regard, Brandenburg and Federkeil (2007) note that “HEI manages in a more or less steered cycle, from a current status of internationality at time X towards a [prolonged] current status of extended internationality at time X + N.”

In order to make a leap in observing the reality of internal organization, this thesis follows the works of authors who have a focus on the analysis of institutional strategies in order to carry out the internationalization process. This methodology is similar to that of Davies (1992, 1995), Rudzki (1998), Knight (1994, 1997, 2001, 2002, 2003, 2004,

2008, 2011, 2012, 2015), de Wit (1995, 1997, 2001, 2005, 2007, 2010, 2011, 2013) and Hudzik (2014).

We Should considering that:

The programme strategies refer to those academic activities and services of an institution of higher education that integrate an international dimension into its main functions. Organisational strategies include those initiatives which help to ensure that an international dimension, or in other words the activities discussed above, are institutionalised through developing the appropriate policies and administrative systems (de Wit, 2001, p. 111).

Regarding the possibility of using Argentine authors to identify a specific conceptual position, as described by Theiler (2005), in de Wit (2005) and in Lamarra (2014), the situation became complex when it was not impossible to define a concept on which the HEIs in Argentina position themselves.

The description used by Astur and Larrea (2011) was understood as being representative - given their roles in the Secretariat of University Policies (SUP) in the Ministry of Education, Culture, Science, and Technology (Argentina) regarding internationalization as a process with respect to the stage(s) in the time continuum. This will also be analyzed in this thesis.

Regarding the characteristics in a HEIs and the strategy(s) that HEIs select to carry out the process of internationalization, it is also possible to find a variety of them in a similar way as indicated in the concept's definition.

Just as it is not possible to identify a **concept** that fits and represents internationalization once and for all, it is not possible to identify the **ideal strategy** that would make it possible to achieve internationalization. It is not an algorithm or even a

guideline that can be followed, given that the variables of factors, interests, decisions, commitments, to name just a few, differ from one HEI to another, as do those responsible for its utilization and contexts.

In terms of the process which is being researched, while considering 1) the institutional moment (given the historical aspects of the Institutions); 2) the institutional interests (with or without globalization, for example); and 3) the degree of one's own commitment and knowledge regarding internationalization, and other factors, there are elements that allow - in the event that the HEI does not describe internationalization in a transparent way - to establish the type of strategy that can be attributed to the HEI within the sphere of internationalization.

It is at this level that the research questions arise:

Hypothesis 1 (H1): Is it possible for a strategy to be copied from one HEI and to work in another in the same way?

Hypothesis 2 (H2): Is it possible that at the national level, despite sharing elements and variables in the strategy, we can observe the repetition of one or several elements in the HEIs' internationalization process by merely following the path proposed by the national government?

Hypothesis 3 (H3): Can we compare the strategies and identify if one is more successful than the other?

Hypothesis 4 (H4): Is it only about observing the ability to adapt the national/international policy interests?

The internal motivations that mobilize an HEI to internationalize will vary and differ as indicated by Hudzik and Stohl (2009, p. 12), without being an exclusive or definitive listing - "the enhancement of the institution's reputation, student learning

outcomes, revenues and markets, research and scholarship, service and engagement, and global bridge building”.

Another interesting contribution is provided by Hunter (IN: de Wit, 2013, p. 61) where that author examines the impact of the national context on the single institution’s ability to respond to a change. In the same line, the Author of this thesis believes that one of the main points to examine is the search for clues to define the existence of rhetorical internationalization. This, then, is the role of IROs as enablers of a real sense of internationalization within the HEIs.

Hunter examines the interplays of internal and external conditions and how institutional behavior may determine the shift from one position to another. Internal drivers are considered to be either static and therefore non adaptive, or dynamic and adaptive to change, while external drivers are defined as either stable or turbulent (Hunter, IN: de Wit, 2013, p. 65)

According to Hunter, one should understand this factor as an answer for institutional responsiveness to adapt to context. Thus, this factor should be seen as a search for institutional characteristics which are more likely to demonstrate the rhetorical existence and weight within the HEI. In other words, Hunter sought to clarify which driver creates advantages or disadvantages in the complex global environment.

Therefore, de Wit (2001, p. 111), when returning to Knight and de Wit (1995), notes that it is possible to find several elements that play a role in the internationalization process nowadays – as in the past – whether they are justified, described, or basically used at all. This process would be linked to the discourse in the sphere of internationalization using a variety of different terms: mechanisms, facilitators, activities, barriers, factors, and strategies. Therefore, the Author of this thesis considers that various factors were certainly used.

However, in this research thesis the term **strategy** will be used to characterize the process which is managed by the HEI in order to accomplish the desired actual, rather than the discursive nor rhetorical, status of **extended internationality**.

Returning to conceptualization of internationalization from as a process. Knight (1999, p. 23) clearly explains that the stress is:

placed on the concept of enhancing and sustaining the international dimensions of research, teaching and service. [Where] Integration is key to the process and strategies which focus on both academic activities as well as [the fact that] organisational factors are central [and thus they should be analyzed] to achieving a successful and sustainable integration of the international dimension.

Knight indicates this as a key element in the **integration** process, and therefore in the strategy selected to be successful in an HEI's internationalization. De Wit (2001) incorporates three more stages into the cycle of Knight (1994), as described before in this thesis, combining them with the elements cited in the analysis of Van der Wende (1996). De Wit focuses on integration as a fundamental factor in the HEI's entire institutional life.

Therefore, de Wit (2001), in observing and analyzing the internationalization process, also implies generating or defining the type of instrument HEIs use to achieve that internationalization. In this way, de Wit provides a roadmap to advance in the description and enter some of the models analyzed in terms of institutional strategy. Knight and De Wit (1995, p.17) have used the term **strategies** to characterize those initiatives which are taken by an institution of higher learning to integrate an international dimension in research, teaching and service functions as well as management policies and systems.

Inside the international rhetorical cycle the above statement could “exist” between the **analysis** and the **commitment** (perhaps also including the **planning**, since plans are an answer for high level managers or rectors). After that one should search the statements’ reality - the actual words used - within the actions in the sphere of internationalization. In other words, it will not be possible to observe or analyze the rhetorical internationalization in the implementation, monitoring, or evaluation stage given that these are the “operational stages”, within which the planning will take place - with or without the rhetorical component - with respect to all of the above. From that point of view, where one can find the elements of the latter’s rhetoric, we would be faced with a system of management that has an awareness of the chosen path and its institutional consequences. However, this research thesis does not aim at analyzing this particular element.

Whichever path is selected in terms of **strategy**, there is no doubt that internationalization must be an embedded element within the organizational structure, mission, and culture, directly influencing the decision system and the decisions made. The entire institution - in all its levels - must embrace the **strategy** in order to internalize the fact that it is not a specific action of an HEI’s particular area or individual, not marginalized or dependent on its novelty within the internal agenda. Finally, the **strategy** is even less of a consequence of the financing it might receive (de Wit, 2001, p. 123).

In line with De Wit (2001) and his detailed analysis of the models of Neave (1992), Rudzki (1993), Davies (1992), Van Dijk and Meijer (1995), Knight and De Wit (1995), Van der Wende (1997), and Knight (1994), in addition to contributions from Söderqvist (2002) and Qiang (2003), the Author of this PhD thesis has advanced in inspecting the models contributed by all of the above authors (plus the results of the analysis undertaken by De Wit, 2001) in order to define the **theoretical elements** that sustain the rest of the work in this PhD thesis.

However, this was not without first considering Zechlin (2010, p. 4), who indicates that “strategic plans are often complicated undertakings. Normally, they consist of a general vision or mission statement followed by descriptions of the current situation in the respective area, strategic objectives and the intended course of action for change”. What Zechlin reminds us of is the complexity of the characterization of strategies, and not only when executing those strategies, but also when analyzing them. Although Zechlin does not indicate it directly, the notion of the management and change of a current situation has been reopened in the search for a betterment of a desired situation at some future stage but Zechlin notes a specific area for the current internationalization work.

On the other hand, Davies (1992, p. 177) in continuing his earlier research (Davies, 1990) and Keller (1983) focus on the search for a conceptual framework in order to analyze the managerial level regarding the internationalization strategy’s formulation, delivery, and institutionalism. Using Keller’s framework, Davies aims to conceptualize the main factors in the development of an **international strategy** in the HEI. Within this international strategy Davies identifies and develops six elements that form the international strategy; as described in Figure I.1.1.2.:

Figure I.1.1.2 Elements in the Development of International Strategy in Universities

Source: (Davies, 1992, p. 190)

In the conceptual framework, Keller develops the three internal elements in detail, and the three external elements. In this PhD thesis, we only mention those elements that support the existence of rhetorical internationalization (for more detail, the reading of the complete chapter is recommended: Davies, 1992, pp. 177-190).

University Mission: *All universities have missions, explicit or implicit (Davies 1987) to be found in various locations (mission statements, policy papers, presidential reports, prospectuses) [websites]. It would seem to be logical that a university espousing internationalism should have clear statements of where it stands in this respect, since the mission should inform planning processes and agendas, resource allocation criteria; serve as a rallying standard internally; and indicate to external constituencies a basic and stable set of beliefs and values* (p. 178) [Bold and italic formats added by the Author of this thesis].

Assessment of Strengths and Weaknesses: Keller focuses here on programs, personnel and finance, and the general contention is that many practices in these areas have been developed by universities for purposes not of internationalism per se, but of general institutional management. They may therefore not be entirely supportive of, nor consistent with the international effort of the institution (p. 179).

Organization Leadership Structure: As is the case with other facets of entrepreneurialism in universities, the delivery of international services may take place through normal organizational units, or through specialist organs created for the purpose [e.g. IRO] (p. 183).

Externally Perceived Image and Identity: This is the mirror of the first internal factor discussed (mission). The issue may be simply stated: it is not too satisfactory for a university to have and to believe in a mission impregnated with internationalism, if external constituencies with which the university purports or hopes to do business...there is a difference between university rhetoric and the perceptions of reality held externally (pp. 184, 185).

The next step is the consideration of the matrix which Davies presents, detailing each of the quadrants representing the dynamics of strategy for each. According to Davies, the HEIs develop their internationalization strategy as is shown in Figure I.1.1.3.

BRIDGES TO THE FUTURE

Figure 1
Elements in the Development of International Strategy in Universities

Figure 1.1.1.3 Institutionalization of Approaches to Internationalization in Universities
Source: (Davies, 1992, p.190).

The matrix used by Davies contains two dimensions that are combined and then explained. In particular, Davies considers that institutionalization can be observed from two dimensions. One dimension will go from an ad hoc dimension to a highly systematic dimension where the management style that is granted in the HEI will be observed. And the dimension, which will go from a marginal spectrum to a dimension of centralization where the importance the HEI gives to internationalization will be observed. (Davies, 1992)

In quadrant A, the Ad Hoc-Marginal is described as:

The amount of international [activities] is relatively small: some overseas students; a small amount of consultancy or continuing education. Research linkages will largely be confined to motivated individuals and arrangements for changing and financing are variable and unsystematic [and unknown by the institution]. A weak data base exists on opportunities, competitions and trends in the international market place and little systematic assessment of opportunity occurs. [The reasons and the amount of Internationalization activities should be described and understood by individuals' interests and/or national/international context. [they] Need to be considered as a *reactive quadrant*] (p. 188).

In the quadrant B, the Systematic-Marginal is described as:

The amount of [activities] is still relatively small, but is well organized [and recognizable inside the HEI structure]. Areas of international activity are precisely identified, and correspond with fields of internal strength and market opportunity. Projects and effort are focused on particular market segments in which the university will endeavor to become expert and niche marketing is usual. Costing and pricing are accurate and realistic. A small number of institutional agreements are meaningful and work. MIS [management information system⁴] and supporting procedures are clear and relevant. Staff training is limited but related [to its internationalization strategy or process in progress] (p. 188).

In quadrant C, the Ad Hoc-Central is described as:

The amount of international [activities] is considerable across a number of different categories and a wide range of market segments and client groups [students, graduates, researchers, professors and staff]. Whereas there may be some strong areas, marketing is usually ill-focused. Curriculum may not be particularly geared to international issues in any coordinated way. Acceptance of projects is usually on a knee-jerked [reactive] basis. Costing and pricing are eccentric. There is a tendency for a sizeable number of institutional agreements, many of which are not operational *but largely rhetorical*. Central marketeers often financial imperative is strong. Tensions are rife. Support services are often not geared to considerable international effort, and ground rules change with bewildering rapidity. [Showing the absence of an internationalization strategy] [bold and italic added by the Author of this thesis] (p. 188).

⁴ An organized approach to the study of the information needs of an organization's management at every level in making operational, tactical, and strategic decisions. Its objective is to design and implement procedures, processes, and routines that provide suitably detailed reports in an accurate, consistent, and timely manner.

In a management information system, modern, computerized systems continuously gather relevant data, both from inside and outside an organization. This data is then processed, integrated, and stored in a centralized database (or data warehouse) where it is constantly updated and made available to all who have the authority to access it, in a form that suits their purpose. management information system (MIS). BusinessDictionary.com. Retrieved September 20, 2014, from BusinessDictionary.com website: <http://www.businessdictionary.com/definition/management-information-system-MIS.html>

In quadrant D, the Systematic-Central is described as:

There is a large volume of international work in many categories, which reinforce each other and have intellectual [and institutional] coherence. The *international mission is explicit* and followed through with specific policies and supporting procedures. The *data base is extensive and regularly updated*. Agency arrangements exist in overseas countries, as do partner institutions for the delivery of programs, with clear and effective operating procedures. Personnel and curriculum policies are continually appraised and readjusted to support the international effort. Financial management is highly systematic, as are interinstitutional linkages. Substantial financial commitment to international projects is apparent. A *dedicated organizational structure* to support a range of international efforts is in place, and the tension exists between these organs and mainstream faculties is usually constructive. Reward and incentive mechanisms are properly used. [Must be considered as the *proactive quadrant by nature*] [bold and italic added by the Author of this thesis] (pp. 188, 189).

It is noteworthy that quadrants described as Ad Hoc by Davies (1992, 1995) are closely related to the Reactive model, as well as the Systematic model linked to the Proactive model described by Rudzki (1998).

Reactive model of internationalization	Pro-active model of internationalization
<p>Stage 1 <u>CONTACT</u> Academic staff engage in making contacts with colleagues in other countries, curriculum development, limited mobility, links lack clear formulation of purpose and duration</p>	<p>Stage 1 <u>ANALYSIS</u> Awareness of what 'internationalization' is and what it entails. Strategic analysis of short-, mid- and long-term organizational objectives - answering the question 'Should we internationalize?' 'Why bother?' Staff training and discussions - understanding of options - what types of international activities are available. International Audit of existing activities and Staff Audit. SWOT analysis. Cost-benefit analysis</p>
<p>Stage 2 <u>FORMALISATION</u> Some links are formalised with institutional agreements being made. Resources may or may not be made available</p>	<p>Stage 2 <u>CHOICE</u> Strategic plan and policy drawn up in conjunction with staff and explicit use made of mutual interest of staff and organization. Performance measures defined. Resources allocated. Networking with internal and external organizations</p>
<p>Stage 3 <u>CENTRAL CONTROL</u> Growth in activity and response by management who seek to gain control of activities</p>	<p>Stage 3 <u>IMPLEMENTATION</u> Measure performance</p>
<p>Stage 4 <u>CONFLICT</u> Organizational conflict between staff and management leads to withdrawing of good will by staff. Possible decline in activity and disenchantment</p>	<p>Stage 4 <u>REVIEW</u> Assessment of performance against policy and plan</p>
<p>Stage 5 <u>MATURITY OR DECLINE</u> Possible move to a more coherent, that is, pro-active, approach</p>	<p>Stage 5 <u>REDEFINITION OF OBJECTIVES/PLAN/POLICY</u> Process of continual improvement and the issues of quality this entails. Return to Stage 1 in cycle of growth and development</p>

Figure I.1.1.4 Reactive and Pro-active model of internationalisation
Source: Rudzki (1998, pp. 216, 218). Own elaboration.

When observing Figure I.1.1.4, again we find reference to the **cycle** when referring to internationalization, as developed and detailed in six steps: first produced by Knight (1994) and then added to in the same three stages by de Wit (2001). All of the steps describe what is ideally expected to be observed, that is, the presence of certain characteristics at the aforementioned **Time X** or the institutional stage that would facilitate the description and analysis of the path taken. But, they do not indicate whether or not within the same stage where the existence of the characteristic inside on each of the 9th stages presented would be expected; What one finds is the absence of the characteristic, which the

Author of this thesis identifies and interprets as the presence of rhetorical internationalization. This is particularly so when observing the persistence of the absence of the characteristic in a period of the aforementioned **Time N** where the HEI was definitely aiming at improving its process of internationalization, by integrating that desired dimension. Hence, there is the question of whether an HEI is truly aiming at improving its process per se or solely adjusting some “individual” and potentially insignificant activities within the ‘grand or larger Scheme of Things’.

One last contribution written by Hunter (2013) analyzes and describes what she calls “critical factors for institutional responsiveness” (p. 65) in exploring “strategic capacity for internationalisation as a response to the new higher education environment” (p. 61). What is interesting for the purposes of this PhD thesis is what she defines as *institutional resources*. These are considered here as enablers for the internationalization of HEIs.

Hunter refers to them as critical factors: (p. 61)

1. Environmental awareness as a means to set the framework for internationalisation and to legitimate the degree of change required.
2. The second factor lies in the institution’s own tools and resources –
 - a. strategic ability,
 - b. appropriate governance structures and
 - c. sound support in financial and human resources.
3. The third factor is leadership, not only in its ability to introduce, facilitate and embed changes but in its ability to imagine a future vision that not only inspires and engages the university community but enables institutions to become agents of their own change.

<i>Critical factors for institutional responsiveness</i>	<i>Main Characteristics</i>
1. Environmental awareness	The ability to understand current and future trends about the environment in which universities operate, or plan to, and the ability to exploit any external conditions or shifts to their advantage.
2. Institutional tools and resources	<p>Strategy: The university must make connections with human resources development clear in order to build capacity and long-term sustainability; it should also be linked to quality processes that measure both performance and stimulate continuous improvement and learning. <i>Simply articulating internationalization within the mission is not enough. The university must also demonstrate a strategic capacity to design an internationalization process and sustain it over time.</i></p> <p>Radical change is achieved only when the institutions develop a carefully planned strategy that will take them through a process of “logical incrementalism” but simultaneously stretch them beyond their current capabilities and resources.</p> <p>Structures: Whether internationalization becomes the new institutional direction or is fully integrated into the general strategy, it will require strong commitment and support from the top. The university needs to ensure the right conditions for realization by <i>adopting appropriate structures able to carry out and drive actions forward according to a carefully defined set of targets and timescales.</i></p> <p>They must act as agile organizations and develop managerial instruments in line with their declared mission.</p> <p>Support: If the strategy is to be implemented and embedded in the university, it must necessarily be underpinned by a sound financial plan in order to make necessary investments in people, structures and systems.</p>
3. Leadership (and the power of imagination)	<p>The leadership model should be one that is consensual and sensitive to the different disciplinary cultures if it is to be able to gain confidence in the community about the new direction, and to convince the latter to accept change and collaborate for its realization. It is leadership that draws on the community’s expertise and knowledge, facilitating and supporting change rather than acting as experts and authorities working in isolation and imposing decisions.</p> <p>While leadership initiates the process of change, it is institutional will that sustains it. The decision to internationalize is not only a question of changing processes and structures but is also about changing beliefs and behaviors.</p>

Table I.1.1.3 Critical factors for institutional responsiveness and Main characteristics

Source: Hunter (2013, pp. 65-69). Own elaboration.

Finally, de Wit (2011) and Knight (2015) wrote about myths and misconceptions behind the internationalization ideology. These are common mistakes that can sometimes drive one towards different misunderstandings when referring to – and also when carrying out – the process, whether one seeks to describe it, analyze it, measure it, or evaluate the strategy and actions, or manage it within an HEI.

On the other hand, presenting some strategy as a factor of success for the internationalization process needs to be understood as proof for the existence of a rhetorical stage. This is not because the practitioner did not read the above articles from the body of literature but rather in relation to the meaning of each factor, within the strategy selected at the institutional level.

De Wit describes nine *misconceptions*:

1. Internationalization is education in the English language
2. Internationalization is studying or staying abroad
3. Internationalization equals an international subject
4. Internationalization implies having many international students
5. Having a few international students in the classroom makes internationalization a real success
6. There is no need to test intercultural and international competencies specifically
7. The more partnerships there are, the more internationalization there is
8. Higher education is international by nature
9. Internationalization is a real goal in itself

Figure V

Source: de Wit (2011, pp. 11-17). Own elaboration.

Knight developed her thoughts about the five *myths* living within the idea of internationalization:

1. Foreign Students as Internationalization Agents
2. International Reputation as a Proxy for Quality
3. International Institutional Agreements
4. International Accreditation
5. Global Branding

Figure VI

Source: Knight (2015, pp. 14-15).

All the models presented above need to be read and understood based on a **process approach** which stresses that internationalization is a **continuous cycle** (de Wit, 2001, p. 115). With or without some characteristics that are mentioned above, internationalization will always accomplish a certain cycle. Knowing how to choose where to start, how to achieve that start, why it needs to be initiated, who needs to do what and for whom, and

the time necessary to undertake the process should be a task for those aiming at internationalization.

In other words, paraphrasing Zechlin (2010, pp. 4, 5), we can affirm that the reference to the actual internationalization should be:

The basic model for rational planning has come under heavy criticism for years, primarily because it places so much emphasis on planning [e.g., stage n° 3 on De Wit modified Cycle from Knight (1994)] while neglecting issues of implementation [stage n° 6 on De Wit modified Cycle from Knight] – the very issues that usually come to the fore during the execution phase of the plans. An analysis steered by experts and implemented by management [those longing a better level of internationality], the critics claim, assumes a division between thought and action that is not consonant with real life [rhetorical internationalization in pure state]. [The third stage] does not happen in isolation, but should be based on [analysis, awareness and commitment] actions and deliberate reflection [within the HEI for each group that makes up the HEI].

I.2 Rhetorical Internationalization

There are several theoretical approaches to define, describe, and analyze the process of internationalization as a unique concept. Whether a scholar or practitioner seeks to describe or analyze it, they will need to specify the term used to do so. As one can observe in the previous section “it has been and continues to be one of researchers’ most discussed elements (conspectus, p. 9)”.

Precisely, it is considered that there is no homogeneous and clear criterion regarding constructs and ways of implementing internationalization in higher education. In fact, a shared construct has not yet been established to theoretically conceptualize the phenomenon (Rojas Morales, 2022). Therefore, following Rojas Morales’ (2022) thoughts, the internationalization of higher education is interpreted and used based on the meaning given to it by the stakeholders, to some extent, because the actions proposed as internationalization practices are directed towards the established goal. Consequently, the existence of a difference between theory and practice is acknowledged.

It is important to understand that within the study of higher education discourse in general and specifically in the discourse of internationalization, they are key factors in advancing the definition and understanding of rhetorical internationalization as an additional element to consider when observing the existence of such disparities.

The study of higher education discourse offers valuable insights into the ways in which language, communication, and power dynamics shape the field of education. Discourse analysis has gained prominence as a research methodology for investigating the multifaceted dimensions of educational phenomena. Within the broader field of higher education, the discourse of internationalization has emerged as a key area of study,

reflecting the growing significance of global collaboration, student mobility, and cross-cultural engagement.

A. Higher Education Discourse:

Higher education discourse encompasses the various modes of communication, including written, oral, and digital, that influence and shape the field of higher education. It encompasses a wide range of actors, including policymakers, administrators, faculty, students, practitioners, scholars, and other stakeholders. The study of higher education discourse aims to examine the discursive practices, ideologies, power relations, and social constructions within the higher education landscape.

The study of higher education discourse is rooted in discourse theory, which examines the ways in which language shapes and constructs social reality. According to Foucault (1972), discourse is not simply a neutral medium for communication but a mechanism of power that organizes and regulates knowledge. In the context of higher education, discourse theory provides a framework for understanding how language constructs and perpetuates certain ideologies, hierarchies, and power relations.

The analysis of higher education discourse focuses on understanding the language used to construct and negotiate meanings, identities, and relationships in higher education. Discursive practices encompass a range of communicative acts, such as policy documents, institutional mission statements, curricula, classroom interactions, and academic writing. These practices reflect and reproduce the values, norms, and ideologies prevalent within higher education institutions.

Higher education discourse studies embraces a multidisciplinary approach, drawing upon various academic fields such as sociology, linguistics, anthropology, and education. It seeks to examine how language is used in higher education settings, the power dynamics inherent in educational discourses, and the ways in which discursive

practices shape educational policies and practices. As argued by Gee (1996), discourse refers to "a socially accepted association among ways of using language, other symbolic expressions, and artifacts of thinking" (pp. 131-132). Analyzing higher education discourse helps unveil the underlying assumptions, ideologies, and social structures that influence the production and dissemination of knowledge within educational institutions.

Thus, its analysis involves examining a wide range of textual and interactional resources, including policy documents, academic articles, lectures, interviews, institutional websites, and institutional practices. By analyzing these discursive practices, researchers gain insights into how higher education institutions construct and communicate knowledge, negotiate identities, and reproduce or challenge existing power structures. The study of higher education discourse is vital for understanding the dynamics of educational systems and facilitating transformative change.

B. Internationalization within Higher Education Discourse:

The internationalization of higher education involves incorporating and integrating international elements into a nation's higher education system, including curriculum, processes, and the core mission. However, scholars often face challenges when attempting to formulate a complete and comprehensive definition for internationalization. As one explores these diverse interpretations, it becomes evident that the internationalization of higher education extends beyond study abroad, student mobility, or exporting educational services. It now encompasses a wide range of activities conducted by institutions, governments, non-governmental organizations, and international organizations working together to advance international initiatives within the higher education sector (Crystle, 2020).

The study of higher education discourse and the discourse of internationalization provide valuable insights into the complexities, power dynamics, and socio-cultural

dimensions of higher education systems in a globalized world. By critically examining these discourses, researchers, practitioners, and policymakers can develop a deeper understanding of the challenges and opportunities associated with internationalizing higher education institutions. It is through the analysis and exploration of higher education discourse that one can strive for more inclusive, equitable, and socially just educational practices on a global scale.

The discourse of internationalization in higher education explores the ways in which institutions navigate the complexities of globalization, cross-cultural interactions, and the international mobility of students, faculty, and ideas. Internationalization is no longer limited to a single institution, country, or region; it has become a global phenomenon with multifaceted implications.

Though, involves the ways in which internationalization is conceptualized, discussed, and implemented within institutions. It encompasses a range of activities, including the recruitment of international students, faculty and staff mobility, curriculum internationalization, and the development of global partnerships. Different conceptualizations of internationalization exist, ranging from instrumental and economic perspectives to more transformative and critical approaches that emphasize intercultural learning, global citizenship, and social justice.

Still, Knight (2004) broad definition of internationalization highlights the diverse strategies and objectives pursued by institutions to internationalize their campuses. As Watkins (p.16, 2021) explains, the concept of internationalization as an integrative process for institutions is continuous throughout the literature. The discourse of internationalization encompasses a wide range of topics, including curriculum internationalization, international student recruitment, study abroad programs, faculty mobility, and the internationalization of research and innovation.

Scholars such as De Wit (2011) emphasize the multidimensionality of internationalization, arguing that it involves academic, cultural, and social aspects. Critical perspectives have also emerged, with scholars like Marginson (2014) examining the potential neoliberal influences on internationalization, particularly regarding the marketization of education and the commodification of knowledge.

Thus, the reference to the term **internationalization** presented before is a construction through Knight (1994, p. 3) and Brandenburg and Federkeil (2007, p. 7) definitions.

Yet, some explanation about rhetoric within the field of internationalization is needed. First, the dilemma about the *rhetoric* and its dynamics through history was considered for this research thesis solely to trace and follow the pattern behind the process. The evidence of this was particularly sought in this thesis research. Inside the internationalization field in order to contextualize where those expressions were partially supposed to be a field reality explanation regarding the internationalization process.

Second, the rhetoric has been identified and researched before, according to the body of literature. Some scholars (e.g., Biddle, 2002; Schoorman, 2000; Söderqvist, 2002; Bull, 2004) have written more on the subject; some have solely noted its existence without giving it more attention other than a few lines in their work (e.g. Hudzik, 2011; de Wit, 2001; Davies, 1992, 1995; etc.). However, to the best of our knowledge, none of them have tried to measure it. This is probably because the devices used have been complicated to trace, due to data reliability, or just because it might be time consuming work, which does demonstrate the discourse on internationalization might be hard – or even impossible – to test or demonstrate to the same people using it, whether it is written or spoken.

As Suddaby and Greenwood (2005) have explained “rhetoric, and particularly “new rhetoric” (Freedman & Medway, 1994), restricts its focus to explicitly political or interest-laden discourse and seeks to identify genres or recurrent patterns of interests, goals, and shared assumptions that become embedded in persuasive texts” (Freedman & Medway, 1994).

One needs to remember that these words also apply to those scholars who research the field. Whether they analyze the process or not at certain points they do find the existence of rhetorical discourse, although they probably do not find the evidence of this rhetoric within the internationalization process. The Author of this thesis certainly does not know and to the best of our knowledge other researchers/authors likely do not know either.

Returning to the words of Brandenburg and Federkeil (2007) regarding HEIs, before developing or using any indicators, researchers and institutions must engage themselves in “setting internationality goals and draw(ing) up a strategy of how to achieve these goals” (p. 10).

According to the above authors, following these steps includes:

- a. Defining internationalization targets,
- b. Developing a coherent internationalization strategy - leading to describing targets and measures.
- c. Compiling a catalogue of short-, medium- and long-term measures to ensure the internationalization strategy’s implementation and realization.
- d. Developing a quality management system that:
 - a. Effectively accompanies the implementation of measures and adjusts them if necessary.
 - b. Documenting and analyzing its influence on strategy targets (p. 10).

This last point should be taken into account when advancing the present proposal. Thus, it is important to reiterate the description of Hunter (2013) regarding the results of her case studies (p. 66):

In the case studies, the national context had been relatively stable for a number of years and universities were typically positioned in box C. Each university found that its own niche and lack of strong external drivers had led to complacency and lack of dynamism. However, when the external drivers changed, they needed to accelerate the internal dynamics to move from C to B in order to reposition themselves to the most favorable conditions available. Where internal dynamics had consolidated toward a more static culture, the response was not rapid or creative enough; and as the speed of change accelerated, the result was a drift to D, the least favorable position of all.

All of the above should be identified and understandable as reliable information when one analyzes the internationalization process of any HEI. If internationalization were a more successful descriptive science, one could simply test the accuracy of its general rules, and different representations of the same rules, or theories, would only have limited impact.

This means that rhetorical issues will be found at every stage and quadrant. However, the difference will be the amount of rhetoric found within the identified process. Finally, all of these are ground-based representations, and they need to be thought of as dynamically as possible.

There are no 100% grounded realities matching the ideal described by any scholar. What one can find are descriptions and analyses based on case studies or idealistic grounded predictions about the future process of internationalization in HEIs. To the best of our knowledge, there is not one case in the field of internationalization

where the description of the ideal is equal to the process in the HEI. Adding the rhetorical internationalization, searching for the amount of its magnitude within the process, will probably diminish the gap between the **ideal reality** and the **grounded reality**.

What follows is a description of rhetorical stages and their current relations within the model, and a guide on how to read, interpret, and understand the analysis (or observation) of the model when analyzing any IRO (i.e., considered to be the organizational unit/organ for managing the process and its cycle) in any HEI.

The **First Stage or the pure Rhetorical Stage** is characterized by an absence of an organizational unit working specifically for international subjects. Activities related to the international dimension will be distributed randomly without any explanation for an institutional tie. However, it will be possible to identify a few “individual” international activities, perhaps as a reaction to the interests and/or expectations of others. Thus, it will be possible to find written news, short messages, congresses, seminars, and summer or winter schools, that have been completed and subsequently reported on. This will be, however, through non-specific links within the university’s mission, strategy, or present-future plan. Indeed, the answer for internationalization should be found in “other” expectations, programs, plans, and interests.

At this point, any single opportunity falling upon the institution to “internationalize” something without an internal effort (e.g., budget, time, human resources) will be considered as part of the process. Awareness, commitment, and plans will be out-of-the-box (i.e., functions immediately) in this case. Documentary and statistical information relating to the institution’s approach to internationalization (Middlehurst, 2008, p. 13) are significant both in what they say and whatever they omit/neglect to say, and there will be no sign of the latter at this stage.

The entire cycle is embedded by rhetorical internationalization however which is not a problem. The problem arises when the level and influence capacity within the strategy at the ground level are too blurry to be identified and measured but remain constant over time. Rhetorical internationalization shifts from being a device which is believed to support the process to being a factor within the process. Thus, interests and expectations are just added into the ongoing process.

Figure 1.1.2.1 Interest inputs on Rhetorical Internationalization (IntZ) Model
Source: Own elaboration.

I.3 Methodological issues

The purpose of this qualitative study based on the **Grounded Theory** tradition will be to explore and describe the existence of a phenomenon called **Rhetorical Internationalization** for HEIs in Argentina (which fulfill the criteria of having been members of an EMA2 and which received support from the national government to generate or strengthen their internationalization). The period comprises the years between 2005 and 2015.

Qualitative research is a holistic approach that involves discovery. It is also described as an effective model occurring in a natural setting, enabling the researcher to develop a detailed understanding by being highly involved in actual experiences (Creswell, 2003).

If a concept or phenomenon needs understanding because little research has been done on it, then it merits a qualitative approach. Qualitative research is exploratory and is useful when the researcher when the researcher is not able to identify variables to examine with unquestionable certainty important variables to examine. This type of approach may be necessary when the topic is new, it has never been addressed within a certain sample or group of people, and existing theories do not apply to the particular sample or group under study (Morse, 1991). (IN: Creswell, p. 35, 2009)

The initial stage of observation leads to questions that the researcher attempts to explain. The strong correlation between the observer and the data is a marked difference. There is no beginning point of truth or any established assumptions from which the researcher can begin (Leedy and Ormrod, 2001). Typically, empirical research collects data reflected by the senses and is used to explain phenomena relevant to social behaviors

in new and emerging theories. The intent of qualitative research is to establish the detailed meaning of information (Creswell, 2012).

Creswell (2003) describes how these methods — as procedures or techniques used to collect and/or analyze data — meet different needs. For instance, case studies and grounded theory research explore processes, activities, and events, while ethnographic research analyzes broad cultural-sharing behaviors of individuals or groups. Case studies, as well as phenomenology, can be used to study individuals.

Qualitative research aims to obtain a full picture of an issue according to the human perspective studied. Qualitative research relates to ideas, perceptions, opinions, or beliefs of the person being studied, and none of them can be measured by numbers.

According to Creswell (2012), qualitative research is a means for exploring and understanding the meaning individuals or groups ascribe to a social human problem. The research process involves emerging questions and procedures, collecting data in the participant's setting, analyzing the data inductively — building from particulars to general themes — and making interpretations of the meaning of the data. Thus, the final written report has a flexible writing structure.

The qualitative researcher is the instrument of research themselves. Being an instrument, the researcher must have a broad theory and insight, so that they are able to ask, analyze, photograph, and construct the social situation under study to become clearer and more meaningful.

In qualitative research, the study's design is inherently emergent, allowing for flexibility and adaptation throughout the research process. Unlike rigidly predefined plans, the emergent design acknowledges the dynamic nature of inquiry and recognizes that unforeseen circumstances may necessitate adjustments to methodology, data collection techniques, or even research questions. This iterative approach enables us to

remain responsive to the evolving needs and realities of the research context (Creswell, 2003).

This qualitative study considers that:

In the social sciences today there is no longer a God's-eye view that guarantees absolute methodological certainty. All inquiry reflects the standpoint of the inquirer. All observation is theory-laden. There is no possibility of theory or value-free knowledge. The days of naive realism and naive positivism are over. The criteria for evaluating research are now relative (Cannella et al., 2016, p. 40).

Thus, qualitative inquiry can contribute to identifying different internationalization definitions or re-definitions. In doing so, the Author of this PhD thesis has sought the path to enlighten future questions and critical research, through the words of Cannella et al. (2016, p. 41):

...critical methodologies are attentive to issues that come up in the larger research design, methods, reflexivity, and dissemination strategies and, as such, might change the direction of the research in unanticipated ways. A researcher must be ready to make change based on the context as critical research is implicitly iterative. In their description of a bricoleur, Kincheloe et al., (2012) posit that one views research methods actively rather than passively, meaning that we actively construct our research methods from the tools at hand rather than passively receiving the "correct," universally applicable methodologies. [Thus] Avoiding modes of reasoning that come from certified processes of logical analysis (p. 160).

Internationalization research is by nature multidisciplinary. Presenting a picture or accurate description of the phenomenon of internationalization from the perspective of only one of the fields connected to it might (or should) generate an absence of information between the reality and the proposed work presented.

The process of data analysis involves making sense out of text and image data. It entails preparing the data for analysis, conducting various analyses, delving deeper into understanding the data, representing the data, and interpreting the larger meaning of the

data. It is an ongoing process involving continual reflection about the data, asking analytic questions, and writing memos throughout the study. Qualitative data analysis is conducted concurrently with gathering data, making interpretations, and writing reports (Creswell, 2009). Many qualitative researchers also use visuals (e.g., Knight, De Wit, Davies, Hudzik, Rudzki), figures, or tables as adjuncts to the discussions. They present a process model (as in grounded theory), advance a drawing of the specific research site (as in ethnography), or convey descriptive information about each participant in a table (as in case studies and ethnographies) (Creswell, 2009).

Therefore, in this doctoral research a constant comparison of the data collected was carried out in a first step in order to explore the data and analyze the HEIs included in this process (Glasser & Strauss, 1967).

By combining ... methods of analysis, each with its own theoretical orientations, we sought to resist theoretical determinism while trying on new possibilities reflective of critical inquiry's emancipatory and empowering objectives (Brown & Strega, 2005; Kincheloe & McLaren, 2005). This *combination of multiple lenses was also meant to strengthen the trustworthiness of the study*. (Pasque & Rex, 2010, p. 71) [Bold and italic formats added by the Author of this thesis].

Accepted methods for developing a grounded theory include content analysis as a method which is independent of a theoretical perspective or framework (Given, 2008). Thus, qualitative content analysis can be helpful in answering questions of why a phenomenon occurs. In qualitative research, content analysis is interpretive, involving a close reading of the text. Qualitative researchers using a content analytical approach recognize that a text is open to subjective interpretation, that it reflects multiple meanings, and that its context dependent (Given, 2008, p. 120).

In other words, supporting the idea developed within this PhD thesis:

...there is a general correspondence between knowledge and "reality", but reality can be perceived, described, and interpreted in a variety of different ways. There is no single

criterion of truth acceptable in all cultures, and scientific concepts, theories, paradigms, tests, judgments, and so on are simply conventions approved by the scientific community. However, this does not mean that these conventions are either arbitrary or lax: On the contrary, they derive from stringent rules and procedures that cannot easily be mastered or changed. Science is based on order, continuity, authority and control, and while it is neither rigid nor inflexible the scope for novelty and innovation is strictly limited by the recognized conventions (tradition) and by the specific circumstances of the scientist's field. Tradition governs the accepted theories, methods, and techniques in any discipline, and also the selection, training, qualification, and socialization of recruits (Klamer, McCloskey, and Solow, 1988, p. 68).

Furthermore, “a static terminology is not well suited to the study of dynamic phenomena”. However, internationalization as a phenomenon should demonstrate a widely open list of terminology, with different perspectives and different meanings (Klamer et al., 1988, p. 73).

Therefore, the result of the research conducted using qualitative approach in this PhD thesis is obtaining a real analysis of the internationalization process, knowing that it is a model which does not fit every situation equally. The main objective of the methodology used in this thesis, through the study of social phenomena in natural contexts, is to generate theories that explain the studied phenomenon.

In Friedman’s usage, any implication of a theory whose truth is not yet known counts as a prediction of a theory, even if it is not concerned with the future. Since the goals of science are exclusively predictive, a theory which enables one to make reliable predictions is a good theory. In case of a tie on the criterion of predictive success, simpler theories or theories of wider scope (that apply to a wider range of phenomena) are to be preferred (p. 10).

Friedman stresses that there is no other test of a theory in terms of whether its “assumptions” are “unrealistic” (p. 14). When Friedman speaks of the “assumptions” of a theory, he includes both fundamental assertions...and additional premises needed in particular applications...Although Friedman equivocates with the term “unrealistic”, usually he means...that an assumption is unrealistic if it is not true, perhaps not even

approximately true, of the phenomena to which the theory is applied (Hausman, 1989, p. 120).

Grounded Theory aims to allow researchers to discover theories, concepts, and propositions starting directly from the data and not from the priori assumptions of other investigations or existing theoretical frameworks. Therefore, in the case of Argentine PUs, they could be analyzed as a sample from a dynamic international base, and from a stable national context with certain advances.

The absence of a support model that would allow adding or incorporating the collected data in itself made up the elements that were involved in the elaboration of this exploratory stage. This was in order to facilitate an analysis of the identified issue, given that the issue was absent during the literature review process. It was not possible to find a model that facilitated comparison, inclusion, or exclusion at any stage of the internationalization process - identified in the sample - as it was absent in the reality presented by the HEIs.

The existence of a category named rhetorical internationalization was generated when the stage or category where an HEI was located was created, given its reality. In other words, to the extent that progress was made in the attempt to compare the collected information to find new patterns of behavior and identify new or different events, the constant comparative method was implied.

Despite constraints of research design, verificational researchers, for their part, sometimes serendipitously observe regularities leading to generalizations about the group, process, activity, or situation they are investigating. (Given, 2008, p. 327).

This ended up being a reality in the present work, given that the collection of data, between October 2014 and March 2015, led the Author to identify an element which had to be incorporated when analyzing the internationalization process. This was thanks to

the presence - despite the international and national issues - of the same element within the studied period and within the sphere that the methodology itself determined for Argentina.

Furthermore, here, as already noted by Gilboa (2012, para. 31) “we hold that axioms might be important rhetorical devices also for descriptive theories, that is, theories that are interpreted as a depiction of reality.” The material planned and necessary to complete the fieldwork did not have the expected result, leading to a combination of the aforementioned negative response with the search for direct information through the websites of the analyzed agents.

Indeed, considering the quote of Hausman (1989) from Friedman (1953):

“a “theory is to be judged by its predictive power for the class of phenomena which it is intended to explain” (p. 8). He stresses Friedman’s idea “that all one wants of science are theories that work for particular purposes.” (p. 121).

Thus, researchers of internationalization should not be interested in what HEIs say, but in the consequences of what they do to internationalize themselves, though surveys and interviews might be considered irrelevant. (Hausman, 1989, p. 121).

Then, we consider what Cohen, Yemini and Sadeh (2014, p. 28) stated:

Brandenburg and Federkeil (2007) claimed that only those indicators that measure only what needs to be measured should be included, without [collecting] invaluable or [useless] data (construct validity). In addition, reliability is critical: measurements should be gathered periodically and, when the basic data has not changed, they should always provide the same results ... They proposed that institutions’ websites can be used as a source of information for internationalization assessment while the use of those websites will increase the applicability of the tool, regardless of which set of indicators is selected.

Thus, following Cohen et al. (2014, p. 28):

Universities, as institutions of higher education and culture, are well aware of the opportunities the Internet brings ... most are committed, in principle, to marketing their

institutions to foreign students and to promoting international contact (Altbach, 2004; Ho et al., 2010). The university homepage is usually the first contact point for anybody who seeks Online information about the university. It is inevitable for the university to develop a dynamic homepage that captures the attention of its users and meets their informational needs.

In particular, [universities'] web visibility ... has become critically appreciated in that the Internet has played a key role in forging the academic and educational competences of universities across countries through various e-learning programs and open sources for cutting-edge knowledge produced by higher education institutions (Ortega & Aguillo, 2009). **University administrators** have also started to recognize the university website as an important channel to increase institutional reputation and organizational image and spread knowledge produced by universities to global communities (Masterson, 2011). Indeed, *institutional websites have become an online mirror of the institutional environment, reflecting ongoing activities and presenting institutional values, vision and mission accompanied with large amounts of data regarding every aspect of institutional life.* [Bold and italic formats added by the Author of this thesis].

In fact, as de Wit (2005) indicates, the methodology used for studies in each country were a combination of different sources - in which web sites were also incorporated. Within the Argentine case, the analysis of smaller surveys is made. “*The paucity of data regarding internationalization* made collecting information a challenge for all of the contributors. For that reason, *the emphasis is on the qualitative rather than quantitative analysis of information*” (p. XIV). [bold and italic added by the Author of this thesis].

Taking into account all the factors mentioned and considering what is done in the HEIs rather than what is said, is the investigative and analytical aim of this PhD research. The initial position was modified to consider in which direction the HEIs were moving and if they were moving at all. This included Argentina's HEIs in terms of internationalization; their location in order to explore whether they moved at all and where they moved to); the type of internationalization management that was being carried

out - with the existence or lack of variations in the actors that collaborated in this process
- and in what institutional locations the actors were found to understand the general picture, thus, making it possible to compare between the different pictures. Potentially, researchers would be able to consider observing this dynamic in the future, comparing it with the same dynamics in other countries, or specifically within Argentina.

Thus, the candidate explores when he possesses little or no scientific knowledge about the group, process, activity, or situation he wants to examine but nevertheless has reason to believe it contains elements worth discovering. To explore a given phenomenon effectively, he must approach it with two special orientations: flexibility in looking for data and open-mindedness about where to find it. *Oriented this way, the first step is to try to acquire an intimate firsthand understanding of the group being observed. It follows that the most efficacious approach is to search for this understanding wherever it may be found ... The outcome of these procedures, and the main goal of exploratory research, is the production of inductively derived generalizations about the group, process, activity, or situation under study. The author then weaves these generalizations into what Barney Glaser and Anselm Strauss referred to as “grounded theory,” which explains the object of study. Such a theory is founded on direct observation of social phenomena.* (Given, 2008, p. 327).

Here one refers to the text of Gilboa once again but applies his thought to the selected path within a framework of qualitative research, outlined to analyze and investigate internationalization (2012, para. 32):

If [internationalization] were a more successful descriptive science...one could simply test the accuracy of its general rules, and different representations of the same rules, or theories, would have but limited impact. However, precisely because [internationalization] is not so successful, and because it is often a case-based “pre-science” rather than a rule-based science, understanding the foundations of [our model] is of paramount importance. Where the main test of models is our own intuition and similarity judgment, rather than hard evidence, foundations are key.

The understanding of these steps generated a global perspective with which to determine how to think of the internationalization as an umbrella and then make this process comparable within the national system. The Author assumes that internationalization is a dynamic and managed step, where the HEI assumes control of internationalization itself, while managing over time the steps to improve its own process of internationalization.

Using these criteria during the collecting phase of this PhD research was in retrospect one of the main challenges. On the one hand, due to the autarky (i.e., national economic self-sufficiency) and autonomy (i.e., acting/functioning independently) of the PU in Argentina, the development of each structure in the group was considered equal from the beginning of this PhD research, even though structures receive different names and the main activities are directly or indirectly related to the internationalization process. On the other hand, to develop this PhD research, the Author made the decision to focus on the managerial level, in consideration of the fact that, to the best of our knowledge, scholars tend to internationalize themselves with or without the support of the Faculties or the university.

However, in this thesis the focus on the managerial level was the guidance towards understanding the types of decisions and movements undertaken within the PU in their internationalization process. Further, each university develops and manages its own 'window to the world' which appears to be reliable due to the fact of institutions having a web page (Cohen, Yemini, & Sadeh, 2014).

Management is a decisive factor for the process of internationalization, defining not only the management staff of the HEI, but also comprises all tasks and structures associated with the management of a HEI (Brandenburg & Federkeil, 2007, p. 13). The path built throughout by the managers is not replaceable. One should reflect upon whether

each specific step will or will not improve the link to the internationalization of the institution.

While faculties, units, and institutes might develop their own processes, in order to develop a comprehensive process across the whole institution, one must find this definition embedded in and shared by the HEI. However, during the earlier research stage of this thesis it was common to find via its absence whether or not a public strategy or an institutional strategy was communicated by the PU.

Chapter II: The European path

II.1 A general review of the Erasmus tool

As reflected in the Commission of the European Communities document, ERASMUS Newsletter, it was correctly indicated that:

May 14th 1987 will go down in the history books as a milestone in the development of the Community as a whole. When the Education Ministers of the 12 Member States, meeting in Brussels, reached agreement on the ERASMUS Programme (the European Community Action Scheme for the Mobility of University Students). (1987, p. 1).

From its very beginnings ERASMUS has been thought of as an instrument in the process of continuous development for EU Member States, their HEIs, and their citizens.

Hence, it was indicated that it:

constitutes a comprehensive instrument for developing a wide range of inter-university cooperative activities, on a voluntary basis, between all Community countries. The main objective of the programme is to help boost student mobility between the twelve Member States well above its present unsatisfactory level, by providing far more students than hitherto with the possibility of spending a recognized period of study in another Community country. The significant increase in the number of graduates with first-hand experience of other Member States to which this will give rise, will not only be a cornerstone in the construction of the People's Europe, as indicated above. It will also be an essential component in helping to raise the awareness of interdependence within the Community, thereby contributing to the completion and consolidation of the internal market which will be the key to ensuring EC competitiveness on the world stage in the years ahead.

Starting a path that was chosen more than three decades ago and one which will continue to be followed by the EU Member States and their HEIs is an advancement within the search processes, an advance in the quality of the process, and an improvement

in definitions used in order to make progress in their own internationalization. Taking the existence of a program of intra-community mobility at the undergraduate student level is a distinctive element of the region in order to advance the mobility of teachers, researchers, and staff. The first positive step for the development of the European Program, that would improve cooperation between HEI and facilitate mobility among its citizens throughout the 12 member states, had been given beyond **rhetoric**. With it, an economic support structure was also created - which has persisted and accompanied each time the EU borders and the Erasmus borders were extended - and its growth was foreseen with a clear future objective: “*key to ensuring EC competitiveness on the world stage in the years ahead*”.

By way of synthesis - it is not the intention of this research thesis to analyze the more than 30 years of the Erasmus Program in detail. The actions contemplated in its bases are presented here:

- 1- European University Network with grants to higher education institutions to facilitate the planning, development, operation, maintenance, monitoring and evaluation of inter-university programs for the exchange of students and teaching staff; ... to help cover the travel and subsistence expenses of staff members carrying out teaching assignments in another Member State; ... and to facilitate visits to other Member States by members of the teaching and administrative staff of higher education institutions with a view to establishing contacts for future cooperative programs and/or for the purpose of acquainting themselves more thoroughly with aspects of the higher education system in the countries visited. (p. 2).
- 2- Students Grants to help cover the ‘mobility costs’ (travel, language preparation, cost-of-living differential, etc.) of students spending a fully recognized period of study in another Community country. Prioritizing students participating in programmes funded under the European University Network.
- 3- Academic Recognition, with the establishment of a pilot scheme for the academic recognition of degrees and course units, known as the European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS); Consolidation of the EC Network of National

Academic Recognition Information Centres (NARIC); and yearly grants for the development of common curricula between HEIs in different Member States.

- 4- Additional Measures, grants to facilitate ‘Intensive Teaching Programmes’; to university associations and consortia operating on a European basis; Support to enable top-level experts to give a series of lectures in other Member States; Publications and other information measures designed to raise awareness of opportunities for study and teaching in other Community countries; and Prizes for students and HE staff members who make contributions to furthering inter-university cooperation in the Community. (pp. 2,3).

Teichler (2009) wrote that “ERASMUS was a trigger for a qualitative leap of internationalisation strategies and policies since the 1990s: towards cooperation and mobility on equal terms, and towards systematic and strategic internationalisation”. Though, one might say, HEIs followed that path with the aim of generating, strengthening, and promoting said qualitative leap including within their institutional structures. (Pérez, 2018).

As Teichler (2009) indicates, this qualitative leap had its support in a milestone for the European Higher Education system - and for the entire world’s higher education system - as a result of the Sorbonne Joint Declaration of 1998, the agreement which exists among the ministers of education of Germany, the United Kingdom, France, and Italy. This declaration concurred “that the segmentation of the European higher education sector in Europe was outdated and harmful” and it led to these countries’ commitment to create the European Higher Education Area (EHEA). The latter was formalized one year later through The Bologna Declaration. (Secretariat, 2009, p. 3):

the Bologna Process was meant to strengthen the competitiveness and attractiveness of European higher education and to foster student mobility and employability through the introduction of a system based on undergraduate and postgraduate studies with easily readable programmes and degrees (Secretariat, 2009, p. 3).

In 2003, the Official Journal announced the “*establishment of a program for improving the quality of higher education and the promotion of intercultural understanding through the cooperation with third countries*” (European Parliament and the Council of the European Union, 2003). A single explicit reference to internationalization is highlighted in the aforementioned communication:

In its communication on reinforcing cooperation with third countries in the field of higher education, the Commission argued that greater internationalisation of higher education is necessary to respond to the challenges of the process of globalisation, identified overall objectives for a third-country cooperation strategy in this field and suggested concrete measures for achieving these objectives. (DECISION No 2317/2003/EC, p. 1).

Within the Lisbon European Council presidency conclusions in year 2000, the following was emphasized, “if Europe is to meet the challenge of globalization, Member States need to adapt their education”. Advancements were made upon the path initiated in previous meetings, such as Prague 2001 and Berlin 2003, which at that time gave sustenance to generate an instrument that would face the process of globalization in the context of the European Union. It would serve in particular to strengthen ties of cooperation with third countries in the field of Higher Education in order to promote “the attractiveness of the European Higher Education Area” as Communiqué (2001) and Communiqué (2003) highlighted.

The main objective of both the Parliament and the Council was defined as the improvement of higher education quality within the European Union. (Pérez, 2018, p. 51). However, in order to advance along this path, the EU launched the call for proposal EACEA/35/2008 to implement the Erasmus Mundus External Cooperation Window in the 2009/2010 academic year. This was open to different regions and countries, such as Argentina, which received the chance through a bilateral window within the program.

Its objectives were:

The Erasmus Mundus External Cooperation Window aims at mutual enrichment and better understanding between the European Union and Third Countries. It is designed to foster institutional co-operation in the field of higher education between the European Union and Third Countries through a mobility scheme addressing student and academic exchanges for the purpose of studying, teaching, training and research. (p.C 328/24).

This communication summarized several of the objectives and results that the EU hoped to achieve through the Program. Among them, we can highlight the Erasmus Mundus Action 2 Partnerships: “1. The Community shall select partnerships of high academic quality ... (b) implement a partnership as a basis for the transfer of know-how” (L 340/95) indicating that this knowledge would be transferred as part of the actions that were implemented to carry out the partnerships.

In this framework, it is important to note that “the Commission, after consultation with the competent authorities in the third countries concerned through its delegations, shall define national and regional priorities according to the needs of the specific third country/ies concerned by the partnerships.” (L340 / 95) It was not possible to access specific information to confirm or refute such a consultation with some Argentine stakeholders who responded differently - even ignoring participation - as can be seen in the next section.

When specifically analyzing the Program Guide in detail where it is possible to find all the information necessary for applying EMA2s1, one can observe that among other points, it is enunciated once more as part of the of EMA2 - STRAND 1’s third specific objectives, “To contribute towards the development of human resources and the international cooperation capacity of higher education institutions in third countries”. (Programme Guide, p. 49) Furthermore, it is expected that the implementation of the

program shall contribute to “Promoting the development of third countries.”(Programme Guide, p.49)

All of the above rests upon the assumption that benefits are transferred on behalf of those who have been mobilized to the areas where they would carry out their activities. At some point there would be an analysis that would grant the individual greater value with an alleged value added for the institutional development of Argentina’s HEIs - in this case - that would benefit both because of the target group 1 (TG1) applicants linked to the partners HEI of the consortiums, as well as the individuals of target group 2 (TG2) not linked with partners. They would all contribute as a whole with the possibility of developing or improving cooperation capacity and promoting the development of third parties in third countries.

(Teichler, 2009)

“ERASMUS activities had existed for some time and had grown in size, questions arose as to whether one has to move from a pioneering stage to a stage of normalisation and routinisation. The [*individual*] pioneers got tired or retired. The activities needed continuity and could not be left at the mercy of the coincidental strengths and weaknesses of the pioneers. Questions were asked such as the following: Does [*individual*] experience permit us to mainstream the activities? Can the activities be undertaken more efficiently through [*institutional*] coordination and economy of scale? Should individual [*reactive*] initiatives be replaced by continuous departmental or institutional responsibilities? Is there a need for prioritisation? Does having a common institutional profile of international activities help individual activities? Many institutions opted for systematic [*and pro-active*] approaches, notably in three respects:

- Regulation of responsibilities and modes of decision making regarding international issues were established at many institutions of higher education. For example, vice-presidents were assigned the task of coordinating international issues. Committees for international affairs were set up, or committees primarily responsible for other tasks were entrusted with the additional task of taking care of international matters. Similarly, at the departmental level, deans began explicitly taking care of these tasks, or staff responsible for international matters were appointed.

- International activities are more complicated than national activities. Internationalisation is not conceivable without the extension of services. Institutions vary, of course, regarding what they do regarding foreign language training, accommodation for foreign scholars and students, information and administrative support, counselling, etc., but they were at least doing something about these things.
- Many higher education institutions created new international offices, or extended their existing offices (Maiworm et al., 1996). At most institutions, international offices play a double role, both providing services for regular international activities and preparing and implementing international strategies.

At the end of the 1990s, higher education institutions varied substantially in the extent to which their steps towards a regular and systematic treatment of international matters could be characterised as a coherent and targeted policy, or even a strategy, although moves in that direction have obviously increased. (pp. 100, 101).

According to the EACEA, within the framework of the call, 262 consortia were approved. Following Perez (2018), “one could say that EMA2S1 has had a low impact in shaping Europe’s *internationalization* process. It is noteworthy, however, that it has accentuated the capacity and knowhow of a reduced set of European HEIs to benefit from that funding.” While there “was an instrument created to strengthen the Internationalization of European Higher Education. It was thought that it would be able to convert Europe into a higher education destination of significant international quality. Furthermore, granting the Mundus label to those HEIs best able to confirm internationalization qualities and skills was thought to be advantageous.” (p. 53).

As Teichler (2009) concludes, ERASMUS generated more than a leap in Europe, it pushed forward a process opened in 1987 and all the activities which were carried out within it.

Cooperation and mobility on equal terms turn out to be a creative challenge to reconsider one’s own activities in every respect. It also has led to the systematic embedding of international activities into the general activities of higher education institutions: efforts are increasingly made to shape international activities into mainstream activities and to

ensure that the mainstream activities are developed in such a way that they serve the international activities. These achievements were reached in a period when special emphasis was placed on student mobility within Europe. (p. 104).

Conclusively, as noted by Perez (2018), applying the Matthew Effect (i.e., The Gospel of St Matthew notes that for to all those who have, more will be given; Matthew 25:29) to the ERASMUS Mundus Action2 Strand1, “the creation of the European Union’s internationalization is part of a reality that should be currently addressed to avoid further disputes over Erasmus+... the EU is peculiar in the matter of how it gives support. It tends to give opportunities to [already] strong HEIs.” (p. 57).

II.2 Argentina's Eight Erasmus Mundus Action 2 Strand 1 Projects

As noted in the previous section, each call for proposals that gave support to the projects contained a fundamental aspect for the European HEIs, through which the European Union would be the beneficiary in the long term. This was despite the fact that one could indicate that the favored candidates were the Argentine HEIs, since the mobilities corresponded to a flow from Argentina to Europe only.

On the other hand, it is understood from the reading and analysis of the call for proposals that the Argentine partners would be directly benefitted in their internationalization process as well as in the management of their cooperation activities, in particular with respect to the sphere of European HEIs. This is due to the *transfer of know-how* (p. L340.95) from the EU HEIs to Argentine HEIs as already described in this thesis.

In order to define and identify the specific characteristics of what happened, an analysis of the summaries of the projects (EACEA website) was carried out during this PhD research with the purpose of reading in detail what they indicated as each of the projects' objectives, regardless of the specific number of individual opportunities. This is because, as can be seen in Figure 1.1.2.1 of this thesis (i.e., Chapter 1.2 Rhetorical Internationalization), the process is understood to be at the institutional level and not at the level of the individuals within the institution.

In particular, if we understand, as noted in the detail of the calls, that Argentine partners did not have the possibility of making specific adjustments or formulations, but they fulfilled the role of partners, in the words of Rudzki (1998) they only reacted by way of the 'call to traction'. However, Davies included many of the partners in quadrants A or B.

If, on the other hand, we aim to apply the cycle used by Wit (2001), we could say that there was no real possibility of using it when analyzing participation, since there was no real possibility of modifying the proposal. Planning, implementing, monitoring, and evaluating responded to the terms of reference of the call; the HEI coordinator responded to this and it was dealt with by paying special attention to accountability to the EACEA. The impact and post-evaluation would seek to observe the compliance detail of the individual places, the reason for the actual call for proposal, and not the objectives described in each of the projects, as can be seen below.

Finally, in this thesis research, before reviewing each project and its objectives, a consultation was made requesting more information referring to each of the projects, with the aim of knowing the final reports that are mandatory. Unfortunately, this information is not public access and the contact made to the EACEA requesting the same had a refusal as a response.

What follows is a presentation of each project according to the information that the EACEA provides via its website, together with the list of Partner Universities; and a summary is added where the proposed objectives of each project are highlighted as a result of the analysis of the project summary sheets.

II.2. a) Rationales and b) Objectives

CALL in YEAR 2009

1. EADIC:

Reference: EACEA/35/08- L16 (Argentina)

Title: Europe and Argentina for Development Innovation and Change (EADIC)

Beneficiary organization: UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA, Italy

Argentine Partners	European Partners
UNIVERSIDAD DE BUENOS AIRES	UNIVERSITY OF ANTWERPEN, Belgium
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DEL CENTRO DE LA PROVINCIA DE BUENOS AIRES	KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT LEUVEN, Belgium
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE QUILMES	UNIVERSITE DE LILLE 1, France
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE SAN LUIS	KARL-FRANZENS- UNIVERSITÄT GRAZ, Austria
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE TUCUMAN	UNIVERSIDAD DE VALLADOLID, Spain
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE ROSARIO	UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI PADOVA, Italy
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DEL COMAHUE	FRIEDRICH-SCHILLER- UNIVERSITÄT JENA, Germany
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DEL LITORAL	UNIVERSIDADE DE COIMBRA, Portugal
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE SALTA	UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA, Spain
UNIVERSIDAD TECNOLÓGICA NACIONAL	

Table II.2.1 Europe and Argentina for Development Innovation and Change consortium
Own Elaboration.

The objective of the EADIC project is to *offer important opportunities for upgrading and reinforcing capacities on issues relevant for the economic and social agenda of Argentinean development*. EADIC aims at reinforcing the educational environment and promoting strategic cooperation along different scientific disciplines between European and Argentinean partner universities, at both academic staff and PhD/Post doc scholar level. The project will strengthen scientific cooperation on strategic issues like natural resources management; sustainable agriculture; biotechnology; renewable energies; hydraulic and bio-engineering; climate change and ICT

development. Finally, EADIC aims at promoting academic staff mobility as a way to reinforce institutional relations among universities.

CALL in YEAR 2010

2. EADICII:

Reference: EACEA/35/08- L13A(Argentina)

Title: Europe and Argentina for Development Innovation and Change II (EADIC II)

Beneficiary organization: UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA, Italy

Argentine Partners	European Partners
UNIVERSIDAD DE BUENOS AIRES	UNIVERSITY OF ANTWERPEN, Belgium
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DEL CENTRO DE LA PROVINCIA DE BUENOS AIRES	KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT LEUVEN, Belgium
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE QUILMES	UNIVERSITE DE LILLE 1, France
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE SAN LUIS	KARL-FRANZENS-UNIVERSITÄT GRAZ, Austria
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE TUCUMAN	UNIVERSIDAD DE VALLADOLID, Spain
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE ROSARIO	UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI PADOVA, Italy
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DEL COMAHUE	FRIEDRICH-SCHILLER-UNIVERSITÄT JENA, Germany
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DEL LITORAL	UNIVERSIDADE DE COIMBRA, Portugal
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE SALTA	UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA, Spain
UNIVERSIDAD TECNOLÓGICA NACIONAL	

Table II.2.2 Europe and Argentina for Development Innovation and Change II consortium
Own Elaboration.

The general objectives of EADICII are to *increase institutional cooperation among European and Argentinean universities, and to contribute to the mutual enrichment of societies by supporting the development of human resources and the international co-operation capacity of HEIs in Argentina.*

The project is concentrated on specific thematic fields such as natural resources management; sustainable agriculture; biotechnology; renewable energies; hydraulic and bio-engineering; climate change and ICT development.

3. MoE:

Reference: EACEA/35/08- L13B(Argentina)

Title: A Move on Education (MoE)

Beneficiary organization: UNIVERSIDAD DE MÁLAGA, Spain

Argentine Partners	European Partners
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE CÓRDOBA	UNIVERSIDAD DE BARCELONA, Spain
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE GENERAL SARMIENTO	UNIVERSIDADE DE LISBOA, Portugal
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DEL CENTRO DE LA PROVINCIA DE BUENOS AIRES	UNIVERSIDAD DE VALENCIA, Spain
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE LANÚS	UNIVERSITÀ CA FOSCARI, Italy
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE LA PAMPA	UNIVERSITY OF WEST ENGLAND, United Kingdom
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DEL NORDESTE	
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE SALTA	

Table II.2.3 A Move on the Education consortium

Own Elaboration.

The purpose of the project is to develop a cooperation and mobility program that will contribute to the international training of human resources of high scientific quality in the field of education, thus strengthening the academic capacity of partner institutions, while fostering cooperation and research links at both the regional and the international levels. MoE will contribute to the consolidation of a network between Argentina and Europe which will allow for the circulation of high quality research with a transforming potential that will impact positively on Faculties of Education at the level of doctorate programmes, which will add to the sustainability of the project.

4. EUROTANGO:

Reference: EACEA/35/08- L16A(Argentina)

Title: EuroTANGO

Beneficiary organization: UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE VALENCIA, Spain

Argentine Partners	European Partners
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE BUENOS AIRES	UNIVERSITEIT GENT, Belgium
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DEL NORDESTE	UNIVERSITY OF PATRAS, Greece
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE ENTRE RÍOS	UNIVERSIDADE DE PORTO , Portugal
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE SAN LUIS	POLITECNICO DI TORINO, Italy
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DEL SUR	UNIVERSIDAD DE VALLADOLID, Spain
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE JUJUY	UNIVERSITY OF GRONINGEN, The Netherlands
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE LA PLATA	UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI ROMA LA SAPIENZA, Italy
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE LA PATAGONIA SAN JUAN BOSCO	

Table II.2.4 EuroTANGO consortium

Own elaboration.

The main objective of EUROTANGO is to promote higher education cooperation between the EU and ARGENTINA through student and academic mobility for the purpose of studying, teaching, training, and research. EUROTANGO partners and associates share the vision that by strengthening the mutual enrichment, by way of a better understanding, by bringing together and capitalizing their methods and experiences, they can strongly improve their performance in the field of higher education. EUROTANGO's proposal seeks to fully attain the objectives of the call by pursuing the following aim: the return of students, researchers, and staff to Argentina after the mobility period will have a direct impact on their home institutions.

The institutional network created (8 European partners, 8 Argentinean partners, and 5 associates) is very powerful as it covers the whole country and is present -through

partners and associates- in the less developed regions of Northwest Argentina and Northeast Argentina.

The institutional network will reinforce the professional and institutional capacity of higher education institutions from Argentina through the establishment of equal relationships between the Consortium members and an entrusted coordination structure that will contribute to sharing responsibilities. This will play a unique role in the development of human resources and the international cooperation capacity of higher education institutions in Argentina, through increased bilateral mobility streams connecting Argentina with the European Union. The experience gained in this project by the participating scholars, partners and associates will be made available through knowledge transfer and sharing of experiences that will strengthen the sustainability and enhance in the medium term the political, cultural, educational, and economic links between the European Union and Argentina, thus promoting common values of respect for human rights, fundamental freedoms, peace, democracy, good governance, gender, equality, the rule of law, solidarity, and justice.

The main objective of EUROTANGO is to promote higher education between the EU and Argentina, through students, researchers, and staff mobility for the purpose of studying, teaching, training, and research. EUROTANGO's proposal strongly relies on the recognized knowledge and expertise of partners and associates in the scientific and technological fields. The foreseen activities will focus on the internationalization of partner universities and associate organizations.

5. EUROTANGO II:

Lot 16A - Argentina

Reference: 204562-1-2011-1-ES-EMA21

Title: S1-L16A EuroTANGO II

Beneficiary organization: UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE VALENCIA, Spain

Argentine Partners	European Partners
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE LA PLATA	UNIVERSITEIT GENT, Belgium
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE ENTRE RIOS	UNIVERSITÉ DE LILLE 1, France
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DEL NORDESTE	UNIVERSITY OF PATRAS, Greece
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE ROSARIO	SAPIENZA UNIVERSITY OF ROME, Italy
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE JUJURY	POLITECNICO DI TORINO, Italy
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE LA PATAGONIA SAN JUAN BOSCO	UNIVERSITY OF GRONINGEN, The Netherlands
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DEL SUR	UNIVERSIDADE DE PORTO, Portugal
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE CORDOBA	UNIVERSIDAD DE VALLADOLID, Spain
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE SAN LUIS	ROYAL INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY, Sweden
UNIVERSIDAD DE BUENOS AIRES	

Table II.2.5 EuroTANGOII consortium

Own elaboration.

The main objective of EuroTANGO II is to foster the cooperation between the EU and Argentina in Higher Education, focusing on the internationalization of Argentinean HEIs, which keeping the economic criteria in mind.

EuroTANGO II wishes to play a unique role in the development of human resources and international cooperation capacity of Higher Education Institutions in Argentina through increased mobility streams with the European Union, in order to:

.- Develop the skills of men and women to better adapt to the labor market and promoting cross-connections among people. Improving the capacity of international institutions to strengthen Argentina's links with European institutions and strengthening existing ones.

.- Promoting the European Higher Education system as a framework of excellence within the Argentinean institutions.

6. ARCOIRIS:

Reference: 204509-1-2011-1-IT-EMA21

Title: S1-L16A ARgentina COoperation for International Research and Study

Beneficiary organization: POLITECNICO DI TORINO, Italy

Argentine Partners	European Partners
INSTITUTO TECNOLOGICO DE BUENOS AIRES	INSTITUT POLYTECHNIQUE DE GRENOBLE, France
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE CÓRDOBA	GEORG-AUGUST-UNIVERSITÄT GOETTUNGEN STIFTUNG ÖFFENTLICHEN RECHTS, Germany
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DEL LITORAL	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT MÜNCHEN , Germany
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DEL NORDESTE	UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI TORINO, Italy
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE MAR DEL PLATA	SAPIENZA UNIVERSITY OF ROME, Italy
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE LA PLATA	INSTITUTO SUPERIOR TÉCNICO, Portugal
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE SAN JUAN	UNIVERSIDADE DO PORTO, Portugal
UNIVERSIDAD DE BUENOS AIRES	UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE VALENCIA, Spain
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE CATAMARCA	UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE MADRID, Spain
	LUNDS UNIVERSITEIT, Sweden

Table II.2.6 ARgentina COoperation for International Research and Study consortium
Own elaboration.

The main objective of the project is to promote higher education cooperation between the EU and Argentina in accordance with the EU's general goal of improving bilateral cooperation in the field of education. For example, promoting transparency, mutual recognition of qualifications and periods of study, research and training, and where appropriate, portability of credits.

The proposal *matches the Internationalization Policy of all Argentine partners that attempt to improve the quality of the educational and teaching level*, offering its researchers and staff several opportunities to participate in international research networks, diversifying knowledge approaches, approaching scientific cooperation and

multicultural experiences, allowing the higher education field to be part of the reciprocity in international relations.

By promoting interdisciplinary research and education, the Partnership will cover all the areas of study and disciplines identified by this lot, enabling all Partners to further improve their research and educational quality and fostering their vision, diversity, and creativity. The wide coverage of all disciplines is achieved thanks to the presence of both comprehensive and technological universities. The implementation of the ARCOIRIS project will create a concrete opportunity for further promoting research and educational collaborations among institutions in the EU and Argentina.

This scheme therefore will facilitate the creation of a greater number of cooperation channels among the partners.

CALL in YEAR 2011

7. ARTESS:

Lot 16B - Argentina

Reference: 204272-1-2011-1-IT-EMA21

Title: S1-L16B ARTESS – ARgentina Towards Europe for Social Sciences

Beneficiary organization: UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI PADOVA, Italy

Argentine Partners	European Partners
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE CATAMARCA	KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT LEUVEN, Belgium
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE LA PLATA	AARHUS UNIVERSITET, Denmark
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE CORDOBA	UNIVERSITÉ PIERRE MENDÈS FRANCE DE GRENOBLE II, France
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE CUYO	FRIEDRICH-SCHILLER-UNIVERSITÄT JENA, Germany
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE QUILMES	ALMA MATER STUDIORUM UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA, Italy
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DEL NORDESTE	UNIVERSIDADE DE COIMBRA, Portugal
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DEL LITORAL	UNIVERSIDAD DE SALAMANCA, Spain

UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DEL COMAHUE	UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA, Spain
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DEL SUR	

Table II.2.7 ARgentina Towards Europe for Social Sciences consortium

Own elaboration.

Scholarships will offer important opportunities for upgrading and reinforcing capacities on issues which are in the agenda of many Argentine institutions, both public and private.

The whole project will improve Argentine universities' capacity for EU and international dialogue, thus facilitating the completion of partnership agreements between European and Argentina for the implementation of double and joint diplomas. The association of Argentine universities will enhance national cooperation and lead to the creation of stronger networks, far beyond the scope of the consortium.

8. EUROPLATA:

Reference: 204556-1-2011-1-NL-EMA21

Title: S1-L16b Europlata

Beneficiary organization: RIJKSUNIVERSITEIT GRONINGEN, The Netherlands

Argentine Partners	European Partners
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE LA PLATA	UNIVERSITÉ DE STRASBOURG, France
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DEL LITORAL	GEORG-AUGUST UNIVERSITY GÖTTINGEN, Germany
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE SANTIAGO DEL ESTERO	UNIVERSITA DI PISA, Italy
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE SAN JUAN	UNIWERSYTET JAGIELLONSKI, Poland
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE RIO NEGRO	UNIVERSIDADE DE COIMBRA, Portugal
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE SAN MARTÍN	UNIVERSIDAD DE DEUSTO, Spain
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE LANÚS	
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE SUR	

Table II.2.8 Europlata consortium

Own elaboration.

The main objective of the Europlata project is to *establish a strong Euro-Argentine network of universities* that will last beyond the scope of these projects for 1)

the furtherance of excellent and socially committed individuals; 2) the enhancement of the capacity-building power of institutions; and 3) the improvement of regional and inter-continental relations.

The *consortium leader and some of the European partners, on the other hand, have ample experience in leading large international projects and will disseminate this knowledge to the other universities.* In short, Europlata is designed to develop higher education teaching and learning capacities, build management capacities, and foster institutional cooperation within the region and between regions. Particularly relevant in this respect is the incorporation of new universities in the global process of educational recognition and curriculum development.

Grantees are expected to become ambassadors of international education and form the bridge between Europe and Argentina in their future careers as scientists, policy-makers, or administrators.

The program aims to **promote and enhance cooperation between the partnership universities.** Additionally, it will further the process of educational reform, curriculum development, and international study recognition, and will also involve new universities in the process. Particular emphasis will be made on creating a better understanding among partners of the research cultures and the education of researchers in both Europe and Argentina.

II.2. c) Results

The Erasmus Mundus Action 2 Strand 1 (EMA2s1) Program was launched in 2007 by the European Union (EU). It was presented as a tool designed to improve the internationalization performance. Between 2007 and 2013 there were 383 European HEIs participating in some of the 262 funded Consortia. Within the 8 EMA2s1 bilateral projects, we found 28 Argentine partner universities.

Funding concentrated on a mobility scheme in consortia between European Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) from member states, and also from non-member states will probably strengthen their internationalization skills. As will be observed in the 8 projects that are discussed in this thesis, the possibilities of strengthening the Argentine HEIs in their internationalization actions stand out to a greater or lesser extent.

Some of the projects directly indicated the objective of improving the capabilities of international interaction, internationalization, and international cooperation. Each and every one would have mobility of individuals as a key element in achieving these objectives since this was the substance of the Program.

Below, there is a summary of the results that were presented in the FINAL JOINT MEETING for 2010 and 2011 Projects in the city of San Salvador de Jujuy, Argentina on December 13, 2013. An observed detail is the absence of references regarding the issue of internationalization in the opening speech of Dr. Ing. Enrique Arnau, the rector of the National University of Jujuy (UNJU is the Spanish acronym).

The EACEA, represented by Clivio Casali (Program Manager of the European Commission), once again presented the number of participants, amount of funds, number of mobility grantees and HEIs participating within the regional and bilateral program for

Argentina. The internationalization process or its improvement within the Argentine partners was neither noted in a transcript nor mentioned verbally.

Within the results presented one can find numbers according to types of mobilities, participation, and target groups, together with mobility duration, but no references to the HEIs and the impact within them of their internationalization processes, whether or not it aimed at strengthening their profile or with respect to driving actions towards internationalization. However, the summaries stated that the 8 projects were supposed to strengthen the HEI capacities. There were no comments and no information supporting the improvement or internal strengthening for the Argentine HEIs and their capacities.

One of the open-ended questions which Casali posed with his presentation closing remarks was: “How are the thematic areas’ priorities defined? Are there concrete synergies with CONICET, MINCYT, INTI and INTA (etc.) in defining priorities?” This led to a direct consultation with each of the four national agencies in order to know the views and benefits that could stand out at the EMA2s1 for the agency as well as for Argentina. INTA, INTI, and MINCYT had similar answers: **They did not have knowledge of their own participation**, even though the 3 National Organisms were associated with parts of the EMA2s1.

CONICET (National Scientific and Technical Research Council, Argentina), however, responded to a brief questionnaire that had been sent out (Annex 4), specifically:

Could you list or share some project results?

“The participation of CONICET in these programs has allowed it, on the one hand, to form part of different Committees that are formed for the evaluation of programs and the admission of candidates. For example, in the case of

EuroTANGO, CONICET acted as a member of the Subcommittee on Communication and Quality and the Selection Subcommittee.

On the other hand, the projects allowed Argentine students to arrange stays in European universities to contribute to the development of their doctoral or postdoctoral theses. The only impediment for CONICET grantees is the completion of a full doctorate abroad, since they can be a maximum of 6 months abroad. However, there are no disadvantages to doing the doctorate in ‘sandwich’ mode.” Daniela Trevisán, email, January 21, 2015.

It is not the focus of this PhD research to perform an analysis or evaluation of the degree of participation of the organizations or institutions associated with the projects. The Author considered it to be of importance, given the direct reference of the EACEA personnel towards them and their possible action in the future. In the context which has been functioning, it was necessary in this thesis to record the reality by referencing the work of Hunter (2013).

Finally, Table II.2.9 presents a review of the results mentioned by the Coordinating HEIs in the conference held in Jujuy with the purpose of presenting the results of the actions carried out by the European Union in Argentina through the windows of cooperation, the regional window as well as the window we investigated in this PhD research, namely, the bilateral window with Argentina.

Table II.2.9 presents project aims and results. The interpretation leads to a comparison between the objectives that were mentioned in project summaries, which are indicated as a reference for those readers interested in existing or absent connections, degree of impact on the Argentine HEIs in this case, among other questions which may arise.

Project	Principal Aim	Presented Results
EADIC	Aims at promoting academic staff mobility as a way to reinforce institutional relations among universities	92 Mobilities. Focus on Individual impact. Importance of resources and networks. International Relations
EADICII	Increase institutional cooperation ... and the international co-operation capacity of HEIs in Argentina	77 Mobilities. Individual impact. Role and importance of resources and networks. New and stronger Relations
EUROTANGO	The foreseen activities will focus on the internationalization of partner universities and associate organizations	73 Mobilities
MoE	Fostering cooperation and research links both at regional and international levels	44 Mobilities Holding a privileged position to introduce practical reforms ... upon finalization of the project. 5 new bilateral agreements (MoU) between the partners
EUROTANGO2	Foster cooperation between EU and Argentina in HEs. Focus on the internationalization of Argentinean HEIs	68 Mobilities
ARTESS	Improve Argentinean universities' capacity for internationalization ... and international dialogue	67 Mobilities. "Future cooperation mostly depends on personal/individual contacts and relations"
ARCOIRIS	The proposal matches the Internationalization Policy of all Argentinean partners that attempt to improve the quality of the educational and teaching level	55 Mobilities; Strengths and weaknesses focused only in mobility
EUROPLATA	Establish a strong Euro-Argentine network of universities...leader will disseminate this knowledge to the other universities	58 Mobilities, Institutional commitment key (learned)

Table II.2.9 EU-Argentina EMA2 Aims and Results
Own elaboration.

Figure II.2.1 IROs Hierarchy in Partner Universities – 2015
Own elaboration.

Universities	Hierarchy IRO	EADIC	EADICII	MoE	EUROTANGO	EUROTANGO 2	ARTESS	EUROPLATA	ARCOIRIS
Universidad Nacional de La Plata	3	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Universidad Nacional del Sur	2	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Universidad Nacional de Córdoba	2	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
Universidad Nacional del Litoral	1	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Universidad Nacional del Nordeste	4	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
Universidad Nacional de San Juan	4	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
Universidad de Buenos Aires	1	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes

Universidad Nacional de Catamarca	1 *	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	Yes
Universidad Nacional de Rio Negro	4	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	No
Universidad Nacional de San Martín	4	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	No
Universidad Nacional de Lanús	3	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No
Universidad Nacional de Santiago del Estero	3	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	No
Universidad Nacional del Comahue	2	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No	No
Universidad Nacional de Cuyo	1	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	No
Universidad Nacional de Quilmes	3	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No	No
ITBA - Instituto Tecnológico de Buenos Aires	ND	No	Yes						
Universidad Nacional del Mar del Plata	4	No	Yes						
Universidad Nacional de Entre Ríos	4	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	No
Universidad Nacional de Jujuy	4	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	No

Universidad Nacional de la Patagonia “San Juan Bosco”	4	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	No
Universidad Nacional de Rosario	1	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	No
Universidad Nacional de San Lus	1	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	No
Universidad Nacional de Tucumn	3	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No
Universidad Tecnolgica Nacional	1	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No
Universidad Nacional de Salta	1	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No	No
Universidad Nacional del Centro de la Provincia de Buenos Aires	4	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No	No
Universidad Nacional de Gral. Sarmiento	0	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No
Universidad Nacional de la Pampa	0	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No

Table II.2.10 Distribution of partners and IRO hierarchies within EMA2s2 projects
Own elaboration.

Chapter III: Support for the Internationalization

Process

III.1 A look at the PU internationalization process during the 2005-2015 period

Before diving into the indicated period it is important to present some details which should be considered in order to comprehend the perspectives of authors in the body of literature regarding the context surrounding the process in Argentina.

Education in Argentina is ruled by the Law of National Education 26.206 (12/14/2006), where one can find several articles dealing with higher education. However, Argentina has a specific law that regulates higher education. As expressed by Fernandes Nogueira (2012, p. 113): “including universities and non-universities, national, provincial and municipal institutions – both public and private. This is Law 24.251 (08/07/1995) – the Law of Higher Education.”

As de Fanelli (2014) explains when describing the governance and administrative structures of the universities:

According to the 1995 Higher Education Act, national universities enjoy substantial autonomy, which is codified in their individual charters or statutes. Public universities have the authority to select their own leaders (presidents and deans) and collegial bodies with the participation of professors, students, and alumni. Among the collegial bodies, the most important is the higher council that is comprised of the deans of each faculty and representatives from professors, students, and alumni. The *universities' authorities also manage their own human resources*, [create their organizational structures, design the strategy], *allocate funds*, and design the curriculum. (Italics and bold text added by the Author, pp. 197).

The other issue that is worthy of consideration is that HEIs evaluation is performed by the National Commission for University Evaluation and Accreditation (CONEAU is the Spanish acronym). Public and private universities in Argentina have been evaluated by CONEAU since 1995. “Institutional accreditation was addressed that year in the higher education legislation, although it has not been widely implemented. CONEAU conducts a *voluntary* external evaluation of public and private autonomous institutions to promote quality improvements.” (de Fanelli, 2014, p. 198).

In summary, one should find two types of evaluations in Argentina. According to CONEAU (1997) guidelines, the first type is called *self-evaluation* report, a qualitative/quantitative document which exposes the universities’ activities, as well as their internal organization, goals, policies, and strategies. It is a process and results-oriented analysis carried out by the institution itself through its Human Resources Department, which is selected by the university authorities.

The second type is called external evaluation and it is intended to evaluate performance. It shows the institution’s organization and functioning; observes its development plot; assesses processes and results, and recommends courses of action. Although it is based on the self-evaluation report and the institutional project it is undertaken by people who do not belong to the university and are independent in their criteria. Guidelines or general criteria are defined by the CONEAU in order to develop it. Guidelines can be reformulated over time and each case will require an adaptation of the external evaluation procedures to the institution’s specific particularities. (CONEAU, 1997, p. 8).

Finally, here is a last detail as an aid in understanding how CONEAU’s institutional evaluation has been developed:

The first criterion for organizing a list of variables has followed two guidelines: on the one hand, the requirement of Law 24.521 which stipulates that the functions to be evaluated should be teaching, research, extension, and in the case of national universities also management; and on the other hand, an attempt to cover both the inputs and results of the university activity and its processes and impact on the social environment. The second organizing criterion has been to consider the functions defined as the ordering of the institutional reality. That is, consider the different elements and aspects of the institution articulated for the fulfillment of the objectives proposed by the institution for the fulfillment of its functions. At this point, it is necessary to make explicit that it is not a question of justifying any action or practice that contributes to the fulfillment of the functions defined by the institutions [the end does not justify the means]; rather, it should capture the meaning of the practices by asking why the actors do what they do and nothing else. (CONEAU, 1997, p. 18) (Italics and bold text added by the Author; translated by this Author).

Clearly focused on how the functions are developed and specifically considering PUs' management, CONEAU's evaluation does not declare or propose any item tied to the internationalization process or the international dimension in the institution's core functions. It is noteworthy that to date this issue has not been incorporated.

Twelve (12) PUs were created between 1999 and 2009 under different national governments (2 in 2002; 1 in 2005; 2 in 2007, and 7 in 2009). By 2014 the number of PUs rose to 55 against the 38 which existed in 2005 (which is the starting date for the work in this thesis).

Taking de Wit (2005) into account, internationalization in Latin America – as in other regions of the world – has become a recognized phenomenon that influences not only *education* but also HEIs. The development of the process as well as its trends, issues,

and opportunities within different countries “are little known” (p. xiii). One can note that it is a starting point to grasp and analyze the process of this versatile issue in Argentina.

In the early 1990s [Argentine] universities *neither viewed internationalization as part of their mission and objectives nor possessed specific administrative structures for international activities*. No government policies promoted the internationalization of higher education, and institutional relations existed between only a few universities and foreign universities. Ties had been forged between Argentine researchers and their foreign counterparts, but they were limited to elite groups (p. 81). (Italics and bold text added by the Author).

With de Wit (2005), one finds a concise analysis that should help develop a clearer understanding regarding the state of internationalization of an Argentine group of PUs. Within the qualitative methodology that is used in the research by de Wit, where interviews with decision-makers, analyses of documents, publications, websites, and also data collection are the basis for country studies by examining the elements (e.g. mobility, curriculum, linkages, and networks), one can understand the process of internationalization at the institutional, national, and regional level from a comprehensive perspective:

The chapter on Argentina, for instance, focuses on sub-regional cooperation within Mercosur [*Southern Common Market, which is a South American trade bloc*] and the active participation of national institutions in international and regional networks. In that chapter...there is a strong emphasis on the balanced relation between national policies and programs and internationalization at the institutional level. (de Wit, 2005, p. xiv).

This information is reviewed in a chapter by Theiler (IN: de Wit, 2005, pp. 71-110). In the findings, Theiler presents some facts about the Argentine situation regarding the internationalization of universities, the interest shown by Argentine PUs within their organizational structures, the specific weight in institutional budgets for the development

of international activities, and the reinforcement or improvement of its human resources capacity, among other issues.

It is noteworthy, as was elaborated in Chapter I of this thesis, that the focus on *organizational strategies* supports this PhD research. Authors working within an analysis of institutional strategies in a process approach (e.g., Davies, Rudzki, Knight, de Wit, etc.) were the basis from which the Author of this thesis could observe and analyze the Argentine case. However, in order to reappraise what could/should be done the reader is referred to Figure I.1.2.1 (p. 55 of this thesis) and the questions presented inside the chapter.

Of the 20 PUs that participated - out of the 37 that existed that year - the survey (Theiler, 2003) states in de Wit (2005) that:

- a. Out of the 75% of HEIs included the International Dimension as an area that should be developed.
- b. 90% have an ad hoc administrative structure for international activities. PUs in Argentina has a hierarchal structure – usually named or created by the Rector and approved by the Superior Council - with the *secretariats* at the top of the hierarchy.

Within the analyzed group, only 20% assigns the status of secretariat (the highest hierarchy within the organizational structure of PUs in Argentina) to the International Relations Office (IRO); 50% have IROs which pertain to offices; and the remaining 30% are low in the hierarchy. An average office has 4 people, and about 45% of them are assistants or student interns. This means, ‘at the end of the day’, that staff engaged in the development of activities at IROs are limited in number.

Officials in charge spend a relatively short period of time in their posts; consequently, staff changes occur quite often at public universities. Sixty percent (60%) of the IROs has not specifically assigned budgetary resources and depends on higher administrative areas. Thus, these offices rarely serve as the administrators or managers of specific HEI Internationalization programs.

Finally, at the national level there are neither systematic activities to evaluate international activities nor institutional evaluations made by the CONEAU. This shows that the international dimension is not analyzed by the highest evaluation body of Higher Education in Argentina.

Presumably this is an indicator of the little value given to the *International Question* to evaluate HEIs in Argentina:

For many years, universities gave no systematic priority to internationalization; those activities that did exist were initiated by individual faculty or groups of faculties. Only in the late 1990s did universities begin to declare internationalization a strategic objective and start to make it a part of the objectives of their strategic development plans, although ***in most cases this was not matched with concrete actions*** or budgetary allocations for pursuing such an objective (p. 95). (Italics and bold text added by the Author).

During the last decade of 2005-2014 PUs had found a motivation to internationalize themselves, and they had been encouraged by national and external drivers - as described in Chapter II of this thesis - through different funding strategies to improve their internationalization processes, or at least to develop or improve the units steering them.

What is sought in the present research is a description of the support given by the Argentine government. In doing so, we specifically aim at taking a deeper look into the group of 28 PUs participating as partner Universities in EMA2s1 which was developed before.

Hunter (2013) presented an interesting model with which to analyze how HEIs behave in a context with national and international influences. Within this interplay, she describes the movement one could observe regarding the dynamic of the process and the level of engagement ascribable to HEI responsiveness. In a proactive context, we can assume that one should ordinarily be able to distinguish differences after a period of 10 years.

However, as Knight (2005) observes in the institutional policies of Latin American countries, regarding Argentina:

Internationalization of higher education is frequently mentioned in speeches and official declarations by educational authorities. It is seen as a key strategy for enhancing the quality of teaching, learning, and research in order to meet the demands and challenges of the twenty-first century. Despite this recognition, there is an absence of explicit policies for internationalization...

The country studies suggest that international activities and programs are not yet integrated into regular planning procedures. International activities do not address the specific priorities of the institutional agenda, and they are organized in an ad hoc manner, left mainly to the initiatives of individual faculty members. Many programs are simply responses to opportunities offered by international institutions or organizations. Higher education institutions are not yet used to planning their own international activities in a systematic way and setting objectives based on their needs, requirements, and financial resources in the short, medium, or long term. (p. 350).

Finally, it is worth noticing some of the conclusions which Lamarra (2014) indicates below:

Siufi (2009), Fernández Lamarra (2009, 2012), and Hermo (2010) indicate that there have been more advances *at the declarative intentions level than at the concrete actions level*. The activities, projects and programs of internationalization of higher education in Argentina have grown significantly, but they are not usually included - in a final form - in regular policies and implementation practices (p. 19). (Italics added by the Author).

Lamarra concludes in his analysis that:

In Argentina, the internationalization of higher education is being installed in the National State's agendas and institutions of higher education ... However, despite these important advances, *in many cases the internationalization of higher education has not been a substantial issue, but it appears to be ad hoc or an ad hoc policy activity* (p. 22).

In other words, what was observed and recorded in 2005 with respect to Argentina as a part of the study still applies 10 years later.

III.2 Improving the IROs: The First Call in 2006

The Ministry of Education's N° 635 Resolution of June 7, 2006 created the Argentine University Promotion Program (PPUA is the Spanish acronym). It was meant to promote the Argentine universities' activities abroad, and create networks and strategic alliances in order to support students, professors, incoming students and outgoing mobilities, exchanges of services, knowledge, and know-how (i.e., practical knowledge). With 38 PUs in existence at that time, the proposal was received with great enthusiasm, in particular due to the possibilities that it opened for them such as an opportunity to begin developing strategies linked to the international dimension. In other words, it meant generating present and *potentially future* stability for improvement in the internationalization process. This was one path clearly driven by national and international stakeholders, with many activities where the starting point were the *traditional* mobilities, but aiming further towards a process where Argentina would strengthen institutional networks; finally culminating with one pattern within the HEIs: the importance of their IROs.

There is no doubt that the national context, following international signals, began to devote more than simple rhetoric towards its own PUs, proof of which are the words (refer to an earlier discussion in this thesis) that stand out in the foundations of the first Call for Projects to Strengthen the Areas of International Relations of National University Institutions. Hence, the focus on what the HEI indicated on their websites showed, that these calls directly positioned the IRO as an instrument for managing the process. This situation was indicated in the previous section as part of the conclusions reached by Theiler (2005) and the set of references to IROs:

The internationalization policies of higher education are turning from their traditional forms of academic and student mobility programs towards the constitution of networks and strategic alliances for new scenarios that are a real challenge for universities and the State.

In this context, it is appropriate to review and reorient the policies of the Argentine university system in a mature and permanent dialogue between the university institutions and the National State aimed at strengthening the capabilities of the system for an active and effective insertion in internationalization processes.

The Ministry of Education, Science and Technology of the Nation of Argentina, along with the PPUA, began its search to promote the establishment and strengthening of international networks of universities, the incorporation of foreign undergraduate and graduate students and the design of policies for strategic alliances with universities and scientific institutions abroad, among other objectives. (Resolution 635, June 2006, p. 5).

In a first reading of the general objectives, one can identify that the emerging dynamic in relation to the process of the internationalization of PUs was valued at the national level, possibly with a very strong bias toward strengthening mobility. There was also a need to generate progress or improvements in this process based on the national government's economic support.

As reflected in the findings presented by Theiler, we can conclude that the Argentine government, through the PPUA, took the general objectives as the basis for the development of the call. The Argentine government stressed that in this stage it should aim to strengthen national universities' areas of international relations and cooperation, in order to capitalize "the path traveled to the present" and contribute to the improvement

of existing technical and operational capacities to develop the strategic role, that new scenarios demand, in a more efficient way (Call for Projects, p. 4, paragraph 1)⁵.

It is within this line of institutional strategic vision that it was referenced within Chapter I that while some individual estates can develop their own internationalization processes, a definition must be found which crosses all HEIs and which must be shared and communicated by all the individual parts of the HEIs. Thus, the Author proposes that *one could say we sought to invest in favoring institutional strategies in order to advance the process of internationalization* by establishing the IROs as fundamental actors and the agents that manage the process within PUs.

It was nothing more than affirming the path that by necessity had been indicated a year earlier. This was part of the conclusions of the work undertaken by Theiler (de Wit, 2005), given that among some of its specific objectives we can observe the following:

- a. Improving the International Relations and Cooperation Offices or equivalent areas in the technical capabilities of national university institutions.
- b. Facilitating the constitution of the same as noted above in ‘a.’ in those institutions that do not have it.
- c. Strengthening the assigned personnel’s training and development.
- d. Improving institutional websites’ incorporation versions in foreign languages (at least in English and Portuguese).
- e. Supporting and generating spaces for the coordination of policies and strategies to internationalize the university system. (p. 4).

⁵ 2006 Call for Projects downloadable in:
https://web.archive.org/web/20070223174644/http://www.me.gov.ar/spu/guia_tematica/promocion/promocion-convocatoria.htm

Hence, we can see what Argentina identified as Internationalization, how it hoped to collaborate in its improvement, and how PUs that had not yet started upon that path could initiate their own progress along it.

However, outside the PUs that benefited from the call, it is not possible to reach information that may have been collected. At that time, there were no instruments that facilitated or allowed comparison with the present situation regarding Internationalization in order to be able to carry out an evaluation of the impact generated. On the basis of the research by de Wit (2005), we can attribute a scarce development in the PU sphere regarding its internationalization process at the time of the call. There is also minimal or no development of the international dimension within the management system of the PUs, due to the limited presence of the IROs, and especially when considering some of the specific objectives of the call.

From the objectives of the call, we can infer that advancement was expected within a process that would consolidate its integration over the entire institutional range managed by the IRO. Similarly to the decision of an HEI and with the financing of the PPUA to consolidate or strengthen its existence, the IRO would be in charge of invigorating the internationalization process of the PUs.

In support of the above, the 32 PU beneficiaries from this first call are detailed in Table III.2.1.

Public Universities in Argentina
Universidad Nacional de La Plata
Universidad Nacional del Sur
Universidad Nacional de Córdoba
Universidad Nacional del Litoral
Universidad Nacional del Nordeste
Universidad Nacional de San Juan
Universidad de Buenos Aires
Universidad Nacional de Catamarca
Universidad Nacional de San Martín
Universidad Nacional de Lanús
Universidad Nacional del Comahue
Universidad Nacional de Cuyo
Universidad Nacional de Quilmes
Universidad Nacional del Mar del Plata
Universidad Nacional de Entre Ríos
Universidad Nacional de Jujuy
Universidad Nacional de la Patagonia “San Juan Bosco”
Universidad Nacional de Rosario
Universidad Nacional de San Luís
Universidad Nacional de Tucumán
Universidad Nacional de Salta
Universidad Nacional del Centro de la Provincia de Buenos Aires
Universidad Nacional de Gral. Sarmiento
Universidad Nacional de la Pampa
Universidad Nacional de Formosa
Universidad Nacional de la Rioja
Universidad Nacional de las Artes
Universidad Nacional de Luján
Universidad Nacional de Misiones
Universidad Nacional de Río Cuarto
Universidad Nacional de Tres de Febrero
Universidad Nacional del Noroeste de la Provincia de Buenos Aires

Table III.2.1 PPUA 1° Call for beneficiaries

Own elaboration.

Thus, the PU beneficiary sphere will be compared with the findings of Agnese (2011). Within her study, one can discern the existence of differences between the picture offered by Theiler (2005) and the first results which were released a year after the PPUA call. As was summarized before in this thesis, the internationalization process is analyzed in this research by considering organizational structures as well as integration within the PUs and IROs within them.

With reference to the Organic Structure, 22 PUs responded from a total of 44 PUs, considering that the sample complies with the Confidence Index (CI) of Agnese (2011, p. 3):

a. More than 80% indicate that they have an IRO; where an organizational location does not prevail. But as previously observed, 18% are distinguished with a Secretariat Rank, 27% as Sub-Secretary or Undersecretary, 31% as Directorate, and 22% as another (Department, Area, Coordination, Rectorate Deputy).

b. The number of professional staff that develops activities within the same is 40.9%. 63% lack auxiliary, 31% lack administrative staff, etc. When referring to the internationalization priority level, the survey evaluates the degree of importance given to International Relations and analyzes in which documents it was contemplated.

Forty-one percent (41%) indicate that this is contemplated in the University's Mission, 77% in its Strategic Plan, 27% in the University's Statute, and 4.5% do not indicate anything. On the other hand, 50% indicate that they evaluate the impact of their internationalization programs, 27% indicate the contrary, and 23% do not answer.

A final detail is the reference in the study to the Framework Agreements issue indicated as "an important internationalization strategy" (p. 28). In the first chapter it was indicated the confusion regarding how counting the number of agreements in the internationalization process usually leads to errors while evaluating it (see Annex 4).

As noted in Chapter II of this thesis regarding EU actions, in the Argentine case agreement are also taken as the indicators/results of the process, with no further analysis other than the number of frameworks and specific agreements signed with other regions around the world. It is intended for it to be understood as part of the number of

international activities performed, although this has been far removed from what was originally indicated.

This occurs in addition to specific cases, which are considered to be valid and to be assets, without further indications regarding the implication of said differences, nor the evaluation systems with which to consider them as active agreements or not.

The existence of an instrument that allows the evaluation of how the agreements function or develop, generally or specifically, is not found in this publication or in other publications, to best of our knowledge. This is an element that to date has been considered as an enhancer of *rhetorical internationalization*.

A final element that should be highlighted is the scarce international mobility activity of the personnel who belong to the IROs, and the lack of reception they indicate for the years 2006-2007. In this section, the author concludes that “it would be important to stimulate this type of activity considering the possibility and strength that the mobilities imply for training the IROs’ permanent staff cadres.”

It would be of great importance that within the universities, at the decision-making level, the true importance of international relations in higher education, *the comparative advantages* that this implies and *the large number of activities* that can be developed from this type could be *understood...* of offices, and for this reason it would be a **great advance for the Argentine university that these IROs were adequately** supported [truly] to develop their full potential (p. 64). (Bold text and italic added by the Author).

Once again *rhetorical internationalization* is observed. Although, this time it is understood within the percentages presented in each part of the work of Agnese, given that it was made in the year of the execution of the Development Projects, Strengthening of the International Relations and Cooperation Offices or equivalent areas in the PUs, and

the numbers which Theiler (2005) obtained, but above all, due to his affirmations noted in the above chapter.

III.3 The Second Call in 2010

Meanwhile, in 2009, better planning, monitoring and evaluation of the IROs' actions were sought in order to consolidate and improve PUs' internationalization policies, as the words of the Secretary of University Policies corroborated (RSPU N°828, 2009).

In the latter, it was established that:

Integration in the international context and cooperation are strategic tools to achieve the strengthening of universities ... it is necessary to strengthen the dissemination of the offer of undergraduate and postgraduate courses, the mobility of students, teachers and researchers, the constitution of academic networks and teaching of Spanish as a foreign language, as pillar of the international insertion of our universities (p. 1).

This was the road initiated four years earlier by the Argentine government in the search to improve or generate a space in charge of managing the PUs' internationalization process. A process that, unlike that of the previous stage, should be understood within the Internationalization cycle's framework (Knight, 1994; de Wit, 2001). The system's actors, in this case the PUs, should have complied with each of the stages foreseen in the cycle. Therefore, it was expected that following Brandenburg and Federkeil (2007), PUs were managing a steered cycle, from a current status of internationality in 2006 towards a longer current status of extended internationality in 2009 and beyond at the time of the second national call.

This should have been undertaken by observing the Argentine call and analyzing it by applying the internationalization cycle's perspective, particularly:

Review: Assessing and enhancing quality and impact of initiatives and progress of strategy developed by the PUs after the 2006 call;

Reinforcement: Developing incentives, recognitions and rewards for institutional (i.e., faculty, staff, and students) participation after the 2006 call;

Integration effect: Impacting the internationalization of teaching, research, and service functions of the process after the 2006 call.

At least, from the theory put forward, this is the path the PUs should have followed in order to improve the present state of the process - considering 2010 as the present. Once again, the specific weight given to IROs within the organization is observed, as a space in charge of materializing it. Therefore, it is worthwhile to review in detail the bases of the call by trying to understand the expectations towards the process of internationalization of the PUs and the degree of improvement existing in the units in charge of managing it.

In the bases one can read:

After three years of innovative work with universities, the Program now considers it necessary to consolidate the actions undertaken, *promoting instruments that facilitate and strengthen universities' internationalization policies...*

The establishment of strategic lines and priorities within the framework of an explicit planning facilitates and enhances the coordination of joint actions and alliances between the Argentine universities themselves, in the face of an increasingly complex and challenging internationalization. But at the same time, it is rich in opportunities *to strengthen policies to improve the quality and relevance of training, research and the transfer of our higher institutions.* (Italic added by the Author) (Bases, 2009, p. 1)

It can be seen that internationalization is an element which is present in the university system and that it should favor the strengthening of the quality of the Argentine university system. However, given the context of increasing global internationalization, it is not possible to find a definition of *what is meant by internationalization*, or more generally a reference system for the *international dimension in higher education*.

Specifically, the call deals with the meaning of a Strategic Plan for the Development of International Relations while defining the general plan “as anticipated decision making and a guide of action towards a desired situation, through a reflective instrumentation of media”. And in this particular case, as “anticipated decision making that allows one to foresee, organize, coordinate and control situations, actions and results, oriented to strategically develop the international dimension of the university”.

The Plan must give an account of objectives, goals and means in the medium term (for example, three years), although in fact what should be centrally presented is an *Operational Plan* for 2010, within the framework of a longer-term scope of vision for the university’s international dimension (Bases, 2009, p. 2).

According to the requirements, the PUs had to have an IRO with an institutionally recognized leadership to *promote, direct, coordinate, and evaluate* the actions of the plan. Only one plan per PU could be presented - which implies the existence of internal differences within the PUs regarding the direction of the process or the possible scenario of chaos within them regarding internationalization. There was also the obligation to make one’s own contribution of 30% of the requested amount with the corresponding institutional commitment signed by the PU’s Rector as it was stated within the call.

The characteristics of the presentation showed that it was expected that an in-depth definition in the first instance, by the unit responsible for promoting, directing, coordinating, and evaluating the actions corresponding to the international question.

Specifically, this included its mission and functions, as well as the type of infrastructure, and equipment available at the unit. In addition, presentations would have to be endorsed by Rectoral or Superior Council University Resolutions: an element of *Reality*.

A summary of the activities was developed - without indication of the time that would be covered - by the IRO, along with a set of the PU's international activities. This was done with a clear understanding regarding lack of coordination in the process; or as an element which facilitated the identification of weaknesses and real opportunities.

On the other hand, for the first time mentioned literally as such, presentations requested that medium- and long-term objectives of the PU regarding its international dimension were stated. At that point, mostly likely, universities and units did not know what those objectives were referring to. Every presentation had to be accompanied by *official documentation*.

Finally, more specifically, the presented objectives, goals, actions, and resources for the year 2010 were indicated as part of the operational plan. Clearly, it was intended that the information requested would be useful and facilitate either an ex-post evaluation, or a comparative study with respect to the process in the PUs that were part of the Erasmus Mundus projects.

Of the eligible items, it will be possible to observe the activities that, in the national view, were necessary for strengthening the plan in order to set in motion the Development Plan proposed by the PUs. In short, this is where the plans are translated into actions that can be measured both in their quantity - compared to the past - as well as in terms of improving the quality of the process which is present in each of the universities. Here, the role played by the IRO as the institutional driver of the process is fundamental, considering that in each of the items it was indicated what the PUs should

have to incorporate as fundable category, and to have institutional regulations that monitor/control such actions.

The categories selected to receive financing were accompanied by a justification together with potential institutional indicators.

Item	Justification
1.- Academic networks with foreign institutions.	One can request funds for the start of new networks. These networks must be integrated with at least two other institutions from abroad and may have the purpose of developing joint undergraduate or postgraduate training programs, research and development, extension and technological linkage or specialized technical assistance to third parties. Other universities or public or private Argentine organizations may join them. They must develop their activity within the Agreements framework or the Protocols of Framework Agreements (established or to be established in the project's execution) and the university must have specific regulations that regulate the creation and management of international academic networks.
2.- Student Mobility Programs.	They can be general or specific (oriented towards a discipline, academic unit or destination institution). They must be carried out within the framework of agreements already established or to be unfailingly established during the annual development of the Plan, guaranteeing the recognition of the partial studies carried out and the reciprocity of treatment. The university must have a general regulation of international student mobility under criteria of equity and quality.
3.- Teacher Mobility Programs.	They will aim to facilitate the mobility of teachers/researchers to participate in international academic events (Workshops, Conferences, Workshops, courses or seminars, etc.) Particular emphasis should be placed on the training of novice teachers. The university must have specific regulations that regulate international teaching mobility under criteria of quality and equity.
4.- Institutional Strengthening Program.	It may include the training of staff and teachers in topics related to the international dimension of higher education. It also contemplates the improvement of the statistics, norms and instruments of the institution's international activity,
5.- Dissemination Material and Institutional Image in foreign languages.	It can be developed under different supports in the framework of an institutional strategy of international promotion. This may include the internal dissemination of international activity as well as the improvement of the website in foreign languages.
6.- Design of specific international programs.	("Semesters abroad" short courses, Spanish as a second or foreign language, university extension courses, postgraduate courses, technological linkage programs with third countries, etc.)

Table III.3.1 Funded items and explanation
Own Elaboration.

Another program for strengthening the Internationalization of PUs is The Program for the Internationalization of Higher Education and International Cooperation (PIESCI is the Spanish acronym) from - along with the PPUA. Funes (2014), when referring to it, indicated that:

According to the interviewed referents, it has made a quantitative and qualitative leap with an expansion of actions since the years 2007-2008. In this sense, this growth is translated into *the hierarchization of the area and the valorization of internationalization as a strategic line in universities* (p. 47). (Italic added by the Author).

This is despite the fact that it constitutes a program which unquestionably, exists as a result of internationalization. To date, we do not have elements that allow such words to be endorsed. As noted in the previous section, no tangible differences were observed in the real situation of the IROs in those PUs that chose to give answers to the work carried out by Agnese, and a difference could not be observed in the state of the situation posed by Theiler (IN: De Wit, 2005) either.

Among other similarities observed, Tobin (Tangelson, 2014), when referring to the issue of human resources in PUs' IROs, indicates that the staff which integrate them - be they technical or political - do not have postgraduate training in "the process of university internationalization". While, in respect to those responsible for the IROs, he says that many of them "do not have training and only in some cases have some experience gained through its continuity". This is a description of a reality that is different from expectations in the context of supporting the development and strengthening of the same model since 2006. Alternatively, it could simply be another example of *rhetorical internationalization* in Argentine PUs.

Therefore, as Tobin (IN: Tangelson, 2014) states, "the evaluation of internationalization activities and programs" are among the pending issues. This is an

element that is sustained and suggested on different occasions in the work of Tobin. So much so, that he specifies the following:

“The establishment of evaluation mechanisms for internationalization activities is not a usual practice and it is very difficult to know the impact of these actions without the corresponding evaluations ... in general terms, *there is no practical implementation of evaluation mechanisms that can contribute to notoriously improve the management of the areas responsible for carrying out the process of internationalization*” (p. 63). (Translated by the Author; Italic added by the Author).

In other words, the expectations of the impact of the PUs' process of internationalization were of absolute improvement with regards to an *unknown present situation*, with very little identification. A primary observation scenario in place was aimed at the year 2010, since it was expected that all the activities would be executed by that year. This was also taking into account the existence of a previous call, 3 years earlier, with more elementary characteristics, but with a focus on the international dimension and its dynamics within the same sphere of participants. The IRO was without a doubt the fundamental actor in the internationalization process there.

Having stated the above, the PUs beneficiaries of the year 2006 First Call are detailed in Table III.3.2, as are those of the year 2009 Second Call. Note that two (2) PUs do not repeat the access to financing, and that six (6) PUs arise as new beneficiaries, totaling 36 of the PUs for this call.

1st Call 2006	2nd Call 2009
Universidad Nacional de La Plata	Universidad Nacional de La Plata
Universidad Nacional del Sur	Universidad Nacional del Sur
Universidad Nacional de Córdoba	Universidad Nacional de Córdoba
Universidad Nacional del Litoral	Universidad Nacional del Litoral
Universidad Nacional del Nordeste	Universidad Nacional del Nordeste
Universidad Nacional de San Juan	Universidad Nacional de San Juan
Universidad de Buenos Aires	Universidad de Buenos Aires
Universidad Nacional de Catamarca	Universidad Nacional de Catamarca
	Universidad Nacional de Río Negro
Universidad Nacional de San Martín	Universidad Nacional de San Martín
Universidad Nacional de Lanús	Universidad Nacional de Lanús
	Universidad Nacional de Santiago del Estero
Universidad Nacional del Comahue	Universidad Nacional del Comahue
Universidad Nacional de Cuyo	Universidad Nacional de Cuyo
Universidad Nacional de Quilmes	Universidad Nacional de Quilmes
Universidad Nacional del Mar del Plata	Universidad Nacional del Mar del Plata
Universidad Nacional de Entre Ríos	Universidad Nacional de Entre Ríos
Universidad Nacional de Jujuy	Universidad Nacional de Jujuy
Universidad Nacional de la Patagonia “San Juan Bosco”	
Universidad Nacional de Rosario	Universidad Nacional de Rosario
Universidad Nacional de San Luís	Universidad Nacional de San Luís
Universidad Nacional de Tucumán	Universidad Nacional de Tucumán
	Universidad Tecnológica Nacional
Universidad Nacional de Salta	Universidad Nacional de Salta
Universidad Nacional del Centro de la Provincia de Buenos Aires	Universidad Nacional del Centro de la Provincia de Buenos Aires
Universidad Nacional de Gral. Sarmiento	Universidad Nacional de Gral. Sarmiento
Universidad Nacional de la Pampa	Universidad Nacional de la Pampa
	Universidad Nacional de Chilecito
Universidad Nacional de Formosa	Universidad Nacional de Formosa
	Universidad Nacional de la Patagonia Austral
Universidad Nacional de la Rioja	Universidad Nacional de la Rioja
Universidad Nacional de las Artes	Universidad Nacional de las Artes
Universidad Nacional de Luján	Universidad Nacional de Luján
Universidad Nacional de Río Cuarto	Universidad Nacional de Río Cuarto
Universidad Nacional de Tres de Febrero	Universidad Nacional de Tres de Febrero
Universidad Nacional de Misiones	
Universidad Nacional del Noroeste de la Provincia de Buenos Aires	Universidad Nacional del Noroeste de la Provincia de Buenos Aires
	Universidad Nacional de Villa María

Table III.3.2 PUs beneficiaries in both PPUA calls

Own elaboration.

Chapter IV: Rhetorical Internationalization:

The Pattern

IV.1 A model to aid understanding. General considerations

As stated above, the internationalization process has been characterized and described from different perspectives that were understood and used in a complementary way.

Improving and simplifying access to institutional information implies a greater investment of time, not only for analyzing but also for generating conclusions. As presented in this thesis, it implies a qualitative leap in both the analysis and the conclusions generated from investigating the internationalization process' patterns in the PhD research.

It is the understanding of the Author that this is why, in many of the studies in the body of literature and much of the research made on the subject, the focus of analysis and conclusions related to the internationalization process are centered upon the following:

1)

The set of activities that are developed within the HEI which seek to promote or strengthen the international dimension of teaching, research or the institution's services, or of any of the aforementioned functions in particular.

2)

Analyses which regard the institutional strategy as the internationalization dynamic's fundamental element and that of the process which chooses and

administers the HEI univocally, with the purpose of encompassing the entire institution on the way to integrating the international dimension in its functions.

Whether it is because individual activities are adopted as institutional activities, such as those institutional decisions which lead to the creation of policies which support some of their functions internationalization actions, time as an element of comparative value is rarely mentioned and its use is limited to observing or analyzing the progress of the internal process. As Brandenburg & Federkeil (2007) note, from a present situation to a desired future, it will be possible to analyze and make decisions in order to state the desired improvement or correct the errors, and, in doing so, weaken the specific weight that the *institutional rhetoric* possesses.

This perspective adds to the internationalization cycle of de Wit (2001) that was mentioned before. One can again observe the existence of a dynamic which can be established under a temporary analysis that begins in the present time (N). In de Wit's terms, it is developed to obtain feedback and starting over process. The author of this Thesis refers directly to time as an element or factor for the analysis - to move forward following the cycle until returning to an (N) situation, which the author understands we must comprehend as being an improved situation given the cycle's explicit characteristics. The starting stage will be what is called the Analysis of Context, and a later advancement to the Awareness stage, and thus, continue on the path of integrating the international dimension to the HEI's basic functions.

An enlightening feature here will be the *time factor*. It is a core element for the observation and improvement of the internationalization process as long as the definitions, conclusions, and proposals that are generated come from the *true institutional*

reality and the *present institutional dynamics*. That is, the use of time as an element of analysis will be beneficial if it is accompanied by the most accurate characterization of the *present institutional reality*, where *rhetoric internationalization* exists and should be identified, analyzed and, where possible, measured in order to establish *the real present situation* and thus, generate progress in the process of *future institutional internationalization*.

Rhetorical internationalization is defined as a **traceable and measurable** “factor” within the internationalization process. However, when taken as individual elements, activities carried out by the HEI - whether teaching, research, or service functions - do not allow one to identify the anchoring in the present institutional internationalization strategy, nor do they serve as indicators of the path that the institution has chosen in order to integrate an international institutional dimension, according to the reality that the institution itself did demonstrate.

Thus, rhetorical internationalization constitutes and shapes the internationalization process and the amount and importance of such rhetoric within the process will help explain the level of institutionalization, the level of importance, the national and international support capacity, as well as a profile of a reactive or proactive model of internationalization, as developed by Rudzki (1998). But, it will be shown how much adding of individual or integrating institutional interests was undertaken in order to internationalize the HEI in a concrete national/international context.

Generally – though not exclusively – one will be able to identify the way in which the process might be related or initiated by an external decision “or driver” throughout a program, via some activity or funding directed at promoting, generating or strengthening a HEI’s Internationalization, or even via the HEI’s action/reaction to that program/process.

Any internationalization strategy should be understood as the path along which a HEI is moving, through a managed process, from an X status of internationality at time(N) towards a modified actual status of increased internationality at time (Y). The presence and weight of *Rhetorical Internationalization* – as elements or factors – constitute evidence from the managed advances as to whether they will be executed or not in order to internationalize the HEI. Otherwise, they will demonstrate whether an HEI had anything to do with the process or not. At this point, it will be demonstrated the existence of a pattern which is identifiable from the perspective of the institutional reality, and that of the activities which lead or do not lead forward.

By steering towards the desired level, *Rhetorical Internationalization* will shift (or increase) institutional importance, decreasing the time it takes to make policy decisions and thus, reducing the amount of *Rhetorical Internationalization* which shapes the institutional process.

University websites play a fundamental role, as aforementioned. They are the source to confront – or even search for – the results expressed by the external drivers, by the institutions themselves and by the reality that is shown. In other words, University websites act as the reality which HEIs indicate and allow themselves to be as a type of document that will facilitate the identification and existence of rhetorical internationalization.

Argentinean HEIs under analysis are characterized by: strong weight for individual activities/actions (within the process); an absence of institutional targets (or unclear targets); a discourse supporting every single activity carried out with international partners (at an official level); these are disconnected from the HEI's overall website image. There is a low organic hierarchy for the IRO within the HEI. Thus, the HEI's main's activities are carried out as a reply to individual/national/external drivers (e.g.,

communications, national calls, international calls, memorandums of understanding (MoUs), etc. – i.e., within the Microsoft Excel chart/spreadsheet annex). The strong importance from a) national driver's/stakeholders, and b) external drivers are shown by the IRO's characteristics (i.e., structure or division generated by the website as well as programs, calls, and activities shared within the website).

Last, but not least, every step performed in order to characterize or analyze the internationalization status at time (N) and the rhetorical influence must be understood while considering whether the HEI describes/presents/expresses its plans/strategies to internationalize itself (and the interests behind the strategies) or not. In both cases the chosen path will be demonstrated.

The main point for searching will be what a HEI says/shows/expresses/reports about internationalization through its own website. This information must be considered and should be understood as *the chosen institutional reality* – the field proof. The information gathered navigating the website will support or reject the existence of rhetorical internationalization as well as help measure its weight.

In other words, the stronger the *rhetorical internationalization* within the HEI, the more difficult it will be to explain the internationalization process, international interests, the activities carried out, MoUs signed, etc. through their own website and, of course, the parameters which exist to achieve it (and the more difficult it will be to observe internal organizational changes through time). The weaker the rhetorical internationalization is, the easier it will be to find and explain interests, activities, MoUs signed, and the path selected to achieve the desired integration (organizational and strategic changes versus time).

First, interests must express/demonstrate the goal sought by the HEI. Second, developed actions and activities should be linked to and connected with the strategy

selected to achieve it/them. Third, the instruments/tools created to facilitate the process should be embraced and understood by the entire institution, specifically by their IRO, as the institutional unit's driving the process. Fourth, autonomy and managerial capacity must be ensured throughout the unit or organ (Davies, 1992) while carrying out the activities in a proactive way (Rudzki, 1998) within the internationalization circle. Last but not least, the interplay of external and internal conditions needs to be added (Hunter, 2013) in order to generate an institutional approach to Internationalization as a strategy for responsiveness tailored to each HEI's particular culture and interests. Any choice made in order to internationalize will require a selection of certain strategic, structural, and institutional support (p. 67).

Whether the HEI stays at the first stage or at the D quadrant, rhetorical internationalization will always be found. The point to analyze and debate should be the weight within the process and the time taken to generate institutional decisions in order to diminish it and turn it into a strength.

Meanwhile, adding individual interests can be verified through several factors: a) mobility and institutional actions lead everywhere and support individuals' actions = at an Individual level; b) MoUs are signed with any Institution = at a Faculty-Institute level; c) Everything done will justify and imply the Internationalization of the institution = at an HEI level. Thus, they are the main elements with which to identify the weight of rhetorical internationalization within the HEI strategy. The additional presence without precedents or standards is where the internationalization process should be defined as a chaotic internationalization within which the cycle will be useless.

Simultaneously, integration should be verified through the implemented decisions which drive the process, which are once again verified through some factor such as: a) mobility and institutional actions also had strategic options becoming individuals' actions

and institutional planned benefits as well = Individual level; b) MoUs will be signed with institutions interested in fostering cooperation vis à vis = Faculty-Institute level – and HEI level; c) Internationalization will be understood as “this”; therefore the institution decided to do it following “x” plan to internationalize itself = HEI level. Though ultimately one follows (or backtracks) upon the path drawn, verifying that each level is represented within the process in a coherent and evaluable/ measurable Strategy. This makes the cycle worthy of the effort and causes it to flow harmoniously.

One of the distinguishing and repeated characteristics which exists in all the quadrants - whatever their level of institutional development might be - is the clear decision defined as awareness - or the necessary decision perhaps if one considers one’s own scarcity - to spread existing global opportunities to access funds, grants, and scholarships for mobility. Notwithstanding, there are the access funds offered by other institutions, which are usually copying or linking the information without indicating the presence of professional units within the IROs which require the necessary technical support.

As progress is made in the degree of institutional formalization granted to the unit in charge of the process, organizational structure and standardized procedures within the unit itself and within the institution start to be identified, which allow one to address the following questions in a precise manner. What does the HEI understand internationalization to be? Why does the HEI push internationalization forward? How does the HEI intend to carry internationalization forward?

But it is also important to emphasize that in the same way, it is clarified that internationalization is understood to be a process which is managed and linked to whoever manages or carries out the process; for whom it is carried forward; and with the amount

of time (N) necessary to make decisions that measurably modify the degree of awareness and commitment the HEI has with respect to the desired process.

Thus, internationalization will evolve from being an individual goal to being an institutional process in which the target group commits itself, in order to integrate with the institutional life in a comprehensive way.

IV.2 The model

As part of the framework which grants possibilities of being validated within the process approach (de Wit, 2005), there are activities identified as key components of internationalization in any HEI selected. In order to locate those components in one of the quadrants, the focus will be placed on the Organizational Strategies category: initiatives which help to ensure that activities seeking to integrate an international dimension are institutionalized through the chosen path.

Within Knight's clarification, one can observe the context and search for the possibility of elements that confirm the existence of rhetorical internationalization from within the HEI itself.

At the institutional level, policies can be interpreted in different ways. A narrow interpretation would include those statements and directives that refer to priorities and plans related to the international dimension of the institution's mission, purpose, values, and functions. This could include the institutional mission statement or policies on study abroad, student recruitment, international linkages and partnerships, cross-border delivery, international sabbaticals, and so forth. A broader interpretation of policies at the institution level would include those statements, directives, or planning documents that address implications for or from internationalization. If the institution has taken an integrative and sustainable approach to internationalization, then a very broad range of policy and procedure statements would be implicated ranging from quality assurance, planning, finances, staffing, faculty development, admission, research, curriculum, student support, contract and project work, and so forth (Knight, 2004, p. 16).

Figure IV.2.1 Model of Rhetorical Internationalization
Own elaboration.

First, the way to approach this must consider the axes upon which the different analyses are formulated. There are four axes:

The First Higher Axis, where the dynamic always runs from AD HOC to SYSTEMATIC, allows us to observe the existence of advances in the degree of institutionalization within the analyzed HEI which will imply the reduction of the specific weight of the Rhetorical internationalization within the institutional behavior;

The Second Left Axis, where the dynamics always advance from MARGINAL to CENTRAL, and where the increase of the importance of internationalization in the HEI will be observed implying a reduction of the specific weight of the internationalization within the institutional investment towards the process;

The Third Lower Axis, where the dynamics will go from TURBULENT to STABLE, or vice versa, allows one to observe, describe, and analyze the advantages and disadvantages given (or granted) by the national system and the possibilities of impact in Axes 1 and 2;

The Fourth Right Axis, where the dynamic will go from STATIC to DYNAMIC, or vice versa, allows us to observe, describe, and analyze its degree of importance along with the advantages and disadvantages that one or several international drivers give (or gave) and the possibilities of impact within Axes 1 and 2;

For Axes 1 and 2, the author does not consider the existence of an inverse dynamic “to-from” that is. What can be observed is either a decrease in the real location of the degree of institutionalization or the level of importance of internationalization in any HEI. This is because the extent of which Rhetorical Internationalization is identified and loses a specific weight in the process makes it impossible for it to be modified in a negative

way. The characteristics of the dynamics in rhetorical internationalization imply that it is possible - and so in fact, one can observe stagnation at one instance within the Argentine case under study in this PhD thesis - but one would not find regression once the stage has been overcome.

In other words, it is possible that through time measurement stagnations that are observed and maintained in one or both axes one could find evidence about the specific weight that rhetorical internationalization has within the institutional status quo or how it is rooted within the institutional culture. In these cases, the use of instruments for monitoring or evaluating the process should be more complex.

Regarding Axes 3 and 4, according to what could be observed in the selected stage, it must be indicated that they have a dynamic that goes from one end to the other, and this dynamic does not respond to the HEI's individual characteristics and how they carry out their internationalization process. Rather, the axes respond to their own interests, values, objectives, etc., and, as result, as time advances, they can disappear or be modified, increased, divided, etc.. This can be observed, for example, in the Argentine National case as well as in the case of the existence of bilateral EMA2s1 projects on Argentina's side.

In addition, the same observation parameter allows for the application of the model which permits it to adjust to a more specific level e.g., a) Faculty level, where the Lower Axis will be the HEI and the Right Axis will be the national context; and, b) research group level where the Lower Axis will be the Faculty and the Right Axis will be the HEI.

Under these characteristics one should consider that the rhetorical internationalization elements will potentially be more visible, as is the access to basic information (raw data) that will allow for analyzing the degree or level of changes in Axes

1 and 2, which should also be simpler. As a consequence, the analysis of the process and cycle in the selected HEI is strengthened.

But what will make the model valuable is that in this expansion of the most basic level within the HEI one can visualize the path, patterns, and activities that make the process from the micro reality of the lower echelons of the institution to the macro reality of the HEI. This is where one can contemplate whether the rhetoric also accompanies the process in the mentioned units, or if it is an element that arises at the top of the institutional organization.

In short, its application to analyze the internationalization performance may be for use by the HEI's, the Faculty, the Institute, or the Research group; and it could also be used at the national level. Notwithstanding, the degree of reduction in its application will depend on the degree of specificity required to observe and analyze the existence of progress in the real internationalization process.

All of the above will delve into the model presented, inferring from here the circumstances that from the most general context (the Right Axis), intermediate context (the Lower Axis) to the most specific context (Axes 1 and 2) let one see the state of the institutional internationalization process at the date of application Time (N) will give a result regarding the position/location of (X), and also the direction where it should be advancing. An element that will facilitate this measurement will be the dynamics that the MoUs possess with respect to the planned reality (see Annex 4).

Note that the fundamental value of the variables mentioned are the sum of those specified by Rudzki, Hunter, and Davies that considered as a whole, and applying the cycle of Knight (1994) and De Wit (2001), allow for adding the rhetorical internalization factor from highest to lowest in the specific weight of the explanation for each quadrant. This results in showing the extent to which the "ideal" is advanced in its acknowledged

existence, but as an element which accompanies the dynamics of the process and internal changes in order to respond to the internal-external context which Hunter (2013) defines. It is considered that once the last quadrant is “reached” then INSTITUTIONAL modifications are precluded. However, there may be modification of who manages it, as aforementioned.

Rhetorical STAGE:

1.- Information published on the Web refers to opportunities with no institutional ties (no connection searchable at first step) The Author refers to the international opportunities or proposals of actions that are reported within the institutional website when searching for RRII.

2.- IRO hierarchy is unknown and cannot be found inside the organizational scheme.

3.- There is no institutional strategy (or this is not visible and apparent, or it is located somewhere else within the entire HEI website) that refers to the Internationalization process, its goals, plan, actions, among other elements.

4.- A bulky number of MoUs are shown.

5.- The absence of assessment for the conducted activities is evident.

6.- No information from previous years is accessible or is segmented into something else (e.g., into external program from the European Union, where the HEI just shares that program).

7.- Absence of contact information (IRO contacts or authorities from other areas such as staff, administrative officers, boards, among others).

The dimensions to be identified for the analysis of the existence and specific weight of rhetorical internationalization for Axes 1 and 2 are: a. Governance; b. Operations; c. Services; and d. Human Resources. Within them, and although not

thorough here is a list with some general characteristics that can be refined or adjusted to other realities from the same data collection format as is offered for each quadrant. Furthermore, they are also valid to use and analyze in the rhetorical stage.

QUADRANT A

A.1. Opportunities are linked to offers from different Agents, Organizations, Embassies, and so forth without any strategic institutional interest and/or supporting activities derived from them. They are a window for opportunities (i.e., solely a window to open grants and scholarships) within the webpage.

A.2. The IRO hierarchy is unknown within the institution organizational chart (it is neither defined nor explained). Internationalization or international relations/cooperation will be related to some unit other than the IRO.

A.3. There is no formal Strategy guiding the HEI. A broad description of Internationalization, quoting scholars' definitions, or a list of general intentions described as the goals will be found.

A.4. A wide number of MoUs is shown. The existence of results from collaboration within their framework is not expressed or clearly linked to HEI activities but they are expressed individually. There is a disconnection with shared opportunities, as well as an absence of an open system made for tracking levels, activities, profiles, interests, and so forth through the international partners.

A.5. There is an absence of monitoring and evaluation tools that can be applied to the internationalization process through decisions applied to improve any unit, faculty, or human resource engaged with it.

A.6. There is neither accessible general information or information tracking system from previous years, nor is information segmented into partners, targets, fields of science, world regions, among others.

A.7. There is no email address in the contact details so as to facilitate any kinds of requests.

QUADRANT B

B.1. There are some limited opportunities connected to activities carried out by/with HEI/Network partners. These are shown as international opportunities/international grants/ international scholarships within the IRO Webpage.

B.2. The hierarchy of the IRO as an internationalization unit is known and is included in the institution's organizational chart. The characteristics of the unit are presented and the scope and goals are broadly defined with no deep explanation regarding the process followed to internationalize. One could assign an intermediate location within the institutional chart (a medium level) with the possibility of participating in making decisions regarding the process but without the economic autonomy or the independence of the indicated units as being of a higher hierarchy.

B.3. There is a Strategy guiding the HEI that includes a description about the process of Internationalization selected. The strategy is defined by making reference to scholars' definitions and concepts about internationalization. It presents a short list of activities supported and carried out within the HEI through the IRO and the expected outcomes are mentioned.

B.4. A list of operational/active MoUs is shown. The most important MoUs are highlighted in order to embed and improve activities supported by the HEI at all levels. It presents the connection between the individual promoter, the institutional interests and the results searched by them and has an open list to track, search and identify

opportunities between the international partners. It includes a list of formal steps necessary to accomplish the establishment of a MoU with a potential partner.

B.5. Activities are evaluated and tools present results from previous years. There is an open system to access and download administrative and policy acts related to internationalization, which reflect how the HEIs develop the process, analyze it, and improve it (at every internal level for their human resources, and for any international action).

B.6. Information from previous years can be downloaded as graphic/s or slide/s. Generally speaking, one will be able to appreciate general numbers presented as the results from the internationalization process which is being followed. One will not be able to reach/track or deepen into the data or find a comparison between previous years and the goals achieved. However, there will be a contact email address where one can ask for specific data.

B.7. There is a list with the team and short profiles with each member's e-mail address to contact them.

QUADRANT C

C.1. There is a great number of opportunities linked to offers from different Agents, Organizations, Embassies, and so forth. The majority of these groups do not have any strategic institutional interest and/or supporting activities behind them. Individual interests are primary in their diffusion and all are shown to be international opportunities. These are found within the IRO Webpage without any type of order or division according to Internal target groups.

C.2. The IRO is presented as part of the HEI, and is dependent on a formal higher unit within the organizational chart. However, its hierarchy is blurred within the

institution organizational chart. Activities carried out are listed but not defined or explained. It can be placed in the lowest hierarchy range within the institutional chart. Without being able to participate in the decision-making process regarding the internationalization process, it acts as an administrative and information gathering unit for the unit on which it depends. It generally is directly dependent on the Rector or Vice-rector.

C.3. There is a broad explanation about what the Strategy's significance is, with no connections or description about the institutional steps to formalize and improve the institutional process. A list of activities shown are noted as the process in itself. Within those, a list with results or outcomes from specific activities with partners are published as a proof of the *level of internationalization* without any information supporting whether they were planned/operationalized either by the IRO or by the person in charge.

C.4. A large list of MoUs is shown. Even though some might present results (with or without institutional support), they are mainly not presented or explained by the opportunities they represent for the HEI; there is no tool to track or search for deeper information than the MoU itself and sometimes the promoters. Any individual with an institutional link will potentially be able to advance and establish an MoU with a potential partner.

C.5. There is a general description about the steps performed in order to improve the activities – but this appears to be more of a desire than a performed reality. However, the internationalization is not assessed. There is no information about institutional acts to improve the process and there are no political statements supporting the engagement at different institutional levels (i.e., unit, individual, faculty, HEI) or even for specializing its human resources.

C.6. There are numbers listed within the website indicating e.g. incoming international students, MoUs, countries' HEIs, partners' HEIs, networks membership, and so forth (outdated information). No accessible general/specific data for previous years, nor segmented data related to partners, targets, fields of science, world regions, and so forth. For further details can be addressed by using the corresponding e-mail address.

C.7. There is an e-mail address responsible for queries and a second e-mail address responsible for enrollment/mobility issues.

QUADRANT D

D.1. Opportunities created and/or supported by the institution are listed and grouped by categories and levels. The section presents those activities (e.g. scholarships, institutional/national/international grants, network grants, and so forth) related with the integration of the international dimension and tied to the institutional expectations shown. There is another section covering a general and open list of international opportunities updated. Both sections not only have a frequently asked questions (FAQs) section but also specific staff members to contact in order to receive technical support.

D.2. The IRO is located at the highest level within the organizational chart. Along with the institutional act creating it, the unit is presented, along with its characteristics, responsibilities within the Internationalization Strategy defining its mid- and long-term goals, as well as activities planned in order to improve the process comprehensively. The internal divisions, available staff, connection, and activities with a board of advisers/counselors engaged with the process are shown. There is an Interinstitutional Council acting at the Macro-, Meso-, and Micro levels (provosts, deans, directors, professors, scholars) who are supporters that challenge the discourse as well as a selected Strategy and they appear to be willing to improve it. The IRO has the institutional power and autonomy to develop, create, invest, and propose changes within the process. Thus,

it can create opportunities once they are detected without losing time or struggling with any institutional/cultural particular status quo.

D.3. The Strategy is presented within the HEI's Strategy Plan for period (N). The rationales and approaches selected to achieve the planned goals, and the mission assigned to the IRO are specifically described. The shared concept arises as an institutional reality response, expressing not only the institutional engagement with internationalization but the levels of embedment and awareness which exists regarding its dynamic. It explains how the HEI integrates or mitigates (and who deals with) the differences within the internal and/or individual interests (at the activity, program, and institutional policy levels). Activities developed and supported are presented within the IRO structure and the institutional expectations regarding it.

D.4. There is a list with operational MoUs highlighting the target groups, topics, regions, networks and international partners within them. This database allows one to search permitted activities, given support, and results expected to advance for. Information about motivations and promoters – which are the reason to maintain its activities – are accessible, and one can connect with them by e-mail. Lastly, there is a section explaining how an MoU works, why and when the HEI might analyze, support, and proceed or not with a signature process, and the institutional expectations behind them. Who manages the process? For whom is the process undertaken? And what time period is covered? These are questions to answer as a single rule to verify how much concern the HEI has for MoUs.

D.5. Evaluating and monitoring protocols and tools at internal level are presented. Results are periodically published. There is a broad explanation about activities carried out in order to improve the institutional process. Institutional acts, protocols, administrative actions, and policy acts related to the process are accessible and

downloadable for the HEI community. How a formal/real engagement within the HEIs community with the process will imply formal benefits for themselves is also explained (e.g. financial support, institutional certificates, extra points within internal grants calls, access to salary raises, career compensations, and so forth). Evaluation certificates which have been received will be shown as well as the results of each self-evaluation with the recommendation list received.

D.6. Institutional management reports are presented with qualitative and quantitative data. Comparisons between years are possible. Information contains statistics, graphics, and explanations about the HEI's performance (at the institute, faculty, and HEI levels). Achievements within the selected strategy and challenges for the future are also presented. Specific data e.g. networks, degrees, mobilities (in-out) are accessible information, as well as levels, patents, articles, books, research, congress, studies taught in foreign languages, international students/professors/researchers/staff, rankings, and so on. There is an IRO contact for further details, and the person in charge has an e-mail address provided for specific queries.

D.7. The IRO's unit is presented individually. Each person is presented with a short BIO. Within it one is able to read that they have/had an international experience, what divisions they are responsible for, and that they hold at least a bachelor degree. The IRO also presents its internal divisions and how to contact any of them (by phone, e-mail) and includes the schedules of their office hours. Lastly, the officers' functions and duties, section managers, and the Head are all explained.

A valid clarification for its application in the observation and analysis is that the characteristics described above in each of the quadrants are not considered restrictive or exclusive regarding the location of the HEI in any of the presented quadrants. This means that it will be possible to find characteristics that respond to a quadrant in an institution

which, due to its general profile, is possible to be located in another one of the quadrants. For example, in particular, it has some characteristic of quadrant C but is located in quadrant B. This is not synonymous with the fact that it is found within both, but it shows that the process is dynamic per se, and that situations can occur with more than one quadrant's characteristics. Yet weighing all characteristics (including others which are added) will result in the quadrant profile to which the noted HEI corresponds, given that they are characteristics which help identify what happens in the joint institutional reality. In other words, the descriptions do not function as limits to rhetorical internationalization, but rather they facilitate the possibility of determining their specific weight and the analysis of the HEI's behavior with its internationalization process in an integral way and not by individualities.

IV.3 Considerations for analyzing internationalization in the Argentine case

While searching to add the aforementioned element, for the selected case, in this PhD research a lapse of 10 years was contemplated for the analysis. The period has the characteristic of having had: a) on the one hand two specific calls to generate, strengthen and improve the process of PUs' internationalization developed in Chapter IV of this thesis; and, b) the presence of eight projects with European funding, which indicated among their objectives to seek to improve and strengthen the capacities of non-European partners in the theme developed in Chapter III of this thesis.

According to *Lower Axis 3* the characteristics developed in Chapter IV of this thesis allow one to assert that for the period of observed time (N): 1) it was STABLE given the certainty granted to the development of the PUs' internationalization, as well as to the generation or strengthening of the units responsible for carrying it forward; and, 2) that this should facilitate the description and analysis of the impact on the process of HEI's internationalization that was studied when observing Axis 1 and Axis 2.

With these elements it should be feasible to identify and locate in the institutional realities, that is to say in Axis 1 regarding Institutionalization; and in Axis 2 regarding the Importance of Internationalization, which as direct results would be a real increase in the general percentages of the PUs and their IROs.

The complexity of the actors' direct participation in the study as a result of their own actions has been indicated. The reasoning behind the use of their own websites, as a reinforcement to the documentary analysis of both calls and institutional realities has also been previously indicated in the methodological section of this thesis. That presents the possibility of contemplating the set's results in a simple reading model that would facilitate the aggregation of factors that arise. Further, along with the group of authors mentioned in Chapter I of this thesis, that would facilitate the comparison as long as it is

based on - or possible to generate - a present situation that contemplates the information of the 4 axes used here.

This situation facilitated the possibility of establishing a situational picture of the present for the case studied in order to observe the existence of real changes in the PUs' internationalization process dynamics.

To do this, the situation regarding the IROs for year 2005, year 2008, and for year 2015 for the whole of Argentina are presented in the graphs; and, for the PUs that benefited from one of the two national calls and that were also members of some EMA2.

The set of participants for year 2015 are the PUs that benefited from at least one EMA2 and also had national funding for the development or strengthening of their internationalization process, as previously described in this thesis.

Figure IV.3.1 IROs situation 2005

Source: Theiler (2005, p. 96)

Own Elaboration.

Figure IV.3.2 IROS situation 2008
 Source: Agnese (2011, p. 5)
 Own Elaboration.

Figure IV.3.3 IROS in Argentinean EMA2 partners 2015
 Source: Annex 1
 Own Elaboration, Annex 1.

Figure IV.3.4 IROs in Argentine PUs 2015
 Source: Annex 1
 Own Elaboration.

Figure IV.3.5 Dynamic of IROs in 10 years
 Sources: Theiler (2005); Agnese (2011); Annex 1
 Own Elaboration.

Table IV.3.1 reflects the results obtained in the final collection of information for the 27 PUs which acceded to one or both national financings in order to develop or

strengthen their IROs; and the previous results plus one private HEI that were part of at least one EMA2s2 in the analyzed period.

Universities	First National Call 2006	EADIC 2009	EADICII 2010	MoE 2010	EUROTANGO 2010	Second National Call 2010	EUROTANGO 2 2011	ARTESS 2011	EUROPLATA 2011	ARCOIRIS 2011	Hierarchy IRO 2015
Universidad Nacional de La Plata	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	3
Universidad Nacional del Sur	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	2
Universidad Nacional de Córdoba	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	2
Universidad Nacional del Litoral	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	1
Universidad Nacional del Nordeste	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	4
Universidad Nacional de San Juan	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	4
Universidad de Buenos Aires	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	1
Universidad Nacional de Catamarca	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	1
Universidad Nacional de Río Negro	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	4
Universidad Nacional de San Martín	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	4
Universidad Nacional de Lanús	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	3
Universidad Nacional de Santiago del Estero	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	3
Universidad Nacional del Comahue	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	2
Universidad Nacional de Cuyo	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	1
Universidad Nacional de Quilmes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	3

ITBA - Instituto Tecnológico de Buenos Aires	No	No	No	No	Yes	ND						
Universidad Nacional del Mar del Plata	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	4
Universidad Nacional de Entre Ríos	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No	4
Universidad Nacional de Jujuy	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No	4
Universidad Nacional de la Patagonia “San Juan Bosco”	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	4
Universidad Nacional de Rosario	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No	1
Universidad Nacional de San Luís	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No	1
Universidad Nacional de Tucumán	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	3
Universidad Tecnológica Nacional	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	1
Universidad Nacional de Salta	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	1
Universidad Nacional del Centro de la Provincia de Buenos Aires	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	4
Universidad Nacional de Gral. Sarmiento	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	0
Universidad Nacional de la Pampa	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	0

Table IV.3.1 PUs beneficiaries and their IRO hierarchies for 2015

Own elaboration.

Rhetorical STAGE: Chapter V: CONCLUSIONS and Recommendations / Summary / Future Discussions

From the very beginning, five initial reasonable and other questions were at the forefront of this PhD research thesis: 1) Does the HEI add or integrate interests from each level? 2) Does it generate a benefit in order to advance within the process? 3) Does rhetoric fulfill a mission within the strategy? 4) Does it accompany and favor the changes that occur as the process progresses; and 5) Does it allow the HEI to adjust the interests of each group within the institution's stakeholders and strengthen its international dimension?

Or is it actually a factor that has become an instrument which helps describe the decisions of what it does, and also what the HEI does or does not do in terms of internationalization? Is it possible to identify the existence of rhetorical internationalization using some element that all HEIs use? And, does that element serve to demonstrate existence and also measure it?

Are HEIs integrating or adding interests to plan their internationalization strategies? Are they planning at all, or simply reacting to the context?

The device with which to analyze the generating of a measure would be within easy reach. Does one want to know or really understand and fix the problem and what about resolving both; understanding and fixing?

When rhetoric assumes a place within the process, the ideal which is followed goes to the rhetorical internationalization ground. Thus, everything is about

internationalization. When rhetoric helps, internationalization is thus rhetorical and the HEI decides to use rhetorical internationalization at time (N). By measuring MoUs, one should be able to identify not just the level of activeness but the level of rhetorical internationalization within the institutional reality through the time (see Annex 4).

This Author is not dictating that all universities are potentially international; because many have reached a degree (X) of internationality, but some universities do work towards improving the process of internationalization internally; while none escape the established rhetorical internationalization within them. Yes, we can consider that a point which must be quantified and which is a key point is the time consumed to mobilize and decide upon an element of the aforementioned rhetoric into the internationalization process from a decision made to strengthen or improve it.

One cannot measure the world's Internationalization level and progress. However, what one could/can aim at is the measuring of the level of Rhetorical Internationalization (choosing one or more tools used to internationalize, i.e., MoUs) in a particular national system, by measuring its HEI and how they perform the process within a national and international context. Although, if one can prove it with solid evidence, then it will be possible to generate a *real stage in the internationalization process* approach in whatever country, region, continent, or in the world.

One must consider that each country has its own cooperation pattern, cultural characteristics, HEI bureaucracy patterns, economic interests, and so on. All of them have rhetorical internationalization at a certain level. But every institution develops a different approach in order to reduce the rhetorical aspect. However, the comprehensiveness regarding the internationalization process might be understood through this lens.

The concept of rhetorical internationalization should be the link between the Grounded Theory and other theories. Thus, the path towards comprehensive

internationalization will be more than a political discourse/statement shared with the community.

In order to enlighten understanding in a real and measurable process of internationalization, one must assess rhetorical internationalization or at least identify its existence at a certain level if one wishes to evaluate and compare any proactive progress in the process of an HEI's internationalization.

As shown in *Figure IV.2.1 Model of Rhetorical Internationalization*, each HEI can indicate which quadrant it corresponds with. The decision to leave the same without completion is due to:

a.- As was widely developed in Chapter 1 of this thesis, internationalization is understood as a process that is necessarily dynamic, which would mean that at the time of presenting this PhD research, one or more of the indicated locations/ratings could likely be incorrect, since the rhetoric also is incorrect;

b.- The objective of this PhD research is to identify and describe a variable/factor or rhetorical internationalization that in the aftermath might facilitate the analysis, evaluation, or monitoring of an HEI's internationalization process at a specific time. Further, this would allow one to have a point that starts to draw the HEI's lines of behavior and action in terms of reality;

c.- Taking into account the possibility that an HEI is interested in advancing itself within a self-assessment, in consideration of the work performed in this thesis, it is

possible to use ANNEX 4 for that purpose, in which a table is presented that will facilitate the selection of the quadrant where the HEI is inserted at the moment of completing it, using the MoUs for it;

d.- Finally, as indicated in *One path, many activities, one pattern: Rhetorical Internationalization. Towards understanding the Internationalization of Argentine Public Universities*, the author's intention was to advance the understanding of internationalization of Argentina's PUs, taking into account a factor, identified as a pattern in the selected case of transduced time. The possibility of reaching this point and being able to identify which quadrant corresponds with each of the HEIs that met the aforementioned characteristics, implies a different way of understanding the internationalization process.

Maybe it can be an element that can be used and not only for national studies, but also as an element of the comparative development of internationalization. In order for this to happen, it must be analyzed and improved by adding a greater number of specific factors although they are common within HEIs to accurately limit more the degree of existence and the role of rhetorical internationalization within an HEI.

The possibility of covering, in part, the gap between the ideal to which authors, rectors, practitioners, researchers, and others refer; and the reality in the HEIs has been covered. It is necessary to advance in the study of the *institutional behaviors* towards the internationalization question and its internal process. As well as the observation of such behaviors beyond what they say they do, if what is sought is the permanent improvement in a process that is dynamic by nature.

That is primary motive of this PhD research thesis, in aiming at elucidating on the difference between what was held when observing the potentialities and opportunities in the aforementioned context and what the institutions actually do in reality order to advance in the aforementioned process.

Considering rhetorical internationalization as an active component in the process of internationalization per se, facilitated an understanding of the sphere which is analyzed in this thesis. As was observed in the course of this PhD research, the national contextual elements and the external international context should have led to an advance or modification in the status of the areas or units responsible for carrying out the process, as a probative element of the value assigned to the internationalization within the PUs.

According to the time slice/period analyzed for retrieval and analysis of the scant information referring to the reality of the IROs in the PUs as a sample element of the reality of Argentina's HEIs' internationalization, the data generated along with the identified elements allow the present Author to assert that it is not possible to identify a change or improvement in the process of the HEIs' internationalization, and by default in the specific weight of the internationalization within the said process, if it is not an internal decision in the first place.

As the research conducted at such an open, progressive and internationally oriented university as the University of Oxford proves, there is no possibility of substantial improvements in internationalization without changing university culture (Ovseiko et al., 2019). As Natalia Volkova and Maria Plakhotnik very recently noticed, culture still tends to be neglected in research into higher education, including internationalization processes:

very little is known about organizational factors, such as university culture, mission, structure, and planning, that serve as a foundation or glue for academic factors during

university internationalization. How these factors help in uniting internal stakeholders, such as faculty, staff, and students, during internationalization remains unclear. (2021, p.3)

The aim of this dissertation was to fill the gap and to provide better and deeper understanding of how the internationalization of modern universities works. It is the process that is defined not only by national and institutional policies but that is shaped by culture of people involved in supporting (or, unfortunately, preventing) internationalization.

Of course, one cannot notice the shift of university cultures across the globe, making higher education institutions more like business corporations than temples of wisdom. Marketization of universities and commodification of knowledge resulted in some substantial changes.

The ideal conception of the university—as a public sphere that truly fosters progressive pedagogies and an educational culture that cultivates critically-reflexive sensibilities and practices in its students—morphs into something akin to a scientifically-managed production line such that opportunities for self-exploration and personal growth become avenues for “professional development,” the acquisition of a “relevant” skill-set, and collecting the requisite credits, internships, and service requirements so as to most “effectively” credential one’s resume to improve one’s “job prospects.” (Elavsky, 2012, p. 298)

The evolution of universities, leading to the emergence of “scientifically-managed production line” is also affecting processes (and future perspectives) of internationalization.

The possibilities of generating an improvement based on conditions, factors and actors at are external to the institution were not sufficient elements to break the institutional status quo, much less to transform rhetorical internationalization into a factor that mobilizes the institution towards change.

This is what this Author refers to when discussing internationalization as a pre-science, without letting us forget the words of the Argentine doctor, professor, and pharmacist, Dr. Bernardo A. Houssay (1887-1971): “*Science is universal, and truth is everywhere*”. In order to advance within this Author’s search for truth at a specific moment and regarding his interest in finding out what is true regarding the process of internationalization, the fact is that this model cannot be replicated, which is a serious point for consideration. However, this does not imply that its application might not facilitate the institutional reality’s analysis regarding the chosen internationalization process in present time (N).

Appendix 1 - Argentine Public Universities – IROs chart

<i>University/N° EMA2/students Number 2012 yearbook</i>	N° Employees	Hierar chy	N° Subcategori es	Types	Mission/Visions	Extra data	Webpage for foreigners
Universidad Nacional de La Plata: 5/ 111.527		3°	5	Mb SA Cm Pj Ms	<p>Unidad de Relaciones Internacionales Universitarias - Institucional</p> <p>MISIÓN Generar políticas eficaces que permitan promover la cooperación internacional, potenciando la presencia de la Universidad Nacional de La Plata en la región y el mundo.</p> <p>VISIÓN Posicionar a la Universidad Nacional de La Plata como una institución educativa líder en el mundo.</p> <p>OBJETIVOS Humanizar y concientizar Ampliar los horizontes culturales, estableciendo caminos amplios de negociación. Vencer prejuicios y fomentar la solidaridad entre los países Conocer la mirada que se tiene internacionalmente de la UNLP</p>	<p>Esta Dirección plantea el desafío de ser la instancia articuladora de las relaciones internacionales universitarias implementando el acompañamiento de proyectos y convenios interuniversitarios junto al soporte logístico y operacional en las diversas instancias de relacionamiento de las unidades académicas.</p>	<p>English complete</p> <p>Portuguese (half) http://www.unlp.edu.ar/driu outdated</p>
Universidad Nacional del Sur: 4/ 19.476	6 Translator2 No titles 3 1 Informatics	2°	3	Mb Schp MoU	<p>La Universidad Nacional del Sur ha iniciado un proceso de Internacionalización como estrategia para renovar y mejorar la calidad de la educación superior que supone la formulación y puesta en práctica de una política de apertura hacia el exterior en la que debe involucrarse toda la comunidad universitaria. Una de las iniciativas para lograr este objetivo, fue la creación de la Subsecretaría de Relaciones Internacionales en el año 2007 que tiene a su cargo las acciones tendientes a promover:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . La movilidad de estudiantes, profesores, investigadores y administrativos. . La participación en redes de carácter regional e internacional. . La oferta educativa internacional. . Las titulaciones conjuntas. . Los acuerdos con instituciones de reconocido prestigio. . Las investigaciones conjuntas con grupos extranjeros. . La oferta de programas de enseñanza de idiomas y cultura locales. . La internacionalización de la curricula. 	<p>Spanish</p> <p>http://www.servicios.uns.edu.ar/institucion/ver_contenidos.asp?cod_entidad=406and_cod_contenido=94 updated</p>

<p>Universidad Nacional de Córdoba 4/ 107.542</p>	<p>19 7 graduates 2 accountants 1 master 2 translators 1 teacher 6 no titles</p>	<p>2°</p>	<p>7</p>	<p>Mb Cm Pj MoU EF HRA Spsh</p>	<p>En el marco del proceso de internacionalización de la Educación Superior, la Universidad Nacional de Córdoba posee la visión de transformarse en un centro académico con liderazgo en las relaciones académicas que Argentina establece con el sistema universitario internacional, contribuyendo a apoyar los valores de la educación pública, con calidad y equidad.</p> <p>La Prosecretaría de Relaciones Internacionales (PRI), coherente con esa visión, tiene como misión generar espacios de vinculación entre la UNC y diversos actores internacionales, a través de la promoción de proyectos de cooperación con instituciones de educación superior, redes académico-científicas, y organismos regionales y multilaterales. De esta misión se desprenden dos objetivos principales, uno que proyecta a la UNC y otro que la ofrece al mundo:</p> <p>1. Insertar productivamente a la UNC en el proceso de internacionalización de la educación superior, lo que conlleva las siguientes acciones generales:</p> <p>2. Ofrecer a la UNC como un centro académico de excelencia para los estudiantes extranjeros, de grado y posgrado, que deseen cursar estudios parciales o totales, lo que conlleva las siguientes acciones:</p>	<p>1.- .-Promoción de una cultura académica que reoriente a la comunidad universitaria hacia los nuevos modos de funcionamiento de la cooperación internacional. .- Acrecentamiento del intercambio y la movilidad estudiantil, de grado y posgrado, a través de becas y programas especiales. .- Estímulo a la participación de los profesores en programas y redes académicas internacionales de docencia e investigación. .- Promoción de convenios interinstitucionales en áreas estratégicas para el desarrollo de nuevos programas que articulen a la universidad con el desarrollo local y nacional. .- Fortalecimiento de los vínculos académicos con las redes regionales de educación superior para la integración latinoamericana.</p> <p>2.- .- Readecuación de la normativa y reglamentación en torno a los estudiantes internacionales. .- Puesta en marcha de un Programa especial para estudiantes internacionales (PECLA) con cursos de lengua española y cultura latinoamericana y argentina. .- Promoción de la UNC como un centro de excelencia para la formación permanente de graduados internacionales que persigan la capacitación en áreas específicas. .- Asesoramiento de potenciales alumnos, inscripción a la UNC, seguimiento y certificación por parte de la PRI. .- Trabajo articulado con las distintas unidades académicas de la UNC para encauzar a los nuevos estudiantes internacionales. .- Para llevar a cabo estos objetivos la PRI es el enlace entre las delegaciones extranjeras y la comunidad académica de la UNC,</p>	<p>Opportunities : English Rest: spanish http://www.unc.edu.ar/internacionales/gestion/pri updated</p>
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						propiciando nuevos acuerdos y fortaleciendo los numerosos convenios existentes.	
Universidad Nacional del Litoral: 5/43.236	19 (smth in charge) 1 Engineer 4 Lawyer 1 Architect 2 CPA (certified public accountant) 1 Vet 2 Graduates 3 Teacher 2 Master 2 no titles 1 technician	1°	11	Mb Nand A Pj IS EF OL ES Lng CD IAR RE+D	La UNL realiza numerosas acciones de cooperación internacional, con la convicción de que el conocimiento trasciende las fronteras geográficas y asume un carácter universal en el actual contexto de globalización. Consciente de los beneficios del intercambio científico entre su comunidad y la de otras instituciones del mundo (grupos de universidades, agencias de cooperación, fundaciones y organismos unilaterales), la Universidad, a través de su Secretaría de Relaciones Internacionales, establece acuerdos y convenios, participa activamente en foros y encuentros, promueve intercambios académicos y científicos, y realiza proyectos conjuntos en las áreas de educación, investigación y desarrollo tecnológico y social. En las acciones de proyección internacional, la UNL compromete sus capacidades y recursos, en la construcción de un espacio académico común y en el desarrollo de una cultura integrada	Each area has a paragraph explaining in general words the main goal.	English, French Portuguese by google translate – all - http://www.unl.edu.ar/categories/view/internacional#.VSUviPms XGA updated
Universidad Nacional del Nordeste 5/49.454	3 1 lawyer 1 Master 1 no title	4°	1		El Área de Cooperación Interinstitucional, es uno de los órganos de la Subsecretaría de Relaciones Interinstitucionales, cuya misión principal consiste en entender en la articulación de los diferentes sectores de la Universidad y su vinculación con el medio social. Actualmente es el área desde la cual se gestionan y promueven específicamente la mayor parte de las actividades de Internacionalización de la Educación Superior que lleva adelante la Universidad Nacional del Nordeste. Asimismo, se interviene en el trámite de los convenios que suscribe la Institución (sean provinciales, nacionales o internacionales), y le corresponde el archivo de los mismos. http://relint.unne.edu.ar/institucional a considerar por divisorio e historia.	son también sus funciones: .- Coordinar la vinculación de la Universidad con el medio social de la región. .- Promover la vinculación con diversas instituciones a fin de dar respuesta eficaz a las demandas específicas de la comunidad. .- Coordinar la gestión de convenios de cooperación y acuerdos específicos con Universidades, Instituciones Educativas, Organismos Internacionales, entre otros. .- Coordinar las acciones tendientes a favorecer la participación de la Universidad en Asociaciones, Grupos de Trabajo, Redes Nacionales e Internacionales, etc. .- Toda otra actividad vinculada a su competencia que le sea encomendada por el Sr. Rector de la Universidad.	Spanish http://relint.unne.edu.ar/cooperacion-internacional updated

Universidad Nacional de San Juan: 2/ 20.346	Secret (6) Area 3 1 Master 2 graduates	Area 4°	2	Mb Schp	<p>En pos de su internacionalización, la Universidad Nacional de San Juan se encuentra trabajando en la creación de una red con diversas universidades extranjeras que compartan su visión institucional, en el contexto de un marco de colaboración.</p> <p>En el proceso de formación de esta red se han firmado convenios de colaboración con instituciones de educación superior de los más diversos países, que permitirá incrementar significativamente la movilidad internacional de nuestros estudiantes de pregrado, postgrado y académicos, así como contar con la presencia en nuestra universidad de estudiantes e investigadores extranjeros.</p> <p>(aunque se referencia como secretaria no hay información)</p>	<p>http://www.unsj.edu.ar/noticiaDetalle.php?n=1629 informe de creación y selección de autoridades.</p> <p>http://www.unsj.edu.ar/descargas/infoEcli.pdf</p> <p>Language and culture</p>	<p>spanish</p> <p>http://www.unsj.edu.ar/cooperacionNacionalInternacional.php</p> <p>updated (not clear for foreigners)</p>
Universidad de Buenos Aires 5/ 328.361	16 1 Dr 4 graduates 2 Master 7 No title 2 Teacher	1°	6	Adm PIESC I Mb Schp IM MoU	<p>La Secretaría de Relaciones Internacionales tiene como objetivos fortalecer y consolidar el proceso de Internacionalización de la Universidad de Buenos Aires a través de:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * El seguimiento de planes estratégicos para el posicionamiento de la Universidad en el plano internacional * La gestión de programas de intercambio y becas con el fin de impulsar la movilidad de estudiantes, docentes e investigadores UBA hacia el extranjero y de estudiantes internacionales a nuestra Institución. * La participación en redes y consorcios internacionales * La comunicación con Universidades extranjeras, asumiendo la responsabilidad de adoptar convenios de cooperación y de organizar actividades conjuntas * El apoyo a sus 13 Unidades Académicas en relación a temas del ámbito internacional * La difusión de información referente a las oportunidades de participación en programas de intercambio, becas, redes, y otros. 		<p>Spanish</p> <p>http://www.uba.ar/internacionales/index.php</p> <p>incomplete, nor clear and few complex + hard outdates (heavy for navigate and under construction few links)</p> <p>English short version http://www.uba.ar/ingles/index02.php</p>
Universidad Nacional de Catamarca 2/	No data	1° and 2°	3	Mb INC	<p>Misión</p> <p>Gestionar la vinculación de la universidad con</p>	<p>La Subsecretaría de Coordinación y Vinculación Institucional, tiene por finalidad</p>	<p>http://www.unca.edu.ar/coordinacion/</p>

11.927	1 Secretary 2 Directors			ICm	<p>instituciones y organizaciones de la región, del país y del exterior y desarrollar políticas activas a través de programas propios y cooperativos, que conduzcan a la vinculación e inserción académica de la universidad.</p> <p>Funciones</p> <p>I. Promover la firma de convenios de cooperación bilateral y multilateral con entidades e instituciones del medio regional, nacional e internacional.</p> <p>II. Gestionar los vínculos con instituciones del exterior, agencias de cooperación internacional y redes de universidades.</p> <p>III. Ofrecer asesoramiento a estudiantes, docentes, no docentes y graduados sobre oportunidades de formación en el exterior.</p> <p>IV. Planificar la puesta en marcha de programas de movilidad docente, no docente y estudiantil.</p> <p>V. Promover la participación de la comunidad universitaria en los programas de cooperación científico-tecnológico con otras universidades del país y del exterior.</p> <p>VI. Promover la inserción de la universidad en la provincia, la región y el exterior.</p> <p>VII. Registrar y producir informaciones estadísticas relativas a los programas de formación e intercambio que permitan efectuar un análisis de los resultados adecuados por cada uno de los programas implementados.</p> <p>VIII. Elaborar, aprobar y elevar el preproyecto de presupuesto anual de la Secretaría.</p> <p>IX. Planificar la formación de los recursos humanos del área.</p> <p>X. Asistir al Rector en todos los asuntos que este le encomiende.</p>	<p>propiciar la vinculación de la Universidad con Instituciones y Organizaciones de la región, del país y del exterior desarrollando, además, políticas activas a través de programas propios y cooperativos, que conduzcan a la vinculación e inserción académico-científica de la Universidad.</p> <p>Cooperación Nacional e Internacional Desarrolla actividades de cooperación dirigidas a la internacionalización de la Universidad.</p> <p>Gestiona vínculos con instituciones del exterior, agencias de Cooperación Internacional y redes de universidades.</p> <p>Ofrece asesoramiento a estudiantes, docentes y graduados sobre oportunidades de formación en el exterior.</p> <p>Planifica la puesta en marcha de programas de movilidad docente y estudiantil.</p> <p>Promueve la participación de la Comunidad Universitaria en los Programas de Cooperación Científico-Tecnológica.</p> <p>Consejo de Coordinación y Vinculación Institucional Su principal objetivo es facilitar el acercamiento de las oportunidades de Cooperación Internacional y de Proyectos Institucionales Universitarios a las Unidades Académicas, y a la comunidad universitaria en general, para lograr mayor agilidad y racionalidad en la gestión Institucional.</p> <p>El Consejo está coordinado por la Subsecretaría de Coordinación y Vinculación Institucional y conformado por un representante de cada Unidad Académica de la Universidad Nacional de Catamarca.</p> <p>Movilidad Académica La Universidad Nacional de Catamarca tiene, como uno de sus objetivos, insertarse en el mundo, a través de una política de intercambio</p>	<p>outdated Two pages: check print screen down 11/4/2015 http://www.unca.edu.ar/vinculacion.html just one info Authorities and internal areas Secretario de Vinculación Institucional y Relaciones Internacionales: Ing. Eduardo de la Orden Directora de Relaciones Internacionales: Lic. Lilia Exeni Directora de Cooperación Local y Regional: Lic. Claudia Vega</p>
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						<p>de estudiantes y docentes e investigadores, brindando a los visitantes extranjeros toda su oferta de grado y postgrado y posibilitando que nuestra comunidad Universitaria pueda desarrollar actividades educativas en el exterior.</p> <p>Para ello integra asociaciones y grupos de Universidades Nacionales e Internacionales, promueve la movilidad y el intercambio de docentes y estudiantes, participa en foros internacionales y propicia iniciativas de cooperación con instituciones de reconocido prestigio.</p> <p>Modalidades para el intercambio de docentes y alumnos:</p> <p>Existen dos mecanismos que posibilitan el intercambio y la movilidad de docentes y alumnos. La UNCa tiene convenios con Universidades extranjeras que posibilitan la movilidad. Por otra parte integra redes de Universidades con las cuales pueden realizarse moviidades de docentes y estudiantes.</p>	
<p>Universidad Nacional de Rio Negro: 1/ 5.987</p>	No data	4°	7	<p>MoU Ntw Schp Icm ICs Fs IEF</p>	<p>La Oficina de Relaciones Internacionales trabaja articuladamente con los ámbitos de docencia, extensión e investigación en una estrategia de internacionalización guiada por el concepto de asociatividad que consiste en responder a la sociedad del conocimiento. En este sentido el objetivo es compartir con otras universidades, entidades científicas, organismos gubernamentales e instituciones de la sociedad civil, nacionales e internacionales. Se presta especial atención a las áreas de:</p> <p>a- educación a distancia b- humanidades y estudios sociales c- producción, tecnología y medio ambiente, d- economía, administración y turismo,</p> <p>con el fin de optimizar la calidad académica y científica. Se promueve específicamente la movilidad académica de estudiantes y docentes, la co titulación,</p>		<p>Spanish http://unrn.edu.ar/sitio/index.php/relaciones-internacionales updated</p>

					la implementación de cátedras internacionales, los proyectos de investigación y desarrollo y la vinculación con redes académicas.		
Universidad Nacional de San Martín: 1/ 12.782	3 No specific data	4°	5	RRII Mb Fs Schp MoU	<p>La Gerencia de Relaciones Internacionales (GRI) trabaja en pos de la internacionalización de la UNSAM, entendida ésta como “la inclusión de una dimensión internacional, intercultural o global en los programas de estudio y en los procesos de enseñanza y de aprendizaje”. Por ello la promoción y gestión de “actividades internacionales, tales como movilidad académica para estudiantes y docentes, vinculaciones, asociaciones y proyectos internacionales; y nuevos programas académicos e iniciativas de investigación de carácter internacional” son parte de la responsabilidad del área.</p> <p>En ese marco, la misión del área es propiciar el desarrollo e implementación de políticas y programas que vinculen institucionalmente a la UNSAM con universidades y otros establecimientos educativos, centros de investigación y organismos gubernamentales y no gubernamentales, tanto en el ámbito regional como en el internacional.</p>	<p>Actividades de la Gerencia de Relaciones Internacionales</p> <p><u>Internacionalización:</u></p> <p>La GRI estimula y acompaña los distintos proyectos de internacionalización que se desarrollan en el seno de las distintas unidades académicas y áreas de la Universidad. Para ello presta asesoramiento técnico y acompañamiento en las diversas instancias de internacionalización.</p>	<p>http://www.unsam.edu.ar/internacional/rrii.asp</p>
Universidad Nacional de Lanús: 2/ 12.520	8 No specific data	3°	4	MoU/ Spsh Mb Pj Icm	<p><u>Dirección de Cooperación Internacional</u></p> <p>La Dirección de Cooperación internacional de la Universidad Nacional de Lanús tendrá como objetivos fundamentales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avanzar en el fortalecimiento institucional de la Dirección de Cooperación Internacional a través de la organización de actividades de investigación, vinculación y extensión, que mejoren la visibilidad y reconocimiento de la Universidad en el ámbito internacional. • Articular la institución en el contexto mundial de la Educación Superior. • Abrir nuevos espacios para la proyección internacional y la vinculación con redes académicas internacionales. • Ampliar las oportunidades de inserción de los alumnos y egresados a través de la difusión de becas y subsidios de índole internacional. 	<p><u>Presentación</u></p> <p>En la Universidad Nacional de Lanús entendemos que la Cooperación Internacional constituye una estrategia que ha de permitir su proyección internacional.</p> <p>Se trata de un doble proceso, por un lado dirigido al interior de la Universidad a través de su fortalecimiento institucional y por otro hacia el exterior por medio de la difusión de su oferta educativa y de investigación en un espacio supranacional. Por lo tanto, la Dirección de Cooperación Internacional de la Universidad Nacional de Lanús tiene como objetivos fundamentales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avanzar en el fortalecimiento institucional de la Dirección de Cooperación Internacional 	<p>Spanish</p> <p>http://www.unla.edu.ar/index.php/cooperacion-internacional-presentacion outdated</p>

					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difundir y promover los asuntos internacionales de cada Departamento en particular y de la Universidad en general. • Difundir y transmitir la participación de nuestra Universidad en los diferentes Programas de Cooperación Internacional 	<p>a través de la organización de actividades de investigación, vinculación y extensión, que mejoren la visibilidad y reconocimiento de la Universidad en el ámbito internacional.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Articular la institución en el contexto mundial de la Educación Superior. • Abrir nuevos espacios para la proyección internacional y la vinculación con redes académicas internacionales. • Ampliar las oportunidades de inserción de los alumnos y egresados a través de la difusión de becas y subsidios de índole internacional. • Difundir y promover los asuntos internacionales de cada Departamento en particular y de la Universidad en general. • Difundir y transmitir la participación de la Universidad en los diferentes Programas de Cooperación Internacional. 	
Universidad Nacional de Santiago del Estero: 1/ 16.199	1	3°	2	Mb MoU Schp	<p>La <i>Dirección de Relaciones Internacionales</i> desarrolla actividades en dos campos fundamentales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - la cooperación internacional, promoviendo las relaciones con organizaciones del extranjero, incentivando el desarrollo institucional y apuntalando el logro de la excelencia en lo académico, científico y tecnológico; - las relaciones internacionales, diagnosticando la gestión de las relaciones internacionales en la Universidad y contribuyendo a través de una solidaridad inteligente y responsable a que los beneficios del proceso de globalización favorezcan a mayores sectores de la sociedad. 		<p>Spanish http://www.unse.edu.ar/index.php/internacionales outdated – hard to navigate</p>
Universidad Nacional del Comahue 3/ 28.477	ND	2°	ND	ND	ND	ND	<p>http://secrri.uncoma.edu.ar/ not available (04/2015) too</p>
Universidad Nacional de Cuyo 1/	12 No data	1°	5	INC Mb	La Secretaría de Relaciones Internacionales de la Universidad Nacional de Cuyo tiene como objetivo		Spanish

31.755			5 (site structure)	Nand A HRA ICm Obs Schp Exch Inst Nand A	<p>promover los vínculos con otras provincias y países mediante programas de investigación, becas, movilidad estudiantil y docente; y proyectos de cooperación con referentes a nivel nacional e internacional. Para ello, este organismo cuenta con áreas que se encargan de promover tanto la INTERNACIONALIZACIÓN como la INTERREGIONALIZACIÓN de nuestra universidad.</p> <p>“Pensar universal, actuar local”</p> <p>MISIÓN</p> <p>Nuestra MISIÓN se funda en la generación, promoción y fortalecimiento de vínculos de cooperación entre la Universidad Nacional de Cuyo y otras universidades, instituciones u organismos del país y del exterior:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> .- Promovemos la visión internacional en la comunidad académica a través de la gestión de convenios interinstitucionales, intercambio académico, proyectos conjuntos de investigación, actividades de extensión y asociaciones estratégicas con centros especializados nacionales e internacionales en coordinación con otras unidades académicas y otras organizaciones. .- Fomentamos la cultura internacional a partir de la valoración del contexto nacional, los valores regionales y nacionales al interior de la Universidad. <p>VISIÓN</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> .- Nuestra VISIÓN apunta a que la Universidad Nacional de Cuyo participe activamente en el proceso de internacionalización e integración regional de la comunidad académica, para promocionar a sus integrantes como ciudadanos del mundo con estrategias, actitudes y valores universales. 		http://www.uncuyo.edu.ar/relacionesinternacionales/updated
Universidad Nacional de Quilmes 3/ 21.461	No data	3°	5 (site structure)	Mb Pj UALc Schp PAI	<p>Políticas de internacionalización en la UNQ</p> <p>La Universidad Nacional de Quilmes (UNQ) entiende que en tiempos de globalización, la Internacionalización de la Educación Superior es uno de los pilares fundamentales para incrementar la calidad académica, en un contexto de promoción de iniciativas de integración regional (América Latina y</p>	<p>UALc last activity</p> <p>Conferencia final Proyecto VertebralCUE</p> <p>La dinámica de la relación LAC – UE en el emergente contexto internacional 4 y 5 de junio de 2012, Instituto Italiano di Cultura, Buenos Aires.</p>	<p>Spanish</p> <p>http://www.unq.edu.ar/secciones/52-relaciones-internacionales/</p> <p>updated</p>

el Caribe) e interregional (Europa, América del Norte, y Asia Pacífico).

Las políticas de internacionalización son implementadas desde la Dirección de Relaciones Internacionales, encuadrada en la Dirección General de Relaciones Institucionales, a su vez dependiente de la Secretaría General de la Universidad.

Desde 2004, la Universidad Nacional de Quilmes relanza una política activa de internacionalización que se orienta, fundamentalmente, a tres líneas de trabajo:

- Programas de movilidad de estudiantes de grado y posgrado, de docentes e investigadores y de personal de administración y servicios;
- Programas de intercambio y cooperación académica y de investigación;
- Programas de cooperación al desarrollo.

De hecho, la UNQ ha establecido múltiples contactos bilaterales con universidades latinoamericanas, europeas, norteamericanas, y australianas; ha profundizado su participación en redes nacionales (RedCIUN) e internacionales (CINDA, Universia, CONAHEC, Orión y Ortelius, entre otras), ha impulsado tanto la movilidad estudiantil (PROMOVES, Programa de Movilidad Estudiantil del CINDA, Programa JIMA, Programa MACA, Programa de Intercambio de CONAHEC) como el intercambio de docentes e investigadores (Programa de Movilidad Docente de la SPU) y del personal de administración y servicios (PROMOPAS); y ha ganado posicionamiento con su participación en diversos programas académicos de relevancia internacional (Séptimo Programa Marco de Ciencia y Tecnología de la Unión Europea, Programa ALFA III, Programa Erasmus Mundus External Cooperation Windows).

					<p>Por otra parte, en 2009 y en el marco del Proyecto Vertebral ALCUE, se crea la Unidad ALCUE UNQ cuya finalidad es constituirse en ámbito articulador y agente de fomento de las relaciones de cooperación a nivel universitario, nacional e internacional, en el espacio ALCUE (América Latina, Caribe y Europa).</p> <p>Objetivos La Dirección de Relaciones Internacionales asume como responsabilidad central, organizar y coordinar las actividades vinculadas con las relaciones internacionales de la Universidad, y los acuerdos y convenios que se deriven de las mismas. Sus funciones principales son:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promover relaciones de intercambio y cooperación con instituciones internacionales; 2. Proponer la formalización de acuerdos y/o convenios; 3. Relevar de forma permanente las necesidades y oferta existente en materia de cooperación internacional; 4. Participar en la elaboración de proyectos y programas que requieran cooperación o asistencia externa. 		
ITBA - Instituto Tecnológico de Buenos Aires 1 No data available	XX	XX	3 (site structure)	Mb MoUF S	Every year, the number of ITBA's students, who travel to participate in exchange programmes in universities around the world, goes up. Also, every year, there are even more and more foreign students worldwide who choose ITBA as a destination to attend one term (four-month period) or one year of exchange or a dual-degree programme.	MoU = Partners Universities listed into this webpage.	English – Spanish http://www.itba.edu.ar/en/university/international just data for in-out students
Universidad Nacional del Mar del Plata 1/ 22.840	XX	http://www.mdp.edu.ar/index.php?key=10	9 (site structure)	Ntw Fs Mb GS Ct IS Act	En la presente sección usted encontrará información relativa a las Relaciones Internacionales de la Universidad Nacional de Mar del Plata. Conocerá sobre las Redes en las que se participa, los convenios vigentes, las becas y programas activos, entre muchos otros servicios e informaciones más.	El Área de Relaciones Internacionales ofrece los siguientes servicios: • Asesoramiento para tramitar cartas de intención y convenios con instituciones extranjeras. Consulte la normativa al respecto y los formatos en modelos.	Spanish http://www.mdp.edu.ar/index.php?key=5 half and half german - short version

		4° suppo sedly http:// www. mdp.e du.ar/i ndex.p hp?ke y=199		MoU NLt		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difusión y gestión de programas y becas internacionales • Difusión de reuniones científicas de carácter internacional organizadas por nuestros docentes e investigadores como así también enviar información sobre proyectos de investigación y docencia. <p><u>2° - Newsletter section</u></p> <p>Uno de los objetivos del Área Relaciones Internacionales de Vicerrectorado de la Universidad Nacional de Mar del Plata centra su interés en hacer circular información referente a becas que impacte positivamente en la comunidad científica y académica de la institución. Por ello, el Boletín Internacional del programa de becas es uno de los órganos de difusión que ofrece la posibilidad de contactar a nuestros docentes, investigadores y alumnos con universidades de todo el mundo. En este Boletín usted encontrará la oferta de becas internacionales destinadas a graduados, postgraduados y alumnos. Se comunicarán, además, periódicamente, cursos y convocatorias a premios o subsidios y la última información con respecto a reuniones científicas.</p> <p>Usted podrá acceder a esta información a través de dos links: boletín actual (que incluirá toda la oferta de becas actualizada) y boletines anteriores (donde se consignan los boletines que han sido publicados con anterioridad)</p>	
Universidad Nacional de Entre Ríos 2/ 13.615	2(shows just responsible) 2 Teachers	4°	1 (according structure and functions) 8	IRO Mb AS	La política de cooperación internacional de la UNER se entiende en estrecho vínculo con las actividades de desarrollo académico. Por tal motivo, el Área de Relaciones Internacionales depende funcionalmente de la Secretaría Académica de Rectorado y en cada	<u>Estructura y Funciones</u> El Área Relaciones Internacionales depende de la Secretaría Académica y es una unidad de gestión vinculada a las Facultades mediante	Spanish http://www.internacionales.uner.edu.ar/ updated

			(site structure)	Fs MoU Ntw (AUG M) ICs Ct	<p>Unidad Académica se designaron Representantes de una Comisión Asesora institucional en la materia.</p> <p>En tal sentido, el Área tiene como funciones:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participación y representación en Redes y Organismos Regionales e Internacionales de educación universitaria. - Vinculación entre la institución y otras instituciones a los fines de la conformación de Redes académicas y a la celebración de Convenios bilaterales y multilaterales. - Gestión de programas de movilidad académica regionales e internacionales con especial énfasis en la cooperación horizontal. - Gestión de proyectos redes interuniversitarias, de misiones al extranjero. 	una comisión Asesora en Relaciones Internacionales.	
Universidad Nacional de Jujuy 2/ 14.478	6 4 graduates 2 no titles	4°	5	MoU Ocs Ntw Nws Ct	<p>The International Relations was created to meet the internationalization demand manifested in the global academic scenario. UNJu fixed among their policies strengthening the participation of teachers, researchers, students and administrative staff in cooperation areas and exchanges with universities abroad. It also manifested an especial determination to deepen relations with Latin American academic institutions.</p> <p>Objectives</p> <p>General:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To promote the effective participation of U.N.Ju. in the processes of higher education internationalization and partnership with agencies and academic institutions abroad. <p>Specific:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To articular the university internationalization policies with the regional development strategies, establishing general and specific agreements with various universities. 		<p>Spanish- English</p> <p>https://sites.google.com/site/relacionesinternacionalesunju/home</p> <p>external-site</p>

					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To encourage the participation of the UNJu community on international networks. Actively participate in inter-university cooperation programs of teachers and researchers. • To participate in student exchange programs with academic recognition. • To promote interaction UNJu staff. with their counterparts in foreign universities, generating job enrichment interacting systems. • To encourage the involvement of local academics with foreign to encourage the establishment of transnational groups. 		
Universidad Nacional de la Patagonia “San Juan Bosco” 2/13.212	XX	4° http://www.unp.edu.ar/es/estructura.php	3 or 3	Fnc MoU Ct Nws Ocs (InfoNws)	<p>La misión principal de la Oficina de Relaciones Internacionales, dependiente del Rectorado, es promover, fortalecer y expandir los vínculos internacionales y la internacionalización académica de la Universidad</p> <p>Corresponde a su quehacer principal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Buscar y mantener, mediante Convenios, relaciones académicas selectivas y beneficiosas con centros del exterior. • Prestar asistencia a las Facultades en actividades de Intercambio y de Movilidad de estudiantes, investigadores, y personal no docente. • Asesorar, en pos de una progresiva internacionalización de los estudios, sobre sistemas acreditados de reconocimiento de Títulos o de estudios parciales de grado y postgrado realizados en nuestra Universidad. • Encontrar, para sus programas y proyectos estratégicos de desarrollo, formas de financiamiento externo ofrecidas por la 		<p>Old version: Spanish http://www.ori.unp.edu.ar/index.php?option=com_contentandview=articleandid=19andItemid=28</p> <p>New version: Spanish http://www.infoweb3.unp.edu.ar/ori/ mix of data outdated with some new data.</p>

				<p>Cooperación Internacional pública y privada del país y del extranjero.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Asistir a la comunidad universitaria en la búsqueda de información y trámites de becas para estudios fuera del país. <p>·Dar a conocer las acciones académicas, convocatorias y eventos especiales de interés internacional ofrecidas por nuestra Universidad o por otras Universidades y Organismos nacionales o extranjeros.</p>		
<p>Universidad Nacional de Rosario 3/ 74.726</p>	<p>10 + 3 + 1 1 vet 1 Dr 5 Graduates 1 Lawyer 1 Master 3 no titles 1 Technician</p>	<p>1°</p>	<p>6</p>	<p>INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS SECRETARY OFFICE Its function is to assist the Rector and General Secretariat in all matters related to the University international relations activities. Among its main functions it is to promote University relationships to foreign institutions related to scientific, education, research or cultural fields, to promote University relationships to international organisms devoted to the promotion, help, support of scientific, education, research and cultural programs and activities.</p> <p>Spanish web http://www.unr.edu.ar/noticia/368/secretaria-de-relaciones-internacionales (Publicado: 2008-08-25; Por Rosana Vasta)</p> <p>MISIÓN</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Asistir al Rector y Vicerrector en todo lo relativo a las actividades de relaciones internacionales de la Universidad. <p>FUNCIONES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Intervenir en la gestión, preparación y elaboración de convenios entre la Universidad y otras instituciones de investigaciones científicas y culturales del exterior. Intervenir elaborando y/o trasladando propuestas a la Universidad para su inclusión en los convenios que los ministerios referidos en el punto anterior confirmen 	<p>2007-2011 International Management Plan http://www.unr.edu.ar/noticia/332/plan-de-gestion-2007-2011 2011-2015 International Management Plan http://www.unr.edu.ar/noticia/5053/plan-de-gestion-2011-2015 Área de Relaciones Internacionales e Institucionales</p> <p>Misión</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promover la vinculación y comunicación permanente de la U.N.R con universidades extranjeras, organismos nacionales e internacionales y medios locales e internacionales. <p>Funciones</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Generar canales de comunicación permanentes con las Oficinas de Relaciones Internacionales de las doce Facultades. Vincular y articular acciones de difusión y promoción con medios de comunicación locales e internacionales. Intervenir, consolidar y apoyar las relaciones de la Universidad Nacional de Rosario con organismos e instituciones gubernamentales y no gubernamentales. <p>Coordinador Responsable-Tec. Rosana Vasta Asistente Técnico - Sr. Fernando Cambas</p> <p>Gestión</p>	<p>(English-Portuguese) short gral data Spanish http://www.unr.edu.ar/secretaria/116/secretaria-de-relaciones-internacionales/ Updated</p>

				<p>con sus iguales o equivalentes de otros países de la comunidad internacional.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intervenir en la preparación y elaboración de las condiciones para la aprobación de estos convenios. • Intervenir en la preparación y elaboración de propuestas para favorecer y concretar el intercambio que se derive de la firma de los convenios, actas de intención, acuerdos de cooperación entre partes. • Colaborar con las Secretarías, Facultades, etc., en las tareas que estas desarrollen en el campo de las relaciones internacionales. • Intervenir en el asesoramiento para la fijación de prioridades en el área de las Relaciones Internacionales. • Presentar anualmente para su aprobación y posterior ejecución un Programa de tareas a desarrollar durante el año. • Intervenir en la gestión, promoción y difusión de posibilidades de becas que se conozcan para beneficio de la comunidad universitaria. • Promover la vinculación de la Universidad con otras instituciones del campo científico, docente, de investigación y cultural del extranjero. • Promover la vinculación de la Universidad con organismos internacionales dedicados a la promoción, ayuda, apoyo de programas y actividades científicas, docentes, de investigación y culturales. • Promover y/o consolidar la relación de la Universidad con organismos inter universitarios internacionales. • Promover y/o consolidar la relación de la Universidad con embajadas, consulados o representaciones diplomáticas de países extranjeros existentes en el país. • Intervenir en la relación con el Ministerio de Educación y Justicia de la Nación y el Ministerio de Relaciones Exteriores y Culto de las áreas vinculadas al ejercicio de las Relaciones Internacionales 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relación y comunicación Intra-institucional • Relación y comunicación Extra-institucional <p>Área de Cooperación Científica y Tecnológica Internacional</p> <p>Misión</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identificar, difundir y gestionar oportunidades de Cooperación Científico-tecnológica entre la U.N.R y diversas instituciones del mundo científico y universitario. <p>Funciones</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contribuir en la difusión de la oferta científico-tecnológica de la U.N.R en el mundo. • Promover la participación de la U.N.R en proyectos de investigaciones conjuntas con el exterior. • Fomentar la formación de recursos humanos y apoyar el intercambio de docentes-investigadores de la UNR con centros de investigación y universidades extranjeras. • Articular acciones con la Dirección de Cooperación Internacional de la Secretaria de Ciencia y Tecnología de la Nación. <p>Coordinador Responsable > Magister Med. Vet. Roberto Figallo</p> <p>Asistente Técnica > Srta. Erica Mandón</p> <p>Gestión</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <u>Programa Fondo Semilla - UNR</u> - Cooperación Bilateral - Cooperación Multilateral - XVI Jornadas de Jóvenes Investigadores - RECyT- MERCOSUR - Cooperación Internacional con Empresas - PRODEQ <p>Actividades</p>
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					<p>- Presentación Programas y Convocatorias de Cooperación Bilateral y Programa PRODEQ del MINCYT</p> <p>Área de Cooperación Académica Internacional</p> <p><u>Misión</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apoyar y asistir la vinculación y promoción de la Universidad Nacional de Rosario con organismos internacionales y universidades extranjeras a los fines de desarrollar actividades y proyectos de cooperación internacional en el campo docente, cultural y estudiantil. <p><u>Funciones</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intervenir en la gestión, promoción y difusión de becas en el exterior. • Coordinar, programar y orientar el ingreso, la residencia y el alojamiento de funcionarios, docentes, investigadores y estudiantes extranjeros que deseen realizar sus actividades en el ámbito de la U.N.R • Gestionar, difundir y promover todos los programas de intercambio académico internacional que se deriven de la firma de convenios, actas de intención y acuerdos de cooperación entre la Universidad Nacional de Rosario e instituciones del extranjero. • Planificar y programar acciones tendientes a promover y presentar la oferta académica, científica y cultural de la Universidad Nacional de Rosario en instituciones del exterior y en la propia universidad <p>Coordinador Responsable Asistente Técnico - Sr. Javier Varela</p> <p><u>Gestión</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Becas, premios y subsidios internacionales. • Ingreso, residencia y alojamiento de extranjeros. 	
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					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Programas de cooperación e intercambios académicos. • Promoción de la Universidad Nacional de Rosario. <p>Área de Cooperación Internacional al Desarrollo</p> <p><u>Misión</u> Promover y estimular la participación de la Universidad Nacional de Rosario en programas, proyectos y actividades de Cooperación Internacional al Desarrollo.</p> <p><u>Funciones</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacitar y sensibilizar en la temática de Cooperación Internacional el Desarrollo, asumiendo a la Universidad Nacional de Rosario como Unidad de Vinculación y transferencia Tecnológica. • Vincular a la Universidad Nacional de Rosario con agencias y organismos Nacionales e Internacionales que promuevan y gestionen proyectos de Cooperación Internacional al Desarrollo. • Difundir las oportunidades y los alcances de la Cooperación Descentralizada en el circuito de la cooperación internacional. <p><u>Gestión</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensibilización y capacitación en formulación, ejecución y evaluación de proyectos de Cooperación Internacional. • Agencias, Instituciones y Organismos Internacionales de Cooperación Internacional. • Cooperación horizontal descentralizada. <p>Coordinadora Responsable - Lic. Olga Saavedra</p> <p>Unidad de Gestión y Seguimiento de Convenios Internacionales</p> <p><u>Misión</u></p>	
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					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Asistir y asesorar en la gestión y firmas de convenios internacionales entre la Universidad Nacional de Rosario y otras instituciones de científicas, académicas y culturales del exterior. <p style="text-align: center;"><u>Funciones</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difundir y comunicar a toda la comunidad universitaria la nómina actualizada de todos los Convenios Internacionales entre la U.N.R. y las instituciones extranjeras. • Intervenir en la preparación y elaboración de las condiciones institucionales para la aprobación de estos convenios. • Capacitar en la gestión y firmas de acuerdos internacionales. <p>Coordinador Responsable - Abog. María Flavia Gentiletti</p> <p>Asistencia Técnica - Abog. María Victoria Gentiletti</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><u>Gestión</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gestión y Seguimiento de Convenios Internacionales. • <u>Socialización, difusión y promoción de Convenios Internacionales.</u> • Capacitación en gestión y firmas de acuerdos internacionales. <p>Cátedras, Centros y Asociaciones Internacionales</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><u>Misión</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordinar, promover y consensuar acciones conjuntas a los fines de potenciar las políticas de Relaciones Internacionales de la Universidad Nacional de Rosario. <p style="text-align: center;"><u>Funciones</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordinar y consensuar acciones conjuntas. • Ampliar la difusión de proyectos y actividades propias de los Centros y Asociaciones. 	
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						<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fortalecer la presencia de los mismos en ámbitos locales, nacionales e internacionales. - AUGM (Asociación de Universidades Grupo Montevideo) - Cátedra Internacional Andrés Bello - CERIR (Centro de Estudios en Relaciones Internacionales de Rosario) - Observatorio del Sur (Primera Cátedra FODEPAL) <p>(Publicado: 2008-08-13 Por Rosana Vasta) http://www.unr.edu.ar/noticia/480/areas-de-la-secretaria-de-relaciones-internacionales</p>	
Universidad Nacional de San Luis 4/ 13.102	5 1 Teacher 3 perhaps no title Administrative (Hired) 1 “exchange internship”	1°	5	MoU CpT (Ntw+ Ocs) Ocs Spsh Ct	<p>The Secretariat of Institutional Relations is responsible for the Professor Liliana Mollo, Professor of the Faculty of Humanities of the National University of San Luis.</p> <p>The Secretariat has as purpose to advise the Rector in the area of competence and generate relationships with the other Secretariats of the Chancellor, to channel activities related to interagency cooperation both locally, nationally and internationally, aimed at full development of UNSL late, contributing to its insertion and local, regional, national and international positioning.</p> <p>Its mission is to foster inter-linking UNSL at local, national and international environment, developing policies for their full inclusion in these contexts, through science, undergraduate, graduate, research and extension programs and associative cooperative projects, academics and to promote scientific and technological development and university social responsibility.</p> <p>It also raises the mission of spreading the possibilities of international cooperation; calls for promotion of cooperative projects; advice for submission to, management agreements different scopes; Impetus for active participation in networks and cooperation agencies; participation in the Network of International</p>	<p>Review of the Secretariat of Institutional Relations Summary of SRI</p> <p>International Relations area exists in the UNSL as specific unit since 1990 with the creation of the Secretariat for Institutional Relations, in charge usually in different Procedures Governing the Rector and staff with little or no dependent thereon.</p> <p>Until 2007 had only one affected person as an administrative task and did not have a specific budget. A Since September 2007, when a new governance of UNSL, he starts Secretary of Inter by the Vice Chancellor Relations, he designed a strategy of internationalization of UNSL order to enhance and strengthen the existing ties, -and beyond the actions that are still generated in Colleges and academic groups within the University-, which is to promote active institutional cooperation policy, in order to properly install the UNSL in the context of internationalization Higher Education.</p> <p>In 2008, by the Superior Council Ordinance 28/08 UNSL the structure was redefined, and</p>	Spanish, English, Portuguese, French by google translate http://www.unsl.edu.ar/index.php/menu/secretaria/sec_interinstitucionales

				<p>Cooperation of National Universities RedCIUN, organizing events and activities to support participation in cooperative projects, and any other activity related to the competition area.</p>	<p>within the same area to the rank of Secretary of Institutional Relations rose.</p> <p>The SRI the following objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Significantly increase the participation of UNSL networks, programs and cooperative projects. · To facilitate the dissemination of calls for grants, projects, programs and activities of international cooperation. · Manage and support programs for student and faculty mobility. · Strengthen cooperation activities under reciprocal agreements. Progress in the implementation of the Programme of Spanish as a Foreign Language. · Generate a relevant framework and updated on the activities of international cooperation UNSL, particularly on student mobility. <p>This framework has significantly increased institutional participation UNSL Programs and International Cooperation Projects such as framed in the Erasmus Mundus program of the European Union; in Latin American Programs like JIMA (Youth Exchange Mexico-Argentina), MAGMA (Exchange between Mexican and Argentine Universities level teachers and managers); MACA (Exchanges with Colombian Universities), among others (...)</p> <p>Permanently carried out the development and management of projects related to institutional relations of UNSL, under the Calls Promotion Program University of Argentina by the SRI, which has enabled teachers UNSL participate in growing form of the various calls of the program, referred to the Foreign Missions, or Consolidation Generation Networks Cooperation, together with the two Institutional Programs earned by the SRI, led to improvement in this area.</p>	
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						<p>Actively, the Secretariat has participated in networking and cooperation agencies, especially in the Ciun Network (Network of International Cooperation of National Universities).</p> <p>Internally, to promote the participation of UNSL in Cooperation Programs from the SRI, have organized numerous conferences, forums, workshops, etc., on internationalization of higher education and inter-agency cooperation, which in turn has seen reflected in the publication of two books on the subject. Were generated proposals to update a document specific regulations and in coordination with the Academic Secretary, Policy Curriculum Internationalization in UNSL.</p> <p>Also works in UNSL, reporting of SRI, a Program of Spanish for foreigners that aims to institutionalize a newly developed discipline as it is teaching, testing and certification of Spanish as a second language and foreign language (ELSE) area.</p>	
<p>Universidad Nacional de Tucumán 2/ 61.632</p>	<p>7 1 Teacher 2 Dr 2 translators 1 graduate 1 Esc?</p>	<p>3°</p>	<p>5</p> <p>Or 9</p>	<p>Intl Mb x2 SpUp Lks</p> <p>Or Down</p> <p>MoU BDs Mb x2 SpUp CARI Fcs Ct Srvs</p>	<p>Dirección General de Relaciones Internacionales http://www.unt.edu.ar/Anexos/RRII.php La Dirección General de Relaciones Internacionales de la Universidad Nacional de Tucumán es un organismo técnico dependiente de la Secretaría Académica del Rectorado. Está integrada por un equipo interdisciplinar, que tiene el objetivo de brindar servicios a la comunidad universitaria y al público en general. Por sus funciones, constituye el ámbito de referencia en lo que a estudiantes y docentes extranjeros se trata. La Dirección fue creada el 1 de junio de 1990, por la resolución N° 311-990. En 2004 se estableció la estructura funcional, la misión y nuevas funciones.</p> <p>MISIÓN de la DGRI:</p>	<p>Principales Funciones de la DGRI:</p> <p>1°) Desarrollar líneas de proyectos interdisciplinarios impulsados por las áreas de gobierno de la Universidad. 2°) Organizar y actualizar el Registro de convenios con organismos internacionales. 3°) Gestionar los programas de becas y la implementación de los convenios internacionales de los que participe la UNT y que no tengan un organismo de implementación previamente establecido. 4°) Coordinar con otras áreas del Rectorado y con las Facultades la recepción de funcionarios, docentes o investigadores provenientes de organismos internacionales que deseen visitar la UNT.</p>	<p>Spanish English, French, Portuguese doesn't work http://www.internacionales.unt.edu.ar/</p> <p>Only in English Different employees http://www.internacionales.unt.edu.ar/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=154:ingles-integrantes-de-la-dgri&catid=86</p>

				<p>La Dirección de Relaciones Internacionales de la UNT es un organismo técnico dependiente del Rectorado cuya misión principal es implementar las políticas de relaciones internacionales que definan las autoridades superiores de la Universidad.</p>	<p>5º) Coordinar las visitas de los funcionarios provenientes de Cancillería Argentina o de las Embajadas Extranjeras en el país. 6º) Organizar y actualizar el Centro de Documentación sobre Cooperación Internacional. 7º) Intervenir como órgano asesor del Rector en todo trámite de suscripción de convenios internacionales. 8º) Organizar agendas de viajes de funcionarios del Rectorado o Facultades. 9º) Asesorar a las autoridades de la UNT sobre programas y políticas institucionales de carácter internacional. 10º) Organizar eventos internacionales. 11º) Realizar informes y recabar la información sobre cooperación internacional que resulte relevante para la comunidad universitaria. 12º) Desarrollar los mecanismos permanentes de relación con las áreas específicas del Ministerio de Relaciones Exteriores, Comercio Internacional y Culto, las embajadas acreditadas en el país, organismos internacionales, universidades e instituciones académicas y de investigación con asiento en el extranjero. 13º) Organizar, promover y apoyar el área de Becas al exterior. 14º) Impulsar el desarrollo de programas permanentes con organismos internacionales para promover el intercambio de docentes, investigadores y alumnos. 15º) Proyectar un programa específico de cooperación universitaria latinoamericano. 16º) Generar mecanismos de fluida comunicación con órganos de gobierno y facultades de la UNT, tendientes a lograr su intensa participación en proyectos y programas internacionales.</p>	
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						17°) Desarrollar acciones que tengan por objeto lograr una más estrecha inserción internacional de la Universidad Nacional de Tucumán.	
Universidad Tecnológica Nacional 2/ 83.090	XX	1°	XX	XX	La Secretaría de Relaciones Internacionales busca potenciar las relaciones académicas, científicas y humanas a través del intercambio y la comunicación con Universidades, Instituciones y Empresas extranjeras, promoviendo la inserción de los alumnos, investigadores y demás miembros de la Universidad Tecnológica Nacional en proyectos especiales de investigación, desarrollo y planeamiento, alentándolos a que se capaciten y especialicen en sus respectivas disciplinas. Nuestra misión principal es brindar información actualizada de convocatorias de becas y de cooperación internacionales, e invitarlos a que juntos trabajemos para lograr más y mejores oportunidades de crecer académica y profesionalmente. The only data available about it. http://www.utn.edu.ar/secretarias/institucional/default.utn	UTN tiene carácter federal, por abarcar todas las regiones de la Argentina. Sus 29 Facultades Regionales se ubican en la región Noreste Provincias de Chaco, Entre Ríos, Santa Fe - Noroeste - Provincias de La Rioja, Tucumán - Centro - Capital Federal y Provincias de Buenos Aires, Córdoba, Mendoza - y Sur - Provincias de Chubut, Neuquén, Santa Cruz y Tierra del Fuego .	Spanish No data http://www.utn.edu.ar/secretarias/institucional/default.utn
Universidad Nacional de Salta 3/ 25.783	4 +2 interns 1 Dr 1 Graduate 3 no title 1 C.U. (?)	1°	5 Site structure	Rs TC = (MoU) TD Pj Fs	En el mes de Abril de 1991, la actividad de la Secretaría se inicia formalmente a partir de la designación del Secretario, y en el mes de Agosto de 1992, se aprueba su estructura organizacional, creándose definitivamente la Secretaría de Cooperación Técnica, dependiente de Rectorado, y dotándosele de una Dirección y tres Departamentos. A partir del año 2010, a través de la Resolución del Consejo Superior N° 245/10 se incluyen actividades de cooperación técnica internacional, abarcando convenios y movilidades.	La Secretaría de Cooperación Técnica y Relaciones Internacionales tiene las siguientes funciones: 1) Oficiar de centro de información interna y externa en materia de prestación de servicios. 2) Reunir y mantener actualizado un registro de actividades universitarias, susceptibles de ser ofrecido y divulgado en el sector productivo. 3) Mantener un conocimiento actualizado sobre las actividades económicas de la región e identificar usuarios potenciales. 4) Recibir demandas del sector productivo y traspasarlas a las Unidades Académicas, motivando su ejecución. 5) Asesorar y apoyar a la unidades académicas y a sus docentes e investigadores en relación a la prestación de servicios.	Spanish Half/Half http://www.unsa.edu.ar/coopetecnica/

					<p>6) Proyectar los modelos de contratos a utilizar.</p> <p>7) Actuar como Secretario Ejecutivo del Comité de Asistencia Técnica.</p> <p>8) Coordinar las acciones de cooperación internacional de la Universidad con el fin de facilitar su ejecución y evaluación periódica.</p> <p>9) Apoyar las iniciativas que surjan desde el seno de la comunidad universitaria, colaborando en la gestión y llevando un registro de los mismos.</p> <p>10) Desarrollar los planes demandados por las autoridades de la Universidad.</p> <p>11) Hacer cumplir las políticas que dicte el Consejo Superior y toda norma que se establezca en materia de cooperación internacional.</p> <p>12) Entender en la gestión de los convenios y facilitar su ejecución.</p> <p>13) Asistir al Rectorado en todo cuanto se demande para la mayor efectividad en el aprovechamiento de las oportunidades.</p> <p>14) Mantener un registro actualizado para la: a) cooperación internacional en cuanto al intercambio académico y b) obtención de fondos (apoyo económico, becas, ect.) a través de la vinculación con organismos provinciales, nacionales e internacionales.</p> <p>15) Incentivar la concreción de convenios y el seguimiento de la ejecución de las actividades que se desprenden de los mismos.</p> <p>16) Toda otra tarea encomendada por las autoridades.</p>	
<p>Universidad Nacional del Centro de la Provincia de Buenos Aires 3/13.130</p>	XX	4°	6	<p>Fs Ocs UiW Mb MoU Nws</p>	<p><u>Secretaría de Relaciones Institucionales</u></p> <p>En un mundo inmerso en una realidad cada vez más compleja, fruto del constante proceso de globalización que abarca aspectos como el de la economía, la política y la cultura, resulta innegable la importancia del “conocimiento” como instrumento estratégico</p>	<p>Spanish http://www.unicen.edu.ar/rrii updated English short presentation</p>

esencial, para una adecuada inserción de las sociedades que procuran el desarrollo en dicho escenario.

En función de ello, nuestra Casa de Altos Estudios pretende afianzar y consolidar los vínculos existentes con Universidades Extranjeras, a la vez que, dar inicio a otros nuevos, como herramienta clave para la generación y el crecimiento exponencial de las actividades de intercambio, movilidad (de alumnos, egresados y docentes) y cooperación interuniversitaria, funcionales al desarrollo y fortalecimiento de la investigación científico-tecnológica, la formación de recursos humanos y su transferencia en el medio, la especialización docente, el enriquecimiento de la formación de grado y postgrado, y la promoción de su oferta académica.

En efecto, desde su actual Proyecto en marcha de consolidación de esta política institucional, trabaja desde su Área de Relaciones Internacionales, participando activamente y de manera conjunta con Instituciones Internacionales, y con los Organismos Gubernamentales en la actual política pública nacional de internacionalización de las Universidades Argentinas. A manera de ejemplo, se puede citar su participación activa como miembro pleno de la Red de Cooperación Internacional de las Universidades Nacionales del Consejo Interuniversitario Nacional (Red -CIUN), y sus vinculaciones con el Programa de Promoción de la Universidad Argentina (PPUA) de la Secretaría de Políticas Universitarias; con la Dirección de Relaciones Internacionales de la Secretaría de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación Productiva de la Nación; con la Dirección Nacional de Cooperación Internacional del Ministerio de Educación, Ciencia y Tecnología; y con la Dirección de Cooperación Internacional del Ministerio de Relaciones Exteriores; entre otras.

En el plano de la vinculación internacional, mantiene lazos de cooperación bilateral y multilateral a través de numerosos convenios con Universidades extranjeras

<http://www.unicen.edu.ar/english/international-unicen>
 Spanish – wiki
 Old version online
<http://www.rec.unicen.edu.ar/wiki/rrii>

					(americanas y europeas) y otros Institutos de Educación; Centros de desarrollo e Investigación, Fundaciones, Organismos Gubernamentales, Organizaciones, etc. Asimismo, es miembro pleno entre otros organismos e instituciones de: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fundación para el Intercambio Educativo Chino- Argentino (FIECA) • Fundación Iberoamericana de Seguridad y Salud Ocupacional (FISSO) 		
Universidad Nacional de Gral. Sarmiento 1/ 7.042	XX	0 Doesn't exist according the site	XX	XX	XX	XX	Searched http://www.ungs.edu.ar/ms_ungs/?s=internacionalesandms=cfd208495d565ef66e7dff9f98764da
Universidad Nacional de la Pampa 1/ 9.227	XX	0	1?	Nws	XX	From Newsletter: La información que compartimos es elaborada por el Departamento de Cooperación Internacional - Secretaría de Consejo Superior y Relaciones Institucionales la Universidad Nacional La Pampa.	Spanish Hard to navigate, unclear, data all together http://www.unlpam.edu.ar/info/ver_pagina.php?qs=BHRSZ1NhUm9eaAMxAScANAN2UW8ENFI7
Universidad Nacional Arturo Jauretche	2	3	5	?? Mb Ntw CpT Ocs	La política de Relaciones Internacionales de la UNAJ se concibe como un instrumento para la mejora de la calidad de la enseñanza y la investigación. En particular, esta estrategia busca contribuir a la gestión de la UNAJ en el establecimiento y desarrollo de equipos de académicos e investigadores de elevada calificación y compromiso, al involucramiento de la comunidad local y su mejoramiento social, económico, ambiental y cultural y al posicionamiento institucional, académico, científico y social de la Universidad, tanto a nivel nacional, regional como global.	La UNAJ ha desarrollado un Plan de Internacionalización que consta de tres programas complementarios: I. Programa de Vinculación Institucional Enfocado en la promoción de los vínculos institucionales de la UNAJ, tanto con instituciones de educación superior a nivel internacional como con organismos públicos internacionales, regionales, nacionales y locales y organizaciones de la sociedad civil. II. Programa de Gestión de la Internacionalización	Spanish updated July-2015 https://www.unaj.edu.ar/index.php/institucional/relaciones-internacionales

					<p>Para ello, en el año 2011 se ha constituido en el Rectorado de la Universidad la Dirección de Relaciones Internacionales, desarrollando un Plan Estratégico de Internacionalización, orientado a la demanda específica de las distintas áreas de la universidad.</p>	<p>Se dirige a la realización de las acciones que construyan y potencien las capacidades de los diferentes actores de la UNAJ, tanto gestores como académicos y estudiantes, para desarrollar de manera articulada iniciativas de internacionalización que contribuyan al fortalecimiento de la Universidad.</p> <p>III. Programa de Cooperación al Desarrollo Tiene como objetivo generar la participación activa de la UNAJ en iniciativas de políticas públicas, tanto locales, provinciales, nacionales y regionales que contribuyan a la consecución de los Objetivos de Desarrollo del Milenio.</p> <p>Las prioridades de las relaciones internacionales de la UNAJ se enfocan en acompañar el proceso de integración regional a nivel UNASUR, así como en desarrollar acciones estratégicas con potencias emergentes a nivel global, en particular con China.</p> <p>En este marco, en los años de implementación del Plan Estratégico de Internacionalización la UNAJ han desarrollado más de treinta redes de investigación e intercambio, se ha posibilitado la movilidad internacional de docentes, investigadores y alumnos y la realización de proyectos con organismos de cooperación al desarrollo.</p> <p>De esta forma se encuentran en desarrollo actividades conjuntas con instituciones de diversos países (Brasil, Uruguay, Paraguay, Bolivia, Colombia, Venezuela, México, China, Rusia) en áreas tales como políticas sociales, migraciones, salud pública, estudios del trabajo y gestión ambiental.</p>	
Universidad Nacional de Avellaneda	ND	4	7	CpT ICs - Hgl - IV	Desde la UNDAV entendemos la cooperación internacional y la internacionalización de la educación como herramientas relevantes, sobre todo para una época caracterizada por un contexto internacional		spanish updated July 2015

				<p>- PMM b</p> <p>- LApS mb</p> <p>- PPI Mb</p>	<p>globalizado y en constante cambio, que posibilitan elevar la calidad educativa mediante la complementariedad.</p> <p>Dado que la cooperación internacional es un medio para la vinculación e internacionalización de la institución, nos enmarcamos en un modelo activo, integral y transversal de implementación extensiva y equitativa, basado en un doble proceso: hacia el interior, mediante el fortalecimiento institucional y hacia el exterior permitiéndonos posicionarnos internacionalmente, generando vínculos perdurables con instituciones de diversos tipos (educativas, gubernamentales, no gubernamentales, etc.) como así también promoviendo nuestra oferta educativa.</p> <p>Para el logro de tales propósitos, el Área de Cooperación Internacional define como objetivos:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Difundir programas de cooperación internacional. ▪ Propiciar la movilidad de profesores, investigadores y estudiantes. ▪ Participar y crear redes de carácter subnacional, nacional, regional e internacional. ▪ Difundir las oportunidades de formación en el exterior mediante becas, la implementación de oferta educativa internacional, la internacionalización del currículum vitae, las investigaciones conjuntas, los convenios interinstitucionales, la enseñanza multicultural, los programas de cooperación para el desarrollo. 		http://undav.edu.ar/index.php?idcateg=83
Universidad Nacional de Chilecito	1	4	4	<p>CpT</p> <p>RRII</p> <p>Mb</p> <p>Ocs/S</p> <p>chp</p> <p>all are</p> <p>"open</p>	<p>Sus funciones comprenden gestionar la participación activa de la UNDeC en el proceso de internacionalización de la Educación Superior, estableciendo vínculos con la comunidad universitaria internacional, proponiendo la firma de convenios y acuerdos de trabajos conjuntos con Universidades extranjeras, integrando y promoviendo la integración</p>	<p>INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION</p> <p>INDeC duties include managing the active participation of the UNDeC in the internationalization of higher education, establishing links with the international academic community, proposing the signing of agreements and joint work with foreign</p>	<p>spanish</p> <p>updated</p> <p>July 2015</p> <p>http://www.undec.edu.ar/browseAres.php?area=30</p> <p>English</p>

				calls and news"	de redes universitarias internacionales, y organizando y estimulando la movilidad estudiantil, de docentes/investigadores, de personal de gestión y administrativos.	universities, integrating and promoting the integration of international university networks, and organizing and encouraging student mobility, teacher / researchers, personnel and administrative management. Dr. Gonzalo Salerno gسالerno@undec.edu.ar (outdated)	just general data/outdated not the Intz info http://www.undec.edu.ar/browseAres.php?area=30#
Universidad Nacional de Formosa	ND	3	0	0	ND	The web page contains few calls just one e-mail and land phone to contact.	Spanish outdated July 2015 http://www.unf.edu.ar/direccion-de-relaciones-internacionales/
Universidad Nacional de Hurlingham Ley 27.016 Sancionada el 19/11/2014 Promulgada el 02/12/2014	new HEI	new HEI	new HEI	new HEI	new HEI	new HEI	under construction http://www.unahuru.ar
Universidad Nacional de José Clemente Paz	ND	3* (institutional relations)	3	Mb Ntw CandP	Esta dirección tiene como objetivo principal gestionar y coordinar espacios de representación y vinculación entre la Universidad Nacional de José C. Paz (UNPAZ) y diversos actores nacionales e internacionales, a través de la promoción tanto de iniciativas de integración regional e internacional como de proyectos de cooperación con instituciones de educación superior, redes académico- científicas y organismos regionales, bilaterales y multilaterales. Asimismo, tiene la función de desarrollar convenios derivados de dichos acuerdos y contribuir al fortalecimiento Institucional. Las líneas en que se orienta la internacionalización de la educación superior son especialmente: - Programas de movilidad de estudiantes de grado y posgrado, de docentes e investigadores y de personal de administración y servicios; - Proyectos de intercambio y cooperación académica y de investigación; - Proyectos de cooperación al desarrollo.	Área de movilidad internacional Tiene como finalidad desarrollar y vincular actividades académicas y de gestión con alumnos, docentes e investigadores y personal de gestión administración y servicios para la articulación de la movilidad en educación superior. Área de redes interinstitucionales Tiene como finalidad impulsar la inserción y cooperación de la UNPAZ en las redes interministeriales e interuniversitarias. Articular acuerdos, convenios y gestionar una actividad asociativa para alcanzar objetivos compartidos de beneficios mutuos a nivel de las instituciones involucradas. Área ceremonial y protocolo Tiene como finalidad proporcionar a la Universidad Nacional de José C. Paz una estructura de normas y procedimientos que acompañen las ceremonias y eventos en los que intervengan las autoridades de la	Spanish updated July 2015 http://www.unpaz.edu.ar/relaciones_institucionales

					- Proyectos de redes interinstitucionales e internacionales.	Universidad, enmarcando las relaciones académicas e institucionales en un ámbito cortés y armónico. Asimismo, brinda acompañamiento y asesoramiento como área encargada de la organización de eventos institucionales.	
Universidad Nacional de la Matanza	ND	*Institute (5°?)	6	Exch MoU OEA m Schp -Ext Op (new) -Ac Cpt (new)	<p>La Universidad cuenta con diferentes Institutos para el desarrollo de convenios vinculados con la posibilidad de entablar nuevas relaciones con entidades nacionales e internacionales en materia de educación, o para difundir el trabajo que se realiza en el ámbito académico. Estos espacios se encuentran destinados a generar vínculos hacia fuera de la Universidad, con el objetivo de crecer como institución a partir de la difusión de las actividades. Además, se pretende dar a conocer, en otros ámbitos, la misión rectora de esta Casa de Altos Estudios.</p> <p>http://www.unlam.edu.ar/index.php?seccion=2andidArticulo=14</p> <p>La Universidad ha impulsado un proceso de internacionalización con el que busca mejorar, de manera constante, la calidad académica a través de convenios firmados con universidades del exterior. El intercambio académico y estudiantil es una de las formas que se ha propuesto para lograr dicho objetivo que, además, obliga a la actualización permanente tanto de los docentes como de las propuestas educativas.</p> <p>Otra forma de articulación con creciente respuesta de las organizaciones productivas es la demanda de proyectos de base tecnológica y el asesoramiento técnico de nuestros profesionales a las empresas y entidades públicas inmersas en el proceso de reconversión económica, social, cultural y productiva.</p> <p>Instituto de Cooperación Internacional</p> <p>El Instituto de Cooperación Internacional (ICI) tiene como objetivo promover el intercambio académico y estudiantil entre distintas universidades del mundo, a través de la suscripción de convenios con</p>	<p>El Instituto de Cooperación Internacional (ICI) tiene como objetivo promover intercambios y vinculaciones académicas con universidades e instituciones científicas de todo el mundo. Su rol se vincula directamente a la importancia actual de la internacionalización en la educación superior y la actividad de investigación en todo el mundo.</p> <p>El Instituto ha cobrado creciente impulso a partir de la firma de convenios de intercambio y cooperación académica con universidades y centros de estudio de las más diversas regiones. Su labor intenta contribuir a la mayor diversidad cultural e integración de visiones posible en la actividad cotidiana de la Universidad y en la formación de sus estudiantes. Naturalmente, esa labor se enmarca en la regla fundamental de excelencia académica que orienta la actividad toda de la Universidad Nacional de La Matanza.</p> <p>La internacionalización, como ha señalado el Rector de la Universidad Nacional de La Matanza, Lic. Prof. Daniel Martínez, es una herramienta fundamental e insustituible para la mejora constante de la calidad educativa, la cual nos obliga a permanecer actualizados y elevar nuestros niveles de exigencia día a día.</p>	<p>spanish outdated, without information and contents</p> <p>http://internacional.unlam.edu.ar/</p>

					universidades extranjeras, teniendo en cuenta la importancia de la internacionalización de las universidades y la creciente globalización educativa y tecnológica.		
Universidad Nacional de la Patagonia Austral	2 in page 3 http://www.unpa.edu.ar/sites/default/files/editor/pdf/OCS20070087A2.pdf	4	3	-Mb+ MoU(new) CpT+ MoU update d	Desde el área de Cooperación Académica se trabaja para impulsar políticas de internacionalización para incorporar una dimensión internacional en las funciones de docencia, investigación y extensión. La responsabilidad de fomentar el desarrollo de actividades académicas de cooperación e internacionalización entre nuestra casa de estudios y otras organizaciones educativas, científicas y culturales del país y del extranjero es objetivo primordial. Entre estas actividades se encuentran la movilidad académica de estudiantes, profesores, investigadores y personal administrativo; el desarrollo de proyectos de investigación en colaboración; la creación o consolidación de redes; el desarrollo de programas educativos conjuntos; el aprendizaje de idiomas extranjeros, entre otras. Dado el contexto geográfico en el que la Institución está inmersa, algunas de las áreas en las cuales se hace hincapié son: Educación a Distancia, Recursos Naturales no Renovables, Minería y Turismo, entre muchas otras. Dentro de la UNPA no existen aún cursos o asignaturas destinadas a estudiantes extranjeros, así como tampoco carreras de idiomas.	From the area of Academic Cooperation it works to promote internationalization policies to incorporate an international dimension to the functions of teaching, research and extension. The responsibility to foster the development of academic cooperation and internationalization activities between our university and other educational organizations, scientific and cultural the country and abroad is paramount goal. These activities include academic mobility of students, teachers, researchers and administrative staff; the development of collaborative research projects; the creation or consolidation of networks; the development of joint educational programs; . learning foreign languages, among others Given the geographical context in which the institution is involved, some of the areas where emphasis are: Distance Education Non-Renewable Natural Resources, Mining and Tourism, among others. within the UNPA are not yet Courses aimed at foreign students, nor racing languages.	Spanish English Portuguese outdated http://www.unpa.edu.ar/contenido/cooperacion-academica
Universidad Nacional de la Rioja	ND	2	4	Mb Aw(new) Mng MoU	La Universidad Nacional de La Rioja se encuentra en proceso de reinserción internacional. Por ello, la Subsecretaría de Relaciones Internacionales trabaja para ser un puente entre nuestros saberes y la comunidad académica mundial. Promueve la movilidad de formadores con el objetivo de lograr la excelencia académica. Da a conocer nuestra Casa de Altos Estudios como sede de formación de grado y posgrado, incentivando la recepción de docentes y estudiantes extranjeros e impulsando el egreso de nuestros estudiantes hacia	each subtype contents wrong information e.g. inside MoU there are data about the degrees and studies one can do the other option inside Agreements it take one to certificates for students hard to navigate	spanish outdated, http://www.unlar.edu.ar/subsecretaria-de-relaciones-internacionales/

					nuevas culturas que enriquezcan su formación profesional.		
Universidad Nacional de las Artes	ND	4	2	CpT Int St	<p>En el marco de la creciente internacionalización de la educación superior, el Instituto Universitario Nacional del Arte lleva a cabo una política de apertura y colaboración con numerosas instituciones universitarias de la región y del mundo. El Área de Relaciones Internacionales, dependiente de la Secretaría de Desarrollo y Vinculación Institucional, es la instancia del IUNA que promueve la internacionalización entre los miembros de la comunidad universitaria. Además, es el enlace institucional para realizar actividades académicas con organismos de cooperación e instituciones de educación superior nacionales e internacionales. El principal objetivo del Área es el de administrar, coordinar y seguir el conjunto de actividades internacionales de la universidad. Con el fin de promover la diversidad cultural, la interacción con actores sociales, con las expresiones artísticas contemporáneas y la realidad propia de cada país, la política de internacionalización tiene como ejes centrales el desarrollo de los intercambios de estudiantes, de profesores, de investigadores y de artistas, así como la gestión de las redes de cooperación entre universidades. Para el cumplimiento de nuestros objetivos, el Área de Relaciones Internacionales cuenta con:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cooperación Internacional • Estudiantes internacionales 	<p><u>Cooperación Internacional</u></p> <p><u>Convenios internacionales</u> El IUNA ha firmado distintos convenios marco de cooperación con universidades e instituciones extranjeras. Un convenio marco de cooperación es un acuerdo de carácter oficial que establece el intercambio científico, académico y cultural, la cooperación y la colaboración recíproca del IUNA con la institución conveniente.</p> <p>Modelo de convenio marco</p> <p>Para más información sobre convenios: rectorado.internacionales@una.edu.ar</p> <p><u>Redes internacionales</u> A fin de asegurarse un lugar preponderante en el campo internacional, el IUNA es miembro activo de la REDCIUN. Dicha participación, promueve el desarrollo y la transferencia de los saberes así como también la creación y participación en distintos proyectos y programas.</p> <p><u>REDCIUN</u> La Red de Cooperación Internacional de las Universidades Nacionales ha sido creada en el ámbito del Consejo Interuniversitario Nacional (CIN), mediante Acuerdo Plenario N° 326 del año 1999, a raíz de la propuesta de constituir una red de cooperación internacional de las universidades nacionales surgida del Encuentro de Responsables de Relaciones Internacionales de Universidades Nacionales, realizado en la ciudad de Santa Fe, los días 14 y 20 de abril del año 1999.</p>	<p>spanish updated</p> <p>http://una.edu.ar/contenidos/874-area-de-relaciones-internacionales</p>

					<p><u>Programa JIMA (Jóvenes Intercambio México-Argentina)</u></p> <p>Este Programa surge de la base del Convenio de Colaboración Académica, Científica y Cultural, celebrado entre la Asociación Nacional de Universidades e Instituciones de Educación Superior (ANUIES) de la República de México y el Consejo Interuniversitario Nacional (CIN) de la República Argentina. El mismo dio lugar a la firma de un Acuerdo Específico de Cooperación para el Intercambio de Estudiantes de Grado, como forma de contrastar la experiencia propia y de adquirir una visión más rica y universalista de la realidad, y lograr así una mayor integración entre México y Argentina.</p> <p>El IUNA participa en el Programa JIMA desde el año 2011. Desde entonces y hasta el año 2013, 12 estudiantes del IUNA han participado de este intercambio, enriqueciendo su experiencia y formación en universidades mexicanas.</p> <p>La convocatoria al Programa JIMA se realiza cada cuatrimestre, mediante una difusión en las Unidades Académicas y en el Rectorado del IUNA, y está destinada a los estudiantes de las carreras de grado que hayan aprobado el 40% de las asignaturas de su carrera.</p> <p>En este sentido, el IUNA otorga a sus estudiantes seleccionados para viajar a México una ayuda económica, a la vez que la universidad mexicana de destino brinda una beca para contribuir con el alojamiento y la manutención del estudiante durante el semestre de estadía en ese país.</p>	
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Universidad Nacional de Lomas de Zamora	ND	0	0	0	--		doesn't exist Intz space
Universidad Nacional de Luján	4 1Dr 1 Technician 2 no degree	2	(spanish site) 10 + language	Nws Mb A Prof- Mb B stud- MoU AS Fs Lks NLt Ct	image below http://www.coopint.unlu.edu.ar/?q=node/11	English site http://www.coopinting.unlu.edu.ar/?q=node/7 French site http://www.coopintfr.unlu.edu.ar/ Portuguese site http://www.coopintbr.unlu.edu.ar/	spanish English French Portuguese each language has different information (more, less data) http://www.coopint.unlu.edu.ar/?q=node/11
Universidad Nacional de Misiones	2 1 Ing 1 Mgr.	?Progr am? 5..	6	- Respo nsible by Facult y (new) -MoU (inside Ocs) - NtW -Prgm (progr ams, new) -Nws	Programa de Relaciones Internacionales e Integración Regional - RIeIR La Universidad Nacional de Misiones (UNaM), en todos sus ámbitos y niveles, tiene como objetivo profundizar el proceso de integración regional e internacionalización, dando participando en todas aquellas iniciativas que favorecen al desarrollo de la región Mercosur y al mundo. Por ello, surge el Programa de Relaciones Internacionales e Integración Regional que tiene como misión promover y coordinar la vinculación internacional y regional de la UNaM en los aspectos institucionales, académicos, científicos, tecnológicos y culturales en el ámbito de la cooperación. Dicho programa tiene entre sus objetivos: • Desarrollar programas y proyectos cooperativos que conduzcan a generar y consolidar un espacio de planificación, gestión y comunicación entre la Universidad y las instituciones u organismos extranjeros. • Promover la concreción de publicaciones propias, en conjunto con otras instituciones o formando parte de redes de integración de proyectos. • Actualizar y difundir información sobre las posibilidades de estudios, becas e intercambios.		spanish updated http://www.unam.edu.ar/index.php/internacionales.html

					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Asistir a la comunidad universitaria en la búsqueda y utilización de fuentes de financiamiento y modalidades de cooperación internacional y regional. 		
Universidad Nacional de Moreno	ND	ND	ND	ND	<p>La Oficina de Relaciones Internacionales de la UNM asesora a la comunidad universitaria sobre las oportunidades de relacionamiento y cooperación internacional que sean de utilidad para fortalecer las actividades de docencia, investigación y extensión de la institución y de sus miembros.</p> <p>En ese sentido, difunde mecanismos para participar en programas existentes y promueve entre sus integrantes la importancia de desarrollar acciones en el actual contexto de internacionalización de la educación superior.</p> <p>Además, procura generar nuevos proyectos y oportunidades para que la comunidad académica encare la participación en tal proceso desde la especificidad de la institución y del proyecto que la inspira.</p> <p>En esta página, o subscribiéndose a nuestro boletín virtual, podrá encontrar información relevante sobre becas, programas de intercambio estudiantil y movilidad docente, redes de cooperación, eventos nacionales e internacionales y todo tipo de novedades relevantes en la materia.</p>	<p>http://www.unm.edu.ar/autoridades.aspx MG. Jorge L. ETCHARRÁN Secretario de Investigación, Vinculación Tecnológica y Relaciones Internacionales a/c</p>	<p>spanish http://www.unm.edu.ar/boletinvirtualrrii.aspx I can't refer to updated nor outdated since there isn't information</p>
Universidad Nacional de Río Cuarto	ND	1*	5 in spanish 3 in English	<p>-GS -Intl -Mb</p> <p>ENGL ISH -GS -IC depart m (new) -Mb (students) -Ntw</p>	<p>About the International Cooperation Department</p> <p>The International Cooperation Department aims at promoting integration with foreign universities and academic centers through undergraduate and graduate programs and research, allowing student and teacher reciprocal mobility between higher education institutions.</p> <p>The construction of an ample academic space is favored by the development of an international experience to enrich the training of students and academics as well as the institutional strengthening through the establishment of strategic alliances and the development of exchange activities in the area of</p>		<p>spanish updated https://www.unrc.edu.ar/unrc/coopinternacional/ci-institucional.php some information is outdated (MoU until 2011) English shorter than spanish version with mistakes https://www.unrc.edu.ar/unrc/intcooperation/ci-institucional.php</p>

				-Lks	<p>undergraduate and graduate student mobility.</p> <p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To promote the internationalization of the National University of Rio Cuarto. • To intervene in the regional and international promotion of the university to favor its insertion into the globalized world. • To intervene in the connection with foreign universities, cooperation agencies and international organizations. • To design and manage activities to internationalize the university. • To promote and organize the international mobility of the university students and teachers. • To manage the university's participation in international networks. • To understand the dissemination of information about academic and institutional exchanges. 		
Universidad Nacional de Tierra del Fuego, Antártida e Islas del Atlántico Sur	ND	ND	ND	ND	<p>According the webpage, had a International Cooperation space/area, but inside the data explain the Administration Secretary.</p> <p>http://www.untdf.edu.ar/la_universidad/secretaria_de_cooperacion_internacional</p>		<p>spanish without information</p> <p>http://www.untdf.edu.ar/la_universidad/secretaria_de_cooperacion_internacional</p>
Universidad Nacional de Tres de Febrero	2 1 Dr. (Director de Asuntos Internacionales e Institucionales) 1 Graduate (Responsable de Cooperación)	3	2	1 Dirección of International and Institutional affairs (new) a.- presen	<p>a) La dirección de Asuntos Internacionales e Institucionales, creada a fines de 2012, surge de una decisión que va en línea con la constante actividad que lleva adelante nuestra Universidad en asuntos internacionales y con la consolidación del espíritu dinámico de la Untref, que propicia los vínculos con instituciones políticas, económicas y educativas de nuestro país y del extranjero.</p> <p>Esta Dirección se constituye como una impulsora de políticas y actividades, así como un espacio de articulación entre las distintas áreas, centros e</p>	<p>a) Objetivos</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Propiciar actividades que generen nuevos espacios de participación para la comunidad educativa de esta Universidad y que fortalezcan y desarrollen los vínculos ya existentes con organizaciones e instituciones internacionales. • Fomentar vínculos dinámicos y duraderos con organizaciones gubernamentales y no gubernamentales orientadas a la integración regional. 	<p>spanish</p> <p>http://untref.edu.ar/secciones-institucional/direccion-de-asuntos-internacionales-e-institucionales/</p> <p>spanish</p> <p>http://untref.edu.ar/secciones-</p>

	n Internacional)			tation/ NEW b.- Objectives(new) c.- Publications(new) d.- Conferences(new) e.- other activities(new) 2CpT A.- CPT a1.- Principles(new) a2.- Oand Aand Norganismos, agencias y redes(new) a3.- MoU a4.- Mana	<p>institutos que requieran vinculación formal y de alto nivel con dependencias públicas y espacios privados. Las distintas actividades que se realizan desde la Dirección pueden organizarse de acuerdo a los siguientes ejes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elaboración e impulso de políticas internacionales junto a las autoridades dada la dependencia directa de la Dirección con el Rectorado. • Asesoramiento y gestiones necesarias para emprendimientos de distintas áreas de la Universidad. • Realización de acuerdos políticos y culturales binacionales y/o multinacionales por ante organismo públicos y privados. • Emprendimientos editoriales vinculados con la temática de la Dirección. <p>b) La Dirección de Cooperación Internacional trabaja activamente ampliando su participación en el proceso de internacionalización de la educación superior. La UNTREF adhiere a la concepción de la cooperación internacional entre las universidades e instituciones de educación superior –inspirada en la UNESCO- basada en dos principios fundamentales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • el proceso dinámico al interior de las instituciones que expande su potencial a la región y al mundo, al introducir la dimensión transnacional en sus funciones de docencia, investigación y extensión para la mejora de su calidad y proyección. • la complementariedad de sus capacidades con el propósito de contribuir al fortalecimiento institucional y la expansión del conocimiento de manera recíproca. <p>Esto la sitúa en un rol activo en el establecimiento de políticas y estrategias institucionales para la cooperación, y una selección elaborada de objetivos y socios que garantizan el beneficio mutuo y el enriquecimiento académico de las carreras de grado y de postgrado en curso. De acuerdo a esta línea de</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trabajar sobre la realización de seminarios, conferencias y congresos relacionados a las Relaciones Internacionales. • Realizar publicaciones relativas a las Relaciones Internacionales que convoquen a personalidades reconocidas, y que representen un material valioso que se sume al ya producido por esta Universidad. 	institucional/cooperacion-internacional/
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				g (new) a5.-Ct B.-Mb b1.- Prt (prese ntatio n- new) b2.- Indica tors (new) b3.-Ct C.-Fs c1.- under gradua tescou rses(n ew) c2.- ExchS (new) c3.- GS c4.- Enroll ment (new) D.- UALc d1.- Prt d2.- Hst (histor y, new)	acción, se enfatiza la integración de mejores instrumentos de gestión de la cooperación internacional que permitan un impacto institucional en sintonía a las actuales necesidades de producción del conocimiento. La multiplicación de los recursos hace a la creatividad de las modalidades, y por eso el relevamiento de nuevos caminos es permanente.		
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				d3.- Ms and Obj (new) d4.- Strct (new) E.- Prgm Mb-St (new) e1.- FnD (funda mental s-new) e2.- Obj e3.- Acad- Rcg (new- recogn ition) e4.- Rqrm (requir ement s-new) e5.- Enrll ment		
Universidad Nacional de Villa María	1 Contador (Vice Chancellor in charge)	5 (espacio) (Coordinación)	14	-WwA -Nws -Pj - Mb_pr of	La internacionalización del conocimiento y la globalización de la información plantean importantes retos para las instituciones educativas; contexto que representa una oportunidad para que la Universidad acreciente su rol protagónico y de liderazgo en la inserción de su región de referencia con el país y el	spanish updated http://webarchivo.unvm.edu.ar/index.php?%

		<p>n General Unidad de Proyectos Especiales y Cooperación Internacional Unidad de Intercambio y Movilidad Estudiantil Unidad de Actividades de Apoyo)</p>	<p>- Mb_St ud -NLt -Trn -MoU -ExP -Pes -Sps -Ocs -Ct</p>	<p>mundo, intensificando su fortalecimiento institucional a través de alianzas estratégicas con instituciones académicas, de investigación y de cooperación internacional.</p> <p>Para el cumplimiento de tal estrategia, la Universidad Nacional de Villa María cuenta con un Espacio de Relaciones Internacionales dependiente del Vicerrectorado, que promueve el establecimiento de redes, la cooperación internacional y la movilidad inter-institucional de sus docentes, investigadores y estudiantes, contribuyendo a la formación integral de los mismos a través de la experiencia y el contacto con otras culturas y sociedades, favoreciendo un espacio de respeto por la diversidad.</p> <p>El Espacio de Relaciones Internacionales de la Universidad Nacional de Villa María tiene los siguientes objetivos:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Impulsar una Universidad sin fronteras, preparada para enviar y recibir docentes, investigadores y estudiantes, en un ambiente abierto, rico en posibilidades y experiencias. • Internacionalizar la docencia, en especial en el espacio de integración regional de nuestro país (MERCOSUR) con acuerdos de convalidación o equivalencia para facilitar los intercambios fructíferos. • Incorporar la oferta académica de la Universidad a redes internacionales especializadas, de manera de promover su conocimiento y difusión. • Propiciar el desarrollo de una política de formación en lenguas extranjeras mediante programas específicos dirigidos a los docentes, estudiantes, graduados, y personal de administración y servicios de la Universidad. • Promocionar la Universidad como sede de encuentros internacionales, dando 		<p>20mod=cmsinteranda cc=categoriaandid=27</p>
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					<p>apoyo a la organización de los diferentes eventos.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Garantizar la presencia institucional activa de la Universidad en los foros internacionales de carácter universitario más destacados. 		
Universidad Nacional de Villa Mercedes	ND	0	ND	ND	ND	ND	Spanish http://web.unvime.edu.ar/unvime/secciones/autoridades
Universidad Nacional del Chaco Austral	ND	5? http://www.uncaus.edu.ar/index.php/institucional/autoridades doesn't explain	1	CpT	ND	ND	spanish outdated (last data 2012) http://www.uncaus.edu.ar/index.php/cooperacion-y-servicios/cooperacion google translator to: English, Italian, Portuguese, German
Universidad Nacional del Noroeste de la Provincia de Buenos Aires	ND	3	12	MoU Int-Prgm (new) CAVI LA (new) Ocs SmAr g Fs-OA GFs VFs RsFs RqFs	<p>La UNNOBA se ha planteado la ejecución de una política de cooperación como medio fundamental para llevar adelante su compromiso de contribuir con la mejora de la realidad regional, provincial y nacional y de dar curso a la interrelación con otras instituciones, nacionales y extranjeras.</p> <p>La política de cooperación no es un fin en sí mismo, sino un medio que cobra sentido como forma de colaborar y mejorar los alcances de aquellas acciones que corresponden a los pilares fundamentales de la universidad: la docencia, la investigación y la extensión.</p> <p>Desde esta perspectiva, busca dar continuidad al proceso de acercamiento institucional en la estrategia de internacionalización y la política de cooperación</p>		Spanish updated http://www.unnoba.edu.ar/academica/relaciones-internacionales/funciones/

				NLt Ct	<p>con otras instituciones nacionales y extranjeras, que se ha iniciado en el año 2007 y se busca afianzar a través de la firma de convenios de colaboración; la movilidad de estudiantes, docentes, investigadores y gestores; la presentación de proyectos en convocatorias nacionales e internacionales; la participación en organizaciones internacionales cuyo fin sea fomentar la cooperación y la integración entre las universidades; la organización de eventos interdisciplinarios de carácter internacional; la participación en ferias y conferencias internacionales.</p> <p>En este marco, desde Dirección de Relaciones Internacionales la UNNOBA promueve la movilidad, los vínculos y la cooperación con universidades, centros de investigación y organizaciones internacionales dedicadas a la educación superior, la docencia, la investigación y la promoción de la cultura.</p> <p>En este marco, se han firmado más de 60 convenios de colaboración con prestigiosas instituciones de América Latina y el Caribe, Europa, Estados Unidos y China que promueven el intercambio estudiantil a nivel de grado y posgrado. Todos los años la UNNOBA recibe numerosos estudiantes que perfeccionan sus estudios y viven una experiencia enriquecedora.</p> <p>Como parte del proceso de internacionalización, la UNNOBA se ha incorporado a dos importantes organismos internacionales como son la Unión de Universidades de América Latina y el Caribe (UDUAL) y la Organización Universitaria Interamericana (OUI). En 2013 la UNNOBA obtuvo la acreditación internacional otorgada por RIEV-UDUAL. Asimismo, es miembro activo de la Hispanic Association of Colleges and Universities (HACU) que reúne a más de 400 instituciones de educación superior en Estados Unidos, Latinoamérica y España, en las cuales los hispanos constituyen al menos el 25% del alumnado total.</p>		
Universidad Nacional del Oeste	ND	0	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND

<http://www.uno.edu.ar/index.php/secretarias/90-secretarias>

							http://www.uno.edu.ar/index.php/secretarias/90-secretarias
Universidad Nacional Alto Uruguay	New	0	ND	ND	8 de enero pasado, con el decreto N° 10/15 se promulgó en el Boletín Oficial de la Nación la Ley N° 27.074 que crea la Unau.	ND	New - ND
Universidad Nacional de Rafaela	New	0	ND	ND	Universidad Nacional de Rafaela Ley. 27.062. Sancionada el 03/12/14	ND	New-ND
Universidad Nacional de los Comechingones	New	0	ND	ND	Ley 26.998 Sancionada: Octubre 22 de 2014 Promulgada de Hecho: Noviembre 7 de 2014	ND	New-ND
Universidad de la Defensa Nacional	New	0	ND	ND	Ley 27.015 Sancionada el 12/11/2014 Promulgada el 02/11/2014	ND	New-ND

Appendix 2 - Argentine Stakeholders – Charter

Stakeholder	N° Employees	Hierarchy	N° Subcategories	Types	Mission/Visions	Extra data	Webpage for foreigners
<i>CONICET</i>	Not mentioned	http://web.conicet.gov.ar/web/conicet/acerca-de.autoridades/estructura-administrativa (administrative structure)	0	XX	<p>Science and technology CONICET encourages scientific and technologic exchange and cooperation within the country apart from promoting bonds with international scientific communities. Thus, it fosters joint research and development projects with academic and scientific institutions at national and international levels.</p> <p>International Cooperation International cooperation plays a leading role in the field of Argentine science and technology as well as for new developments with added value. Considering this and according to the National Plan for Science, Technology and Innovation from the Ministry of Science, Technology and Productive Innovation, CONICET is committed to establishing lasting and profound bonds with the International scientific community. CONICET engages in international cooperation through agreements with institutions in charge of scientific and technological promotion and with other prestigious academic and scientific organizations.</p> <p>International cooperation activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Thematic scientific exchange programmes with International partners. ▪ International research programmes. ▪ International associated laboratories. ▪ International research centers. ▪ Global programmes in which CONICET has an International component. 	<p>The National Scientific and Technical Research Council (CONICET) is the main organization in charge of the promotion of Science and Technology in Argentina. The principal objective of this agency is to boost and implement scientific and technical activities in the country and in all different fields of knowledge. This institution has its own researchers and professionals. Thus, CONICET offers different grants and finances projects, institutions and national research centres in all parts of the country. CONICET comprises general areas so as to enable comprehensive development of scientific and technological research. Thus, it is in charge of all social interest and productive areas of Argentina. Apart from that, this organization promotes different exchanges and stimulates national and international cooperative processes.</p> <p>Areas of knowledge of CONICET</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Agrarian, Engineering and Material Sciences. ▪ Biological and Health Sciences. ▪ Exact and Natural Sciences. ▪ Social Sciences and Humanities. <p>Technology is present in all the areas and it promotes the implementation of knowledge.</p>	<p>http://web.conicet.gov.ar/web/conicet.trabajamos/investigacion/descripcion1 short version in English</p> <p>updated</p>

		ization chart) http://web.conicet.gov.ar/web/contacto (real location)			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> International consortiums in fields that require large investments. CONICET carries out different scientific cooperation projects with more than 30 countries. http://www.conicet.gov.ar/description/?lan=en 	<p>Founded in 1958, CONICET is a national institution under the Ministry of Science, Technology and Productive Innovation of Argentina. Besides, this agency is considered as one of the principal assets for the national fund in terms of science and technology.</p> <p>http://www.conicet.gov.ar/about-the-conicet/?lan=en</p>	
INTA	5 http://inta.gob.ar/unidades/127400/ 21	3° http://inta.gob.ar/so-bre-el-inta/organigramas or 2° as gral.	XX 4	XX	<p>Tiene por misión:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Asistir a la Dirección Nacional Asistente en la formulación de la estrategia de las relaciones institucionales del INTA en el ámbito internacional, a nivel multilateral, bilateral e implementación de los Labintex. Fortalecer las capacidades institucionales, a través de la promoción de acciones de vinculación y gestión de acuerdos del ámbito internacional con organismos internacionales y nacionales - públicos y privados- del sistema agropecuario, alimentario y agroindustrial. Asesorar a los componentes institucionales del INTA en la gestión de las relaciones internacionales. 		<p>http://inta.gob.ar/unidades/127400/ dependent from http://inta.gob.ar/unidades/127000/</p> <p>updated</p>
REDCIUN	XX	1°?	4 commissions + "1: temporal"		<p><u>OBJETIVOS DE LA REDCIUN</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promover la internacionalización de la educación superior argentina. Contribuir al desarrollo institucional de las universidades nacionales en el campo de su competencia. 	<p>La RedCIUN</p> <p>Son miembros plenos de la RedCIUN las instituciones universitarias nacionales que integran el Consejo Interuniversitario Nacional. La Red está coordinada por una Comisión Ejecutiva constituida por siete</p>	<p>http://www.redciun.edu.ar/ spanish</p> <p>outdated: 06/06/2015</p>

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generar, promover e implementar programas, proyectos y acciones que respondan adecuadamente a los intereses de las Universidades Nacionales. • Constituir instancias de coordinación y articulación con organismos gubernamentales y no gubernamentales a fin de realizar propuestas y formular opiniones. • Promover la articulación con otras entidades y redes nacionales e internacionales que tengan objetivos y propósitos compatibles con los de la RedCIUN. • Contribuir al desarrollo y profesionalización de las áreas de relaciones internacionales como estructuras especializadas en la promoción y gestión de la internacionalización de la educación superior argentina. • Asesorar técnicamente al CIN y a los Ministerios de Educación, Ciencia y Tecnología y de Relaciones Exteriores, Comercio Internacional y Culto en temas de su competencia. • Estimular la capacitación y el entrenamiento de los recursos humanos en temas propios de la RedCIUN mediante la formación de un programa general con intervención de las universidades nacionales y sujeto a las necesidades regionales. • Promover estrategias de acción conjunta para el logro de los objetivos trazados. <p>http://www.redciun.edu.ar/files/OBJETIVOS%20DE%20LA%20REDCIUN.pdf</p>	<p>miembros plenos designados en Reunión Plenaria por el término de un año. En el último plenario, celebrado en noviembre de 2009, se estableció que las siete Universidades que integran la Comisión Ejecutiva para el periodo 2010 son:</p> <p>Universidad Nacional de Catamarca, Universidad Nacional de Córdoba, Universidad Nacional de Formosa, Universidad Nacional de San Juan, Universidad Nacional del Litoral, Universidad Nacional del Sur, Universidad Nacional de Quilmes. Esta última, ocupa el cargo de coordinadora general.</p> <p>Para la adecuada consecución de sus fines, la RedCIUN ha organizado su trabajo en Comisiones Permanentes y Temporarias:</p> <p>Las Comisiones Permanentes son:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comisión de Comunicación • Comisión de Capacitación • Comisión de Estudios • Comisión de Cooperación en Investigación, Transferencia y Desarrollo <p>Las Comisiones Temporarias son:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comisión de Revisión, Interpretación y Actualización del Reglamento <p>Presentación</p> <p>La Red de Cooperación Internacional de las Universidades Nacionales – RedCIUN ha sido creada en el ámbito del Consejo Interuniversitario Nacional (CIN), mediante Acuerdo Plenario N° 326 del año 1999, a raíz de la propuesta de constituir una red de cooperación internacional de las Universidades Nacionales surgida del Encuentro de Responsables de Relaciones Internacionales de Universidades Nacionales,</p>
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						realizado en la ciudad de Santa Fe, los días 14 y 20 de abril del año 1999. http://www.redciun.edu.ar/index.php?option=com_contentandview=categoryandlayout=blogandid=3andItemid=3.html	
<i>SPU – PIESCI</i>	8	5°	4	Cooperación Internacional PROGRAMA DE INTERNACIONALIZACIÓN DE LA EDUCACIÓN SUPERIOR Y COOPERACIÓN INTERNACIONAL OBJETIVOS DEL PROGRAMA <i>Objetivo General</i> • Maximizar el aprovechamiento de las oportunidades que el mundo de la cooperación educativa y académica ofrecen en el ámbito nacional, regional e internacional. <i>Objetivos específicos</i> • Impulsar la inserción de las instituciones de educación superior argentinas en los procesos de internacionalización, integración y desarrollo local y regional. • Funcionar como área de vinculación al interior de la SPU, aprovechando las posibilidades que brinda la cooperación internacional para el apoyo y desarrollo de las políticas universitarias. 2° Programa de Cooperación Internacional Universitaria El Programa de Internacionalización de la Educación Superior y Cooperación Internacional, en el ámbito de la Secretaría de Políticas Universitarias, coordina todas las acciones relacionadas con la internacionalización de la educación superior y la cooperación internacional universitaria. Impulsa la inserción de las instituciones de educación superior argentinas en los procesos de vinculación internacional, integración, desarrollo local y regional, además de funcionar como área de vinculación al	INTRODUCCIÓN POLÍTICAS Y ACCIONES IMPULSADAS Con la finalidad de alcanzar los objetivos planteados, el Programa desarrolla sus actividades principalmente en tres dimensiones o esferas de acción: dentro del ámbito nacional, a nivel bilateral y en el plano multilateral. En lo que respecta al ámbito nacional la función principal del área radica en la canalización de las demandas y necesidades del Sistema Universitario Argentino en materia de internacionalización de la educación superior y la cooperación internacional, y articularlas con los proyectos y acciones impulsadas desde el área. Este enlace se realiza principalmente a través del Consejo Interuniversitario Nacional (CIN) en particular por intermedio de la REDCIUN (Red de Cooperación Internacional de Universidades Nacionales). Asimismo, el área se encarga de gestionar el Sistema de Cupos Universitarios para alumnos extranjeros, establecido en la Resolución Ministerial 1523/90. La información es organizada en una base informática y comunicada a la Cancillería Argentina para su posterior difusión entre las representaciones diplomáticas argentinas en el mundo. Las acciones de cooperación bilateral tienen como eje estratégico la cooperación con los países de América Latina y del MERCOSUR en particular. A través de estas acciones se intenta potenciar las capacidades y contribuir	http://portales.educacion.gov.ar/spu/cooperacion-internacional/spanish	

					<p>interior del Ministerio de Educación, aprovechando las posibilidades que brinda la cooperación internacional para el apoyo y desarrollo de las políticas universitarias.</p> <p>http://portales.educacion.gov.ar/spu/objetivos/</p>	<p>al fortalecimiento de los sistemas universitarios de la región, fomentando la cooperación interinstitucional. Por otro lado, dentro de este ámbito de acción también se intenta lograr un mayor aprovechamiento de las oportunidades de cooperación internacional con países desarrollados, a los efectos de promover el desarrollo del sistema universitario argentino.</p> <p>En lo que refiere a la cooperación multilateral el eje estratégico se encuentra identificado en el MERCOSUR y la UNASUR. De esta manera el Programa participa en representación de Argentina en las reuniones de la Comisión Regional Coordinadora de Educación Superior del Sector Educativo del MERCOSUR y en las reuniones del Consejo Suramericano de Educación, Cultura, Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación de UNASUR (COSECCTI) a través del Subgrupo de Educación Superior. Otro de los espacios multilaterales de la región donde el Programa tiene participación es el Espacio Iberoamericano del Conocimiento, que tiene el propósito de incrementar los niveles de desarrollo de la región, disminuir la brecha entre los países, garantizando un incremento de la productividad, brindando mejor calidad y accesibilidad a los bienes y servicios por parte de la población e incrementando la competitividad internacional de la región.</p>	
<i>CIN</i> *	NA	NA	NA	NA	<p>El CIN tiene por funciones:</p> <p>a. Elaborar propuestas de políticas y estrategias de desarrollo universitario, incluida la coordinación las políticas comunes a las instituciones universitarias que lo integran.</p> <p>b. Definir y coordinar planes y actividades en materia académica, de investigación científica, de extensión y de gestión entre las instituciones que lo integran, sin</p>	<p>El Consejo Interuniversitario Nacional (CIN) fue creado por Decreto del Presidente de la República Argentina, Dr. Raúl Alfonsín, el 20 de diciembre de 1985. El Consejo es una persona de derecho público no estatal que se sostiene, primordialmente, con los aportes que realizan sus miembros.</p> <p>Durante sus primeros diez años de vida, núcleo, exclusivamente, a las universidades</p>	<p>http://www.cin.edu.ar/ spanish updated</p>

				<p>perjuicio de aquellas que las instituciones universitarias acuerden realizar por sí.</p> <p>c. Coordinar las políticas de sus miembros con los distintos niveles y jurisdicciones de la educación y con los organismos de la cultura y de la investigación científica y técnica.</p> <p>d. Conformar, en los casos en que así lo estimare conveniente, organismos regionales de coordinación interuniversitaria.</p> <p>e. Emitir opinión fundada respecto de todo proyecto de creación y cierre de instituciones universitarias nacionales.</p> <p>f. Generar y apoyar políticas de autoevaluación y evaluación externa de sus miembros.</p> <p>g. Coordinar, compatibilizar y establecer propuestas sobre la validez de los estudios totales y parciales, y de sus títulos.</p> <p>h. Proponer y promover una política de becas, para docentes y alumnos, tendiente a asegurar la igualdad de oportunidades.</p> <p>i. Promover programas de investigación común, ya sean de carácter nacional o regional.</p> <p>j. Analizar los problemas de la educación general y universitaria en la República Argentina, y formular propuestas a los poderes públicos.</p> <p>k. Analizar los problemas de la educación general y universitaria en el mundo, y en especial en América Latina, y formular propuestas de intercambio e integración académica.</p> <p>l. Establecer relaciones de todo orden y firmar acuerdos de cooperación con otros organismos públicos y privados, nacionales o extranjeros en general, y especialmente con aquellos que puedan otorgar líneas de financiamiento, colaboraciones o donaciones de fondos e implementos y apoyo técnico, para la ejecución de programas, proyectos y actividades, en el área científica, tecnológica, cultural y deportiva.</p> <p>m. Coordinar y/o administrar programas y proyectos financiados por organismos públicos nacionales,</p>	<p>nacionales que, voluntariamente y en uso de su autonomía, se adhirieron a él como organismo coordinador de políticas universitarias. A partir de la sanción de la Ley de Educación Superior (1995), se han incorporado los institutos universitarios y las universidades provinciales reconocidas por la Nación.</p> <p>El CIN tiene funciones, esencialmente, de coordinación de políticas universitarias y la promoción de políticas y actividades de interés para el sistema público de Educación Superior. Es, además, órgano de consulta obligada en la toma de decisiones de trascendencia para el sistema universitario.</p> <p> Junto con el Consejo de Rectores de Universidades Privadas (CRUP) y representantes de los Consejos de Planificación Regional de la Educación Superior (CPRES), integra el Consejo de Universidades, que preside el Ministro de Educación de la Nación.</p> <p>En el marco del Art. 24° de su Estatuto, se constituyen las Comisiones Permanentes en el Consejo Interuniversitario Nacional (CIN), entre las que se distribuye el estudio de los temas que les asigna el Comité Ejecutivo y la dependencia de las redes interuniversitarias.</p> <p>Las Comisiones están integradas por los rectores de las instituciones miembros del CIN o quienes ellos designen. Así, cada Comisión está presidida por un Vocal del Comité Ejecutivo, y tiene un Vicepresidente, también Rector, elegidos ambos por el Plenario para tales funciones.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Asuntos Académicos • Ciencia, Técnica y Arte • Posgrado
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					<p>provinciales o municipales, o por organismos internacionales.</p> <p>n. Informar sobre sus actividades al conjunto del sistema educativo nacional.</p> <p>o. Cooperar, asistir y asesorar en las actividades y emprendimientos de cada uno de sus miembros cuando le fuera requerido.</p> <p>p. Funcionar como órgano de consulta en las materias y cuestiones que se le sometan y participar en los organismos que integre.</p> <p>Como miembro de Consejo de Universidades, desarrolla las siguientes acciones:</p> <p>a. Acuerda con el Consejo Federal de Educación criterios y pautas para articular con otros niveles educativos.</p> <p>b. Participa en el Consejo Consultivo del Instituto de Formación Docente.</p> <p>c. Determina las carreras universitarias de grado sujetas a acreditación y, de ellas, la carga horaria mínima de los planes de estudio, los contenidos curriculares básicos y los criterios sobre la intensidad de la formación práctica y los patrones y estándares para los procesos de acreditación.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Asuntos Económicos • Asuntos Internacionales • Extensión, Bienestar Universitario y Vinculación Territorial • Relaciones Institucionales • Comunicación y Medios • Conectividad y Redes • Acreditación • Vinculación Tecnológica 	
<i>INTI</i> *	ND	ND	ND	ND	<p>Mission, vision and values</p> <p>Misión Promote the generation and transfer of technological innovation to industry and to ensure that the quality of processes, goods and services comply with global standards and trends. The agency performs activities in its capacity as certifying agency of standards and specifications, and disseminator of knowledge and technology practices.</p> <p>Vision Become a leading institution in the generation and transfer of technology with international projection, human capital and cutting-edge technological-scientific infrastructure that contributes to addressing national priority issues, and increasing the competitiveness of companies, mainly small- and medium-sized enterprises, and that of the whole</p>	<p>Institutional Introduction</p> <p>As the government's technology branch, the mission of the National Institute of Industrial Technology is to promote generation and transfer of technological innovation in industry, while ensuring the quality of processes, goods and services produced in accordance with global standards and trends. The agency carries out these tasks its capacity as certifying agency of standards and specifications, and disseminator of knowledge and technology practices.</p> <p>Under the 2020 Industrial Plan, INTI's activities are performed around three strategic pillars:</p>	<p>http://www.inti.gob.ar / spanish English: short version Updated</p>

				<p>country, in a sustainable manner. Moreover, INTI seeks to become a national leader in quality and metrology for decision-making in public policy matters.</p> <p>Values Reliability Confidentiality Impartiality Technological power Interdisciplinary work Continuous Improvement Sense of belonging Staff development</p> <p>International cooperation The international cooperation policy comprises planning, implementation and supervision of knowledge transfer to countries requiring assistance for industrial development, while identifying foreign technologies that might contribute to Argentina's industrial development. The linking strategy is built on two pillars:</p> <p>International technology transfer The promotion of knowledge, new technologies and innovation transfer to countries of equal or lesser degree of development contributes to strengthening their productive and industrial fabric. Over the last decade, due to the increased regional integration, INTI and other national agencies have responded to requests from the Argentine Fund for South-South and Triangular Cooperation managed by the Directorate General for International Cooperation of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Worship. In this framework, INTI's accumulated knowledge and technical ability in a wide range of areas enabled it to transfer knowledge to several countries in the region and solve technological problems similar to the local ones. As a result of specific bilateral agreements, the agency provided technical assistance to governments of</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Reconstruction of the productive fabric ▶ Federalization of industry ▶ Promotion of innovation in SMEs across the country <p>INTI's role is to develop, preserve and maintain the national measurement standards, and disseminate their accuracy as Argentina's metrology institute. This role contributes to assuring quality measurements that protect the environment, health, food, public safety, fair trade and industrial production quality.</p> <p>In addition, the agency works with SMEs and social economy ventures, whose articulation with the market economy leads to an improved integration of all productive players in the value chains.</p> <p>INTI has developed sound professional skills and advanced technology infrastructure, in many cases unique in Latin America, for over half a century. This contributes to the development of the national industry and to solving problems. At present, it has 45 research and development centers, and keeps consolidating its presence in every province across the country.</p> <p>Most of the agency's activity is now concentrated at Miguelete Technology Park (PTM), in Buenos Aires metropolitan area, which concentrates the greatest availability of infrastructure in over 50,000 m2 of buildings, and where 74% of its professional and technical staff regularly works. INTI's total workforce exceeds 2,600 agents.</p> <p>Activities range from technology services (analyses, testing, certification, calibration), technical assistance (audits, research and development, consulting and training), to extension as a modality oriented to relatively less developed sectors.</p>
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				<p>several Latin American countries, and promoted the transfer of knowledge to underpin productive and sustainable local development while improving the welfare of people. In addition, these actions promote the transfer of capital assets from Argentine companies.</p> <p>Scientific and technological articulation International cooperation contributes to strengthening institutional capacities. In line with bilateral or multilateral agreements, scientific and technological knowledge is exchanged for the mutual enrichment of capabilities, use of comparative advantages and synergies for common benefits. In this direction, INTI fosters the creation of technical and professional groups to share interdisciplinary and multinational work where members of leading countries in science and technology also participate. Detection of mature technologies in more developed global scenarios becomes an opportunity for technological-productive innovation to increase the competitiveness of our local industry. http://www.inti.gob.ar/inglesrwd/international_cooperation.htm</p>		
<i>MINCyT</i>				<p><i>NATIONAL DIRECTORATE OF INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS</i> http://en.mincyt.gob.ar/ministerio/national-directorate-of-international-relations-11 <u>Role of the Directorate</u> The National Directorate of International Relations deals with those issues inherent in cooperation with foreign countries, agencies and other institutions of international character, related to the field of science, technology and innovation. It directs its actions to strengthen, complement and integrate the local research and development capabilities with foreign countries. In that sense, it promotes the realization of joint research projects and training, exchange of experts, and the transfer of results to national productive sector. Main objectives of the Directorate:</p>	<p><u>Bilateral Cooperation</u> The bilateral cooperation mechanisms between Argentina and a foreign state are set by programmes arising from the signing of International or Interagency Agreements. The main objective of cooperation programmes is to foster the linkage of the national scientific community with their peers abroad on the basis of mutual interest in developing research and exchanging knowledge. The collaboration is implemented through the development of joint research projects, the organization of different kinds of events, the creation of binational centers and the granting of scholarships for training.</p>	<p>http://www.mincyt.gob.ar/ Spanish/English Updated</p>

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Oversee the monitoring of international agreements and the implementation of projects that involve the Cyted, the European Union and the MERCOSUR. • Coordinate the link with agencies of the National System of Science, Technology and Innovation, regarding international cooperation. • Address scientific and technological cooperation issues in the integration process of MERCOSUR countries. • Execute scientific and technological linking actions and resource management actions with other countries, in coordination with the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, International Trade and Worship. • Design instruments for international resource linking and management and their coordination with public and private agencies related to scientific and technological activity. • Follow up international agreements in science and technology and the implementation of joint projects. • Articulate the linkage between Argentinean researchers living in the country and abroad. <p><i>International cooperation</i> The National Directorate of International Relations promotes the strengthening of international cooperation -bilateral, multilateral or with enterprises- as a strategic tool in the design of policies and the development of science, technology and productive innovation nationwide.</p>	<p><i>Multilateral Cooperation</i> Cooperation at multilateral level promotes the participation of institutions, research groups and Argentinean companies in programmes and initiatives related to science, technology and innovation promoted by regional and international organizations. International and Interagency Agreements constitute the legal framework of multilateral relations and set the level of cooperation and commitment generated in each case.</p> <p><i>International Cooperation with Companies</i> The projects of international cooperation promote scientific and technological cooperation between companies of different countries. By doing so, they seek to incorporate knowledge in the productive process in order to improve the competitiveness of companies and promote collaboration of the private sector with research centres. The projects of international cooperation receive financing through the International Non-Refundable Contributions (International ANR and ANR FONSOFT International Window) of the National Agency for Science and Technology Promotion. Moreover, the initiatives may apply for the loans for modernization projects of the Agency.</p>	
<i>RACI</i>						http://www.raci.org.ar /

Appendix 3 - European Coordinators - IROs chart

University/N° EMA2 with Arg/students Number; EMA2s1 in gral	N° Employees	Hierarchy	N° Subcategories	Types	Mission/Visions	Extra data	Webpage for foreigners
<p>University of Bologna/2+1 87,418 (11/12) 78.177 2012-2013 http://statistica.miur.it/scripts/IU/vIU1.asp from: Ministry for Universities and Scientific and Technological Research (Italian): http://www.murst.it/ 4/46 EMA2s1 2007 - 2013</p>	<p>39 No titles data (just staff type)</p>	<p>1°</p>	<p>A* 6 (+2)</p>	<p>1.- ALaN 2.- Eu (Eu: E+ Int and Mb) 3.- RAO 4.- Mb 5.- HRA 6.- EF</p>	<p>Mission La mission dell'Area è supportare tutti i soggetti interessati allo sviluppo di rapporti internazionali, promuovendo il coordinamento di attività di internazionalizzazione della didattica in Ateneo e il raccordo con i diversi attori interni ed esterni nell'ottica del Multicampus.</p> <p>Principali attività promuovere l'internazionalizzazione della didattica in stretta collaborazione con le singole facoltà attraverso il coordinamento globale dei processi di gestione della mobilità internazionale, il supporto e il coordinamento delle fasi precedenti e successive alla stipula di accordi con i partner per l'attivazione di iniziative didattiche internazionali volte alla creazione di percorsi intensivi e di percorsi internazionali doppi/congiunti in forte sinergia con l'Area Didattica e Servizi agli Studenti e l'Area Ricerca e Trasferimento Tecnologico, la promozione di iniziative didattiche internazionali e di progetti per il rafforzamento della didattica, il supporto dell'organizzazione delle Winter/Summer School e di Corsi intensivi etc. gestire la comunicazione, la consulenza e il supporto alle strutture di Ateneo per la partecipazione a programmi internazionali a livello europeo e extraeuropeo e di cooperazione allo sviluppo sui temi dell'istruzione e della formazione; assicurare il monitoraggio delle opportunità di finanziamento; svolgere le attività di gestione e di rendicontazione dei finanziamenti nazionali ed europei sui temi dell'istruzione e della formazione e supportare le Strutture di Ateneo nell'attività di gestione e</p>	<p>1.- Settore area geografica Africa, America Latina, Paesi del vicinato Mission Presidiare le relazioni, i progetti e i flussi di mobilità da e verso i paesi dell'area 'Africa, America Latina e Paesi del Vicinato' 2.- Settore Area geografica Europa Presidiare le relazioni, i progetti e i flussi di mobilità da e verso i paesi dell'area Europa. 2.- A. DIRI - Settore Area geografica europa - Ufficio Mobilità per studio Mission Assicurare la gestione delle attività relative alla mobilità in uscita a fini di studio degli studenti nell'ambito del programma comunitario Erasmus+ e della mobilità nell'ambito dei network. 2.- B DIRI - Settore Area geografica europa - Ufficio Mobilità per tirocinio Mission Assicurare la gestione delle attività relative alla mobilità in uscita a fini di tirocinio degli studenti nell'ambito del programma comunitario Erasmus+ e della mobilità nell'ambito dei network; assicurare la gestione delle attività relative alla mobilità a fini di insegnamento del personale docente e a fini di formazione del personale tecnico-amministrativo. 3.- Settore Area geografica Vicinato est, Russia, Asia, Oceania e Nord America Mission</p>	<p>Italian http://www.unibo.it/it/ateneo/organizzazione/amministrazione-generale/81737/index.html</p>

rendicontazione dei finanziamenti sui temi dell'istruzione e della formazione;
 gestire le attività relative alla mobilità per studio, tirocinio, formazione sul lavoro e attività di docenza, in entrata e in uscita, di studenti, docenti e personale tecnico-amministrativo, dalla predisposizione del bando per l'assegnazione dei posti scambio alla liquidazione dei contributi alla mobilità, garantendo lo sviluppo di servizi rivolti agli studenti stranieri iscritti all'Ateneo, e supportando gli studenti in partenza permettendo loro di usufruire delle migliori opportunità offerte dalle università partner presenti all'estero;
 predisporre le procedure di gestione delle convenzioni e accordi stipulati dall'Ateneo con partner stranieri ed extraeuropei favorendo l'arricchimento dell'offerta formativa, e coordinando iniziative che insistono su ambiti geografici e tematiche specifiche di interesse dell'Ateneo;
 approfondire alcune tematiche legate all'internazionalizzazione attraverso il confronto con i partner internazionali e la partecipazione a progetti di carattere innovativo;
 promuovere la cooperazione interuniversitaria intra ed extra UE con progetti di sviluppo di curricula, di supporto alla riforma universitaria e favorendo iniziative di miglioramento strutturale del sistema universitario (governance, sistemi di finanziamento, etc.), etc.;

costituire uno sportello unico rivolto agli studenti e ricercatori stranieri in collaborazione con l'Area Didattica e Servizi agli Studenti e l'Area Ricerca e Trasferimento Tecnologico.

Presidiare le relazioni, i progetti e i flussi di mobilità da e verso il Vicinato est, Russia, Asia, Oceania e Nord America.

4.- Settore Sportello utenti internazionali

Mission

Gestire le attività e le procedure relative all'accesso degli studenti internazionali ai corsi di studio di tutti i livelli dell'università; gestire le attività di accoglienza degli studenti internazionali in mobilità di scambio; gestire le attività e le procedure per l'accesso temporaneo all'università di Bologna di docenti e ricercatori; curare lo sviluppo di servizi mirati a tutte le tipologie di utenti internazionali.

5.- Ufficio di staff d'Area

Mission

Supportare il dirigente nel coordinamento delle attività svolte dalle altre unità organizzative in relazione ai livelli di servizio, alle procedure di selezione e di gestione della mobilità, alle caratteristiche degli accordi, alle norme generali e ai regolamenti interni contabili e amministrativi; curare la gestione del budget dell'Area e assicurare supporto alla gestione dei budget di progetto; assicurare il presidio delle attività amministrative e delle procedure informatiche di supporto all'Area; curare le attività di staff di area.

6.- Unità professionale progetti europei

Mission

Assicurare la comunicazione, la consulenza e il supporto alle strutture di Ateneo per la partecipazione a bandi relativi ai programmi europei di istruzione e formazione a livello europeo, assicurare il supporto alla gestione dei progetti finanziati e assicurare il monitoraggio delle opportunità di finanziamento.

<p><i>Universitat Politècnica de València/2+1</i> 29.266 (2012) http://www.upv.es/entidades/SG/infoweb/sg/info/U0650072.pdf pp.62 3/20 EMA2s1 2007 - 2013</p>	<p>7 (organizational chart)</p>	<p>3°</p>	<p>4</p>	<p>Mb IS UNESCO O CfD</p>	<p>International Affairs Office The International Affairs Office is part of the Rector's Office at Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV), and its main objective is to co-ordinate, promote and support the University's international presence through postgraduate programmes and academic collaboration with foreign institutions. The International Affairs Office is in charge of: - The financial and administrative co-ordination and management of postgraduate programmes implemented under an agreement with foreign institutions. - Providing support and advice to the University community in the management, co-ordination and administration of agreements and joint projects to be developed in conjunction with foreign institutions. - Channeling the participation of the University community interested in establishing international academic projects, as well as facilitating the submission of proposals to national (AECID...) and European (EACEA...) funding bodies. - Promoting the international standing of the UPV through the negotiation of new agreements and the participation of the University in international networks. Likewise, the International Affairs Office welcomes any initiative originating both from within the UPV and from external institutions.</p>	<p>Purposes and aims La Oficina de Acción Internacional es la encargada de: - Promover, apoyar y tramitar la formulación de acuerdos marco y específicos con universidades e instituciones extranjeras. - Dar difusión, informar y apoyar a los profesores de la UPV en la presentación de solicitudes de proyectos en convocatorias de administraciones públicas tanto a nivel nacional como internacional. - Canalizar la participación de la comunidad universitaria interesada en la presentación de proyectos académicos a propuestas de consorcios interuniversitarios en programas con financiación externa (Programas nacionales, de la Comisión Europea u otras instituciones financiadoras) - Gestionar la incorporación de becarios de programas bajo convenio institucional para su formación en la UPV apoyándolos hasta la finalización de su estancia. - Potenciar la presencia de la UPV en redes internacionales y su representación institucional en foros, tanto internacionales como nacionales, como la Comisión de Internacionalización y Cooperación de las Universidades Españolas (CICUE), delegada de la CRUE. Todo ello con el fin de contribuir a fortalecer la internacionalización de la universidad, en el marco de su estrategia institucional.</p>	<p>Spanish/Valencian http://www.upv.es/entidades/OAI/ English – incomplete Updated</p>
<p><i>Universidad de Málaga/1</i> 37.091 (12-13) http://www.uma.es/secretaria-general/memoria1213/contenidos/VicerrectoradodeEstudios.pdf 1/3 EMA2s1 2007-2013</p>	<p>17</p>	<p>2°</p>	<p>9</p>	<p>Mb x 3 (MbE+ and LaAO) MoU E+ IP</p>	<p>http://www.uma.es/cms/base/ver/base/basecontent/61627/proyeccion-internacional/?set_language=en INTERNATIONAL The UMA International Relations and Cooperation Service considers the internationalization process as one of its main strategic lines, encouraging this process</p>	<p>http://www.uma.es/relaciones-internacionales/cms/menu/bienvenida/?set_language=en Through the Deputy Vice-President for Student Mobility and the Deputy Vice-President for International Relations and Cooperation, the International Relations and</p>	<p>Spanish/English http://www.uma.es/cms/base/ver/base/basecontent/61627/proyeccion-internacional/ Deutsch/French/Chinese</p>

				<p>Pj PjC EF</p> <p>through the signing of agreements with foreign universities, institutions and enterprises. <u>Its main tasks are to:</u> > Manage mobility programmes for students, teachers, researchers and administrative staff. > Plan, apply for and manage international projects. > Strengthen cooperation and foment networking with foreign universities through the signing of agreements. > Extend knowledge and seek cooperation with foreign companies and institutions. > Develop cooperation programmes with third countries in the field of teaching and research. > Manage mobility programmes for students, teachers, researchers and administrative staff</p>	<p>Cooperation Service is directly responsible for managing international exchange programmes and providing those international students who want to study at UMA with the necessary guidance.</p> <p>STUDENT MOBILITY The International Relations and Cooperation Service manages student exchange programmes with foreign universities.</p> <p>INTERNATIONAL INTERNSHIPS The International Relations Service at UMA wishes to promote relations between the academic domain and the labor market at an international level. In this section we will announce calls to apply for internships in companies or other types of organization.</p> <p>INTERNATIONAL PROYECTS The internationalization policy of the University of Malaga has as essential element its presence and active participation in different projects, networks and international partnerships that enhances its international visibility and consolidates its prestige. The experience in the coordination of international projects opens windows to the global world each year to strengthen its international dimension, building up its presence among the European universities with larger number of international projects:</p> <p>Erasmus-Mundus; Programas Intensivos; Leonardo da Vinci; Tempus; Grundtvig; Redes Erasmus; Jean Monnet; PIMA; Progress; Europe Aid; Creative Europe</p> <p>International Cooperation According to the Code of Conduct for Universities on Development Cooperation, to which UMA adhered to on February 12th, 2009, “the University must assume a leading role in human development processes.” Along</p>	(Basic Information)
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						<p>these lines, UMA has included objective 25.2. in their 2009-2012 Strategic Plan: “Get the University of Malaga involved in Development Cooperation through education, training, and support for projects”</p> <p>Through this Strategic Plan, it is precisely Development Cooperation which UMA has included as one of its lines of action. In line with this approach, the Vice rectorate for International Relations, through the International Cooperation Secretariat, is promoting measures aimed at enhancing, consolidating, giving visibility, and disseminating actions carried out in this sphere.</p> <p>International Cooperation - Calls International Cooperation - Courses and Conferences International Cooperation - Fair Trade International Cooperation - Activities</p>	
<p>POLITO Politecnico di Torino/1+2 Students (2013/2014) 31,800 students http://www.polito.it/ateneo/copolodocchio/?lang=en 27.650 2012-2013 http://statistica.miur.it/scripts/IU/vIU1.asp from: Ministry for Universities and Scientific and Technological Research (Italian): http://www.mur.st.it/ 9/26 EMA2s1 2007-2013</p>	41	1° http://www.polito.it/amministrazione/struttura/	3 A* (check link about statute)	Pj x2 (EU and non EU) Mb + out/in	<p>INTERNATIONALIZATION</p> <p>The Politecnico di Torino has long faced the biggest international technical schools in education and research fields. The first agreements date back to nineties and their number increased very soon thanks to collaborations on student mobility.</p> <p>The University was able to create a true international and multicultural environment and a world research network on the main subjects of reference by strengthening education in English; supporting international mobility of students and teachers; attracting foreign students, doctoral students, and researchers; taking part in combined research projects and programs.</p> <p>A Politecnico's network of campuses abroad strengthens international relations with countries whose collaboration has strengthened over the years,</p>	<p>ACTIVITIES AND CONTACTS</p> <p>Since the early eighties the Politecnico di Torino has adopted a new policy for international cooperation, and the network of international relations, in its various aspects, has expanded greatly.</p> <p>The Politecnico's international programmes include a range of different activities such as bilateral and multilateral partnerships with universities and research institutions of both European and extra-European countries, as well as agreements with the European Union on research, training, cooperation and structural projects, plus the organization of student, professor and staff exchanges.</p> <p>Advice and management on non-EU international projects</p>	<p>Italian/English http://www.polito.it/ateneo/internazionalizzazione/?lang=en (just gral explanation)</p> <p>For incoming students: Italian, English, Chinese http://international.polito.it/</p>

especially with China, where the [Italan-Chinese campus](#) in the Tongji University of Shanghai is active since 2006. The most of the foreign students of the Politecnico are from China and the collaboration with the Asian country recently expanded also to research fields, especially after the creation in Beijing, under the aegis of the Italian Ministry of the Environment, of the Center EC2 - EU-China Clean Energy Center, for the implementation of the use of renewable energy sources in the country.

From the Statute 2011, article N° 10
http://www.swas.polito.it/services/docuff/Default.asp?id_documento_padre=10358
 “16. The Rector appoints a Vice Rector for Teaching, a Vice-Rector for Research, a Vice-Rector for Internationalization and a Vice-Rector for Quality.”
 Real Vice-Rectors:
<http://www.polito.it/ateneo/organizzazione/organi/vicereettori/index.php?lang=en>
 the Delegate named CV
http://www.swas.polito.it/rubrica/scheda_pers.asp?matricola=002042

[Advice and management on projects financed by the EU](#)
[Management and coordination of student exchanges](#)

ADVICE AND MANAGEMENT ON NON-EU INTERNATIONAL PROJECTS

The International Relations Office is part of the Department of International Affairs and is responsible for the institutional side of relationships with foreign countries and organizations, with the exception of direct relationships with EU institutions (for which the Office for Relationships with the EU is responsible).

ADVICE AND MANAGEMENT ON PROJECTS FINANCED BY THE EU

The Office for Relations with the EU was created within the External Relations and Contracts Service to facilitate access to programmes co-financed by the EU in the areas of Technological Research and Development, Training and International Cooperation. The results so far obtained have been particularly encouraging: the success rate of proposals made by the Politecnico di Torino has been 35%, against an Italian average of 20% and a European one of 23% (also with reference to the support provided to scientific coordinators in the FP5 projects).

MANAGEMENT AND COORDINATION OF STUDENT EXCHANGES

Within the Department of International Affairs this office manages all the activities, projects and agreements involving student exchanges, both within the LLP/Erasmus programme (UE and associated countries) and in special projects and bilateral agreements between universities for extra-European countries.

					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical support to apply for EU programmes and management of EU funded education initiatives (Main Programmes: Erasmus+, Cultura, LLP, Erasmus Mundus, EuropeAid, Tempus...). 	<p>service of Queen Elizabeth I and founder of the government's secret services; and courageous men like Michel de L'Hospital, collaborator of Catherine de Medicis, Queen of France, and champion of religious tolerance. Another scholar, Stefan Batory from Hungary, became Prince of Transylvania in 1571 and later King of Poland. The 40 portraits in this hall are emblematic of the University of Padova and of its long-standing traditions in the field of internationalisation.</p> <p>Nowadays the University of Padova "promotes the furthering of culture founded on universal values such as human rights, peace, respect for the environment and international solidarity" (Article 1 of its Statutes, 1995). The international dimension of the University is not only witnessed by many spontaneous activities, such as the countless research cooperation projects individually promoted by teachers and researchers and the teaching now offered to as many as 1,500 regularly enrolled foreign students, but also by the existence of several bilateral agreements of 'traditional' type, extensive participation in European programmes for research and education, cooperation with developing countries, and – last, but not least – by committed participation in the project activities of the Coimbra Group (the network of historical European universities) as well as other excellence networks.</p>	
<p><i>Rijksuniversiteit Groningen/1+2</i> 28.200 from 2011 Groningen (factsheet 2012) http://www.vsnunl/rijksuniversiteit-groningen-en.html 5/26 EMA2s1 2007-2013</p>	¿?	0	XXX	XXX	<p>http://www.rug.nl/about-us/internationalization/international-classroom/ General information International Classroom Project – a comprehensive, quality approach The main questions in the international classroom project are:</p>	<p>Internationalization The University is actively involved in the region and considers an international outlook essential. From our central position in Europe, the world is within our reach.</p>	<p>All in English IROs by Faculty: http://www.rug.nl/education/international-students/adressenfaculiteiten</p>

				<p>What makes our programmes international? How to use diversity as a resource in the international classroom? How to adjust our policies to realise our vision on internationalisation? How to realise fit for purpose support for our students and staff?</p> <p>Internationalisation in higher education is a constantly evolving process, with no one model fitting all. The University of Groningen has a long tradition and high ambitions in internationalisation. In a first phase, the focus was on increasing the number of English-taught programmes and incoming international students and staff, stimulating outgoing mobility for students and staff, and establishing an international network of quality partners. Like many other universities in Europe, the University of Groningen is now entering a second phase in which we aim to fully integrate internationalisation throughout our organisation and policies, and to link internationalisation with the quality of education and research. For these purposes, the International Classroom project was started in April 2013.</p> <p>The overarching aim of the International Classroom project is to give added value to programmes through a model of International Classroom and to acquire the quality label (DQFI) for internationalisation from the Dutch/Flemish accreditation body the “NVAO”. The model for the International Classroom will be defined from an overall mission and vision on internationalisation and the results of a pilot project. The concrete objectives of the project are therefore: To develop a clear vision on internationalisation which is supported by all stakeholders, linked to the quality of education, resulting in policies enabling the realisation of the vision on internationalisation To develop international and intercultural learning outcomes for each programme through a vision on internationalisation at programme level</p>	<p>To give students and staff from all over the world the opportunity to succeed, we provide excellent conditions for teaching and research. This means that many of our Bachelor's and Master's degree programmes are taught in English. In addition, we offer a growing number of international double degree/joint programmes in cooperation with our partner universities all over the world.</p> <p>Key figures 3,750 international students and PhD students 7 Erasmus Mundus programmes 1,055 outbound exchange students 3,286 of 27,511 Bachelor and Master students are international students 466 of 1,133 are international PhD students 35.7 % of the academic staff is international More than 120 nationalities currently study or work at the University 107 English-taught Master's degree programmes, of which 11 are Double Degree/Joint Degree programmes 21 English-taught Bachelor's degree programmes, of which 3 are Double Degree/Joint Degree programmes Source: annual report 2013</p> <p>Partners and Networks The University maintains long-term partnerships with international universities with similar high standards, participates in international networks and incorporates international themes in its programmes.</p> <p>Our strategic partners Europe Upsala University (Sweden) Ghent University (Belgium) Göttingen University (Germany)</p>
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				<p>To develop and implement a “UoG model” for the international classroom based on the following NVAO parameters: staff; students; teaching and learning; and international and intercultural learning outcomes</p> <p>To realise fit for purpose, contextual support for staff and students (e.g. for the development of intercultural competences, English language, pedagogical skills).</p> <p>The results of the IC project will be relevant for any HEI or other post-secondary educational institution with an international dimension, as well as for organisations and associations in European Higher Education. Project outputs will be presented on the UoG website and through seminars and (international) conferences and publications. Internal and external stakeholders are invited to provide input and/or respond to the outputs via electronic consultation.</p> <p>http://www.rug.nl/about-us/internationalization/</p> <p>Research and study in an international organization</p> <p>Internationalization is one of the main focus points on the strategic policy agenda of the University of Groningen, and an important instrument in the improvement of quality, innovation and diversity. The University has a strong international reputation and steadily climbs the international ranking lists.</p> <p>Degree programmes</p> <p>For many years now the University of Groningen has been rated very well by our international students in the International Student Barometer. The University of Groningen offers a wide, international curriculum, with over 100 English-taught Master’s degree programmes and PhD programmes, as well as more than 20 English-taught degree programmes at Bachelor’s level.</p> <p>Many degree programmes work intensively with international partners. Examples include the 8 prestigious Erasmus Mundus programmes and a swiftly increasing number of Double degree programmes.</p> <p>Internationalization policy</p>	<p>Indonesia Universitas Gadjah Mada University of Indonesia Bandung Institute of Technology China University of Beijing Tsinghua University Fudan University Japan Osaka University Latin America National Autonomous University of Mexico, UNAM (Mexico) University of Sao Paolo, USP (Brazil) USA UCLA University of Pennsylvania</p> <p><u>Our strategic networks</u></p> <p>The Coimbra Group Asea Uninet APAIE EUA</p> <p>Last modified: September 17, 2014 10:07 http://www.rug.nl/about-us/where-do-we-stand/facts-and-figures/internationalisation-figures</p> <p>Rug and Rankings: http://www.rug.nl/about-us/where-do-we-stand/rankings</p> <p>Rug and policy statements http://www.rug.nl/about-us/internationalization/international-classroom/policy-documents</p> <p><u>Strategic Plan</u> The University of Groningen has formulated its vision of the future in its Strategic Plan: 400</p>	
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				<p>The University of Groningen already has 4000 international students with over 120 different nationalities – we hope to reach 5000 international students in 2015. 20% of the staff and 60% of all PhD students are from abroad. The University of Groningen is proud that the European Union has accredited it with both the Diploma Supplement and the ECTS label.</p> <p>Student and staff exchanges form an important part of the internationalization policy. By 2015, the University of Groningen wants half of all its students to have gained experience abroad during their studies, and it has made incentive funds available to this end.</p> <p>Strategic partners</p> <p>There are many types of international cooperation in both teaching and research. Strategic partners and networks at the University of Groningen include: the U4 network with Uppsala, Göttingen and Ghent; the Coimbra network; Tsinghua, Fudan and Peking Universities in China; Osaka in Japan; IT Bandung and Gadjah Mada in Indonesia; Sao Paulo and UNAM in Latin America; UBC and Maryland in North America.</p> <p>Extra info: Connected to an academic department http://www.rug.nl/let/organization/bestuur-afdelingen-en-medewerkers/afdelingen/afdeling-ibio/ Research and study in an international organization International partner agreements Overview countries Testimonials International Classroom</p>	<p><i>Years of Passion and Performance. Strategic Plan 2010-2015.</i> You can request a printed English copy at the Communication Office secretariat. You can also download the Dutch version or the English version as a pdf.</p>	
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Appendix 4 – Spreadsheets for analyzing performance

Memorandums of Understanding (MoU) are one element to consider when analyzing internationalization performance. As Knight explains in her list of five misconceptions considered as a factor of success for the third internationalization i.e., nº3 *International Institutional Agreements* (2011). MoUs are commonly available information navigating any HEI website. Being part of the information that is given referring to the "current" relationships of HEIs with institutions in other countries; as also as an element that transmits the profile of the HEI in reference to its activities with the world and its strategic partners.

De Wit (2011) said in his misconception N° 7: the more partnerships, the more international. He was referring to a common understanding within HEIs, expressing a large number of partners with no data – nor activities supporting them – about the relationship and the history behind the MoU.

In order to track and identify the real existence of rhetorical internationalization in the internationalization process of the HEI, some independent members from the staff or the HEI board were taught how to achieve some field data. This was done in order for the results to be consistent, reliable and available to develop some institutional measures and also in order to be able to identify the cons of individual behavior.

This was also done to monitor or assess the cooperation activities carried out at the Institutional level, the cooperation performance, the decisions made to develop an international profile, or just to check the links between interests and expectations which were expressed – and supported by the MoUs existence – by the HEI and the internationalization profile conferred to.

An open list is presented with items to search/ask/analyze and consider in order to trace and demonstrate a first connection between the Internationalization Strategy - if it exists - reported or conveyed and the rhetorical internationalization by measuring the level of compliance with the agreements signed next to how they were developed, what were they signed for and how are they running.

As an example, variables to apply in order to analyze MoUs' impact and measure benefits for HEI internationalization are presented in Annex 4. To do this, one should be able to access to the raw data if it exists; or to create it within the IRO.

Emerging conclusions would bring to the forefront a. the cost/benefit results within the relation, b. that the MoU accomplishment average will demonstrate how much rhetoric has been developed by the institution and where one should focus to reduce it, and c. an increase in the awareness level into the international cooperation policies linked within the internationalization strategy followed; in other words, it would help to apply de Wit's cycle of internationalization starting by *analyzing the context* from the institutional reality with zero rhetoric.

Although it can be measured in different ways, and with different conditions to evaluate the behavior of relationships with other actors. The index that is offered here focuses its interest on the degree of results generated according to the expectations indicated in the signed MoU.

As long as 100% of them are fulfilled, we will be before an HEI which has converted its rhetorical internationalization into an initiative to strengthen its own process. With this, we have managed to implement the agreements' generation regarding the search for the generation of desired and planned advances in the international

dimensions' integration designs and plans from the base. On the other hand, the lower the compliance percentage is, the greater the weight of the rhetoric internationalization in the HEI will be. By default, the time necessary to generate a decision or to modify the institutional dynamics regarding internationalization will be greater. In other words, both the importance and the institutionalization of internationalization translates into itself.

To establish the location the scales will observe from:

- A. More types of activities carried out exist than the expressions in the MoU = **Stage D**
- B. The activities are expressed in the MoU, e.g. mobilities, publications, etcetera; = **Stage B**
- C. The activities carried out are 50% of what is stated in the MoU = **Stage C**
- D. The activities carried out are less than 50% of what is stated in the MoU = **Stage A**
- E. Without activities executed = Rhetorical Stage

This implies indicating the status of the real situation of the activities that the HEI undertook to carry out with its partners. From there, and applying the cycle of internationalization, it will be possible to advance in a detailed analysis of the shortcomings in the process, as well as to identify the degree of rhetoric internationalization in institutional behavior. The MoU factor is not determinant in itself, but it also serves as a sample of the real behavior that the HEI has regarding internationalization, so that the time is necessary to advance in the process.

The categories identified, the analysis of the selected path, the activities and the patterns that characterize the process of internationalization of the HEI analyzed.

Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) – General Agreement

COUNTRY	HEI	YEAR	LENGTH DURATION	SPECIFIC	CAUSE INCENTIVE	IMPLY \$	ACTIVITIES	RESULTS - HOME INSTITUTION	YEAR OF EXECUTION	COSTS
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CAUSES/INCENTIVES	Activities	Results
Research/Service Project	Undergraduate Mobility	Publications
Congress	MSc/PhD Mobility	Double Degree
Seminar	Professor Mobility	Thesis Supervision
Student Mobility	Research Mobility	Thesis Co-supervision
Postgraduate Studies	Staff Mobility	Co-Tutoring
Authorities visits	Network-Consortia	Master Class - IN
National Call	Publication: a. Journal Art.; b. Book chapter; c. Book;	Master Class - OUT
International Call	Patent	Virtual Class - IN
Other Call	Poster	Virtual Class - OUT
Other:		Bibliography Exchange
		Summer School
		Winter School
		Apply to National Call
		Apply to International Call
		Professional Internship
		Academic Internship
		Lab Internship
		Other:
		None of the above

Specific Agreement

COUNTRY	HEI	HOME SUBSCRIBTOR	PARTNER SUBSCRIBTOR	YEAR	LENGTH DURATION	CONDITIONED	TYPE	CAUSES INCENTIVES	ACTIVITIES	RESULTS	YEAR OF EXECUTION	COSTS	\$ INVESTED
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Subscriber/Signer	Type	CAUSES/INCENTIVES	Activities	Results
HEI Area	N° of executed activities	Research/Service Project	Undergraduate Mobility	Publication
Faculty	Undergraduate Mobility N°	Congress	MSc/PhD Mobility	Double Degree
Research Group	Graduate mobility N°	Seminar	Professor Mobility	Thesis Supervision
Program	Professor mobility N°	Individual Mobility a. Student; b. Prof; c. Researcher; d. Staff	Research Mobility	Thesis Co-supervision
Lecture Prof	Researchers Mobility N°	Undergraduate Studies	Staff Mobility	Co-Tutoring
	Staff Mobility N°	Authority Visit	Network/Consortia	Master Class IN
	Publication	National Call	Publication 1: a. Journal Art.; b. Book chapter; c. Book;	Master Class OUT
	Apply Grant Call	International Call	Patent	Virtual Class IN
	None	Other Call	Poster	Virtual Class OUT
	Other:	Other:		Bibliography Exchange
				Summer School
				Winter School
				Apply to National Call
				Apply to International Call
			Professional Internship	
			Academic Internship	
			Lab Internship	
			Other:	

References:

Aerden, A. (2014). *A guide to assessing the quality of internationalisation*. European Consortium for Accreditation in higher education. Retrieved from: http://ecahe.eu/w/images/7/73/A_Guide_to_Assessing_the_Quality_of_Internationalisation.pdf

Agnew, M. (2012). Strategic Planning: An Examination of the Role of Disciplines in Sustaining Internationalization of the University. *Journal of Studies In International Education*, 17(2), 183-202. doi:10.1177/1028315312464655

Altbach, P., & Knight, J. (2007). The Internationalization of Higher Education: Motivations and Realities. *Journal of Studies In International Education*, 11(3-4), 290-305. doi:10.1177/1028315307303542

Altbach, P., & Teichler, U. (2001). Internationalization and Exchanges in a Globalized University. *Journal Of Studies In International Education*, 5(1), 5-25. doi:10.1177/102831530151002

Avila, J. (2007). The Process of Internationalization of Latin American Higher Education. *Journal of Studies In International Education*, 11(3-4), 400-409. doi:10.1177/1028315307303921

Arum, S., & Van de Water, J. (1992). The need for a definition of international education in US universities. *Bridges to the futures: Strategies for internationalizing higher education*, 191-203.

Bartell, M. (2003). Internationalization of universities: A university culture-based framework. *Higher Education*, 45(1), 43-70.

Bess, J. and Dee, Jay. *Understanding College and University Organization. Theories for Effective Policy and Practice*. Sterling, VA: Stylus Publishing 2012.

Biddle, S. (2002). *Internationalization: Rhetoric or reality?* (Vol. 56). New York: American council of learned societies.

Brandenburg, U., & Federkeil, G. (2007). *How to measure internationality and internationalisation of higher education institutions!*. Gütersloh: CHE.

Brunner, J. (2009). The Bologna Process from a Latin American Perspective. *Journal Of Studies In International Education*, 13(4), 417-438. doi:10.1177/1028315308329805

Bull, C. (2004). Rhetoric and Reality: The Internationalisation of Education as Experienced in the Cross-cultural and Cross-disciplinary Studio. *Landscape Review*, 9(2), 70-86.

Call for proposals — EACEA/35/08 for the implementation of Erasmus Mundus External Cooperation Window in the academic year 2009-2010 — The Community Action programme for the promotion of cooperation between higher education institutions and the exchange of students, researchers and academic staff from EU Member States and Third Countries. *European Commission*, 2008.12.23 C2008/328/07. Retrieved from: <https://publications.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/fc3c0046-112c-4b07-8248-82e3118c0c37>

Cannella, G. S., Pérez, M. S., & Pasque, P. A. (Eds.). (2016). *Critical qualitative inquiry: Foundations and futures*. Routledge.

Council conclusions of 11 May 2010 on the internationalisation of higher education (2010/C 135/04). *Official Journal of the European Union*, 26.5.2010 C 135/12.

Chan, W. (2004). International Cooperation in Higher Education: Theory and Practice. *Journal Of Studies In International Education*, 8(1), 32-55. doi:10.1177/1028315303254429

Cohen, A., Yemini, M., & Sadeh, E. (2014). Web-based analysis of internationalization in Israeli teaching colleges. *Journal of studies in International Education*, 18(1), 23-44. doi: 10.1177/1028315313479131

Colucci, E., Davies, H., Korhonen, J., & Gaebel, M. (2012). *Mobility*. Brussels: European University Association.

Communiqué, P. (2001). Towards the European Higher Education area. Communiqué of the meeting of European Ministers in charge of Higher Education in Prague on May 19th 2001. Retrieved from: http://www.ehea.info/media.ehea.info/file/2001_Prague/44/2/2001_Prague_Communique_English_553442.pdf

Communiqué, B. (2003, September). Realising the European higher education area. In *Communiqué of the Conference of Ministers responsible for higher education in Berlin on 19 September 2003*. Retrieved from: http://www.ehea.info/media.ehea.info/file/2003_Berlin/28/4/2003_Berlin_Communique_English_577284.pdf

CONEAU (Argentina). (1997). *Lineamientos para la evaluación institucional*. CONEAU. Retrieved from: <http://www.coneau.edu.ar/archivos/482.pdf>

Creswell, J.W. (2003) *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Method Approaches*. Sage Publications, Thousand Oaks.

Creswell, J. W. (2007). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches* (2nd ed.). Sage Publications, Inc.

Creswell, J. W. (2009). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (3rd ed.). Sage Publications, Inc.

Crystle, J. (2020). *The impacts of national and institutional policies on the internationalization of higher education in Australia: What it means for Australia and*

what it could mean for the United States. (Doctoral dissertation). Available from ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global database. (UMI No. 28257465)

Davies, J. (1992). Developing a strategy for internationalization in universities: Towards a conceptual framework. *Bridges to the future: Strategies for internationalizing higher education*, 177-190.

Davies, J. L. (1995). University strategies for internationalization in different institutional and cultural settings: A conceptual framework. *Policy and policy implementation in internationalization of higher education*. Amsterdam: European Association for International Education.

Declaration, S. J. (1998). Joint declaration on harmonisation of the architecture of the European higher education system. *By the four ministers in charge for France, Germany, Italy and the United Kingdom*. Paris. Retrieved from: http://www.ehea.info/media.ehea.info/file/1998_Sorbonne/61/2/1998_Sorbonne_Declaration_English_552612.pdf

de Fanelli, A. G. (2014). Argentine Higher Education. In *Global Opportunities and Challenges for Higher Education Leaders* (pp. 195-199). Sense Publishers, Rotterdam.

de Wit, H. (2013). *An Introduction to Higher Education Internationalisation*. Milan: Vita e Pensiero.

de Wit, H. (1997). Studies in International Education: A Research Perspective. *Journal of Studies In International Education*, 1(1), 1-8. doi:10.1177/102831539700100103

de Wit, H. (2007). Ten Years of Editorial Policy of the Journal of Studies in International Education: Overview, Challenges, and Opportunities. *Journal of Studies In International Education*, 11(3-4), 251-259. doi:10.1177/1028315307303533

de Wit, H. (2011). Globalization and Internationalisation of Higher Education. *RUSC. Universities And Knowledge Society Journal*, 8(2), 77. doi:10.7238/rusc.v8i2.1247

de Wit, H. (2010). Internationalisation of Higher Education in Europe and its assessment, trends and issues.

De Wit, H., Jaramillo, I. C., Knight, J., and Gacel-Ávila, J. (Eds.). (2005). *Higher education in Latin America: The international dimension*. The World Bank. Retrieved from <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/bitstream/handle/10986/7428/343530PAPER0LA101OFFICIAL0USE0ONLY1.pdf?sequence=1>

De Wit, H. (2001). Internationalisation of higher education in the United States of America and Europe. *Amsterdam: University of Amsterdam Thesis*.

Didou Aupetit, S., & Jaramillo de Escobar, V. (2014). Internacionalización de la educación superior y la ciencia en América Latina: un estado del arte [*Translation: Internationalization of higher education and science in Latin America: State of the Art*]. *Mendoza, Argentina: Observatorio de Movilidades Académicas y Científicas del IESALC-UNESCO: Editorial de la Facultad de Filosofía y Letras de la Universidad Nacional de Cuyo, Mendoza, Argentina*.

Elavsky, C. M. (2012). Because "we are...". *Cultural Studies - Critical Methodologies*, 12(4), 297-300. doi:10.1177/1532708612446426

Enders, J. (2005). *The European higher education and research landscape 2020*. Enschede, Center for Higher Education Policy Studies, The Netherlands.

Fernandes Nogueira, J. F. (2013). *The Politics of Access to Higher Education in Argentina and Brazil: A comparative analysis* (Doctoral thesis, UCLA). Retrieved from:

Field, J. (1997). The Learning Society and the European Union: A Critical Assessment of Supranational Education Policy Formation. *Journal Of Studies In International Education*, 1(2), 73-92. doi:10.1177/102831539700100205

Foucault, M. (1972). *The archaeology of knowledge: Translated from the french by AM Sheridan Smith*. Pantheon Books.

Friedman, M. (1953). *Essays in positive economics*. Chicago, Ill: University of Chicago Press.

Funes, M. (2014). Internacionalización de la Educación Superior en Argentina: conceptualización en contexto. *Tangelson, Guillermo (comp.), Desde el sur: miradas sobre la internacionalización*, 39-53.

Gacel-Ávila, J. (2012). Comprehensive Internationalisation in Latin America. *High Educ Policy*, 25(4), 493-510. doi:10.1057/hep.2012.9

Gee, J. 1996 *Social Linguistics and Literacies: Ideology in Discourses* (London: Taylor & Francis, 2nd edn)

Gilboa, A. (2012). Rhetoric in Economics. *Paris Innovation Review*. 3/12/2012. Retrieved from: <http://parisinnovationreview.com/articles-en/rhetoric-in-economics>

Given, L. M. (Ed.). (2008). *The Sage encyclopedia of qualitative research methods*. Sage Publications.

Harari, M. (1972). *Global Dimensions in US Education: The University*.

Harari, M. (1989). *Report# 1, internationalization of higher education: effecting institutional change in the curriculum and campus ethos* (No. 1). Center for International Education, California State University, Long Beach.

Haug, G., & Race, J. (1998). Interregional Cooperation in Higher Education in Europe'. *Journal of Studies In International Education*, 2(2), 3-34.
doi:10.1177/1028315398002002002

Hausman, D. M. (1989). Economic methodology in a nutshell. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 3(2), 115-127.

Hunter, F. (2013). Internationalisation and institutional responsiveness: Harnessing the power of imagination. *An introduction to higher education internationalisation*, 61-74.

Hénard, F., Diamond, L., & Roseveare, D. (2012). *Approaches to internationalisation and their implications for strategic management and institutional practice*. Higher Education Programme, OECD, Paris, France.

Ooi, T. C., Ho, H., & Amri, S. (2010). Education websites and their benefits to potential international students: a case study of higher education service providers in Malaysia. *Current Issues in Education*, 13(1), 1-36.

Hudzik, J. K., and Stohl, M. (2009). Modelling assessment of the outcomes and impacts of internationalisation. *Measuring success in the internationalisation of higher education*, 22, 9-21.

Hudzik, J. K. (2011). Comprehensive internationalization: From concept to action. Retrieved from:
https://www.nafsa.org/uploadedFiles/NAFSA_Home/Resource_Library_Assets/Publications_Library/2011_Comprehen_Internationalization.pdf

Hudzik, J. K. (2014). *Comprehensive internationalization: Institutional pathways to success*. Routledge.

John R. Thelin, *A History of American Higher Education*, Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press 2004, p. xxii-xxiii

Kalvemark, T., & Van Der Wende, M. (1997). National Policies for the Internationalisation of Higher Education in Europe. *Hogskoleverket Studies 1997*: 8 S.

Kehm, B., & Teichler, U. (2007). Research on Internationalisation in Higher Education. *Journal Of Studies In International Education*, 11(3-4), 260-273. doi:10.1177/1028315307303534

Kelo, M. (2006). Toward Improved Data on Student Mobility in Europe: Findings and Concepts of the Eurodata Study. *Journal Of Studies In International Education*, 10(3), 194-223. doi:10.1177/1028315306288755

Kettler, L. K. (2018). *External Global Forces that Affect Higher Education Internationalization Strategies and How Three US Universities Adapt to Them*. (Doctoral dissertation). Available from ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global database. (UMI No. 10829576)

Kincheloe, J. L., McLaren, P., & Steinberg, S. R. (2012). Critical pedagogy and qualitative research: Moving to the bricolage, 14-32. *Critical qualitative research reader*. New York: Peter Lang.

Klamer, A., McCloskey, D. N., & Solow, R. M. (Eds.). (1988). *The consequences of economic rhetoric*. Cambridge University Press.

Knight, J. (1994). *Internationalization*. Ottawa: Canadian Bureau for International Education Research.

Knight, J. (1993). Internationalization: management strategies and issues. *International education magazine*, 9(6), 21-22.

Knight, J., & De Wit, H. (1995). Strategies for internationalisation of higher education: Historical and conceptual perspectives. *Strategies for internationalisation of higher education: A comparative study of Australia, Canada, Europe and the United States of America*, 5, 32.

Knight, J. (1997). A Shared Vision? Stakeholders' Perspectives on the Internationalization of Higher Education in Canada. *Journal Of Studies In International Education*, 1(1), 27-44. Doi:10.1177/102831539700100105

Knight, J. (1999). Quality and Internationalisation in Higher Education. Paris, Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development.

Knight, J. (2001). Monitoring the Quality and Progress of Internationalization. *Journal of Studies In International Education*, 5(3), 228-243. Doi:10.1177/102831530153004

Knight, J. (2002). Trade Talk: An Analysis of the Impact of Trade Liberalization and the General Agreement on Trade in Services on Higher Education. *Journal Of Studies In International Education*, 6(3), 209-229. Doi:10.1177/102831530263002

Knight, J. (2003). Updating the definition of internationalization. *International Higher Education*, 33(6), 2-3

Knight, J. (2004). Internationalization Remodeled: Definition, Approaches, and Rationales. *Journal of Studies In International Education*, 8(1), 5-31. Doi:10.1177/1028315303260832

Knight, J. (2008). *Higher education in turmoil*. Rotterdam [u.a.]: Sense Publ.

Knight, J. (2011). Education Hubs: A Fad, a Brand, an Innovation?. *Journal Of Studies In International Education*, 15(3), 221-240. Doi:10.1177/1028315311398046

Knight, J. (2012). Concepts, rationales, and interpretive frameworks in the internationalization of higher education. *The SAGE Handbook of International Higher Education*. London: SAGE, 27-42.

Knight, J. (2015). Five myths about internationalization. *International higher education*, (62).

Larrea, M., & Astur, A. (2011). Políticas de internacionalización de la educación superior y cooperación internacional universitaria. Retrieved from <http://pep.unc.edu.ar/wp-content/uploads/sites/46/2017/02/Pol%C3%ADticas-de-internacionalizaci%C3%B3n-de-la-Eduaci%C3%B3n-Superior-Larrea-M-y-Astur-A.pdf>

Laufer, M. (2021). Spinning Stories: Communicating Internationalization Through Organizational Storytelling. *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 25(2), 167–181. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1028315319893652>

Leedy, P. and Ormrod, J. (2001) Practical Research: Planning and Design. 7th Edition, Merrill Prentice Hall and SAGE Publications, Upper Saddle River, NJ and Thousand Oaks, CA.

Lopez, D., Lopez, D., Andrade, L., & Lopez, B. (2011). Functional Patterns in International Organizations for University Cooperation in Latin America and the Caribbean. *Journal Of Studies In International Education*, 15(2), 203-215. Doi:10.1177/1028315310382457

Marginson, S., & van der Wende, M. (2007). To Rank or To Be Ranked: The Impact of Global Rankings in Higher Education. *Journal of Studies In International Education*, 11(3-4), 306-329. Doi:10.1177/1028315307303544

Marginson, S. (2014). Higher education and public good: A global study. In *Higher Education in Societies* (pp. 51-71). Brill.

McCabe, L. (2001). Globalization and Internationalization: The Impact on Education Abroad Programs. *Journal of Studies In International Education*, 5(2), 138-145. Doi:10.1177/102831530152004

Merton, R. (1968). The Matthew Effect in Science: The reward and communication systems of science are considered. *Science*, 159(3810), 56-63. Doi:10.1126/science.159.3810.56

Middlehurst, R. (2008). Developing institutional internationalisation policies and strategies: an overview of key issues. Retrieved from: http://www.braude.ac.il/files/Tempus_Iris/Assts/WP2/Articles_and_Material/Developing_Institutional_Internationalisation_policies.pdf

NAFSA's Contribution to Internationalization of Higher Education, May 2008. Retrieved from: https://www.nafsa.org/uploadedFiles/nafsas_contribution.pdf?n=8167

OECD (1999), *Quality and Internationalisation in Higher Education*, OECD Publishing, Paris, France. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264173361-en>

Ovseiko, P. V., Pololi, L. H., Edmunds, L. D., Civian, J. T., Daly, M., & Buchan, A. M. (2019). Creating a more supportive and inclusive university culture: a mixed-methods interdisciplinary comparative analysis of medical and social sciences at the University of Oxford. *Interdisciplinary Science Reviews*, 44(2), 166-191. Doi:10.1080/03080188.2019.1603880

Paige, R. M. (2005). Internationalization of higher education: Performance assessment and indicators. *Nagoya Journal of Higher Education*, 5(8), 99-122, retrieved from: <http://www.cshe.nagoya-u.ac.jp/publications/journal/no5/08.pdf>

Pasque, P. A., & Rex, L. A. (2010). Complicating "Just Do It": Leaders' Frameworks for Analyzing Higher Education for the Public Good. *Higher Education in Review*, 7.

Qiang, Z. (2003). Internationalization of Higher Education: towards a conceptual framework. *Policy Futures in Education*, 1(2), 248. Doi:10.2304/pfie.2003.1.2.5

Ralyk, N. V. (2008). Integrating Internationalization into Higher Education: Reconceptualizing the ‘Why’, ‘What’, and ‘How’. *Educational Leadership and Policy Integrative Paper at University of Utah, Spring*. Retrieved from: <https://elp.utah.edu/documents/programs/med/natalia-ralykfinalpaper-2.pdf>

Rauhvargers, A. (2010). Achieving Bologna Goals: Where Does Europe Stand Ahead of 2010. *Journal Of Studies In International Education*, 15(1), 4-24. Doi:10.1177/1028315310373834

Rojas Morales, A.I. (2022). *La internacionalización de las instituciones de educación superior en la región Centroamericana*. (Doctoral dissertation). Available from ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global database. (UMI No. 28970501)

Rudzki, R. E. J. (1998). Strategic management of internationalization: towards a model of theory and practice.

Rumbley, L. E., Helms, R. M., Peterson, P. M., & Altbach, P. G. (Eds.). (2014). *Global opportunities and challenges for higher education leaders: Briefs on key themes*. Springer.

Scott, P. (2000). Globalisation and Higher Education: Challenges for the 21st Century. *Journal of Studies In International Education*, 4(1), 3-10. Doi:10.1177/102831530000400102

Schoorman, D. (2000). Internationalization: The Challenge of Implementing Organizational Rhetoric.

Secretariat, B. B. (2009, April). Bologna beyond 2010—Report on the development of the European Higher Education Area. In *Leuven/Louvain-la-Neuve Ministerial Conference*. Retrieved from: http://www.ehea.info/media.ehea.info/file/2009_Leuven_Louvain-la-Neuve/91/8/Beyond_2010_report_FINAL_594918.pdf

Söderqvist, M. (2002). *Internationalisation and its management at higher-education institutions. Applying conceptual, content and discourse analysis*. Helsinki School of Economics. Retrieved from: <https://aaltodoc.aalto.fi/bitstream/handle/123456789/11206/a206.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

Stohl, M. (2007). We Have Met the Enemy and He Is Us: The Role of the Faculty in the Internationalization of Higher Education in the Coming Decade. *Journal of Studies In International Education*, 11(3-4), 359-372. Doi:10.1177/1028315307303923

Stone, N. (2006). Internationalising the Student Learning Experience: Possible Indicators. *Journal of Studies In International Education*, 10(4), 409-413. Doi:10.1177/1028315306287633

Suddaby, R., & Greenwood, R. (2005). Rhetorical strategies of legitimacy. *Administrative science quarterly*, 50(1), 35-67. Doi: 10.2189/asqu.2005.50.1.35

Suddaby, R. (2006). From the editors: What grounded theory is not. Doi.org/10.5465/amj.2006.22083020

Tangelson, G. (2014). Desde el sur: miradas sobre la internacionalización. *Buenos Aires: Ediciones de la UNILA–Universidad Nacional de Lanús*.

Teichler, U. (2004). The Changing Debate on Internationalisation of Higher Education. *Higher Education*, 48(1), 5-26. Doi:10.1023/b:high.0000033771.69078.41

Teichler, U., & Janson, K. (2007). The Professional Value of Temporary Study in Another European Country: Employment and Work of Former ERASMUS Students. *Journal of Studies In International Education*, 11(3-4), 486-495. Doi:10.1177/1028315307303230

Teichler, U. (2009). Internationalisation of higher education: European experiences. *Asia Pacific education review*, 10(1), 93-106. Doi: 10.1007/s12564-009-9002-7

Theiler, J. (2003). Relevamiento de actividades de cooperación internacional de las universidades nacionales Argentinas [*translation: Survey of international cooperation activities of Argentine national universities*]. Documento de trabajo [translation: Working Document], *Red de Cooperación Internacional de las Universidades Nacionales (RedCIUN)*, Universidad de Córdoba, Argentina.

Theiler, J. C. (2005). Internationalization of higher education in Argentina. *Higher Education in Latin America*, 71-112.

Tobin, M. (2014). Internacionalización. Conceptos y prácticas. *Tangelson, Guillermo (comp.), Desde el sur: miradas sobre la internacionalización*, 53-65.

van der Wende, M. C. (1996). *Internationalising the curriculum in Dutch higher education: An international comparative perspective*. Enschede: Universiteit Twente.

van der Wende, M. (1999). An Innovation Perspective on Internationalisation of Higher Education Institutionalisation: The Critical Phase. *Journal Of Studies In International Education*, 3(1), 3-14. Doi:10.1177/102831539900300102

van der Wende, M. (2000). The Bologna Declaration: Enhancing the Transparency and Competitiveness of European Higher Education. *Higher Education In Europe*, 25(3), 305-310. Doi:10.1080/713669277

van der Wende, M. (2007). Internationalization of Higher Education in the OECD Countries: Challenges and Opportunities for the Coming Decade. *Journal Of Studies In International Education*, 11(3-4), 274-289. Doi:10.1177/1028315307303543

Veles, N., Carter, M. A., & Boon, H. (2019). Complex collaboration champions: university third space professionals working together across borders. *Perspectives: Policy and Practice in Higher Education*, 23(2-3), 75-85.

Volkova, N. V., & Plakhotnik, M. S. (2021). Commitment of key internal stakeholders during internationalization: challenges of an emerging market culture. *Journal of Marketing for Higher Education*, 1-19. doi: 10.1080/08841241.2021.1933672

Watkins, M. (2021). *The Relationship between Higher Education Comprehensive Internationalization and the U.S. News and World Report College Rankings and Reputation Scores*. (Doctoral dissertation). Available from ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global database. (UMI No. 29133712)

Whitsed, C., & Green, W. (2014). What's in a Name? A Theoretical Exploration of the Proliferation of Labels for International Education Across the Higher Education Sector. *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 18(2), 105–119. doi:10.1177/1028315313491117

Zechlin, L. (2010). Strategic Planning in Higher Education. Retrieved from: https://www.wissenschaftsmanagement-online.de/sites/www.wissenschaftsmanagement-online.de/files/migrated_wimoarticle/StrategicPlanninginHigherEducation.pdf In *The International Encyclopedia of Education, 3rd Edition*, edited by Barry McGaw, Penelope Peterson and Eva Baker. Oxford: Elsevier.

Strategic Planning in Higher Education, IN: International Encyclopedia of Education 3rd Edition. Edited by Eva Baker, Penelope Peterson, and Barry McGaw, Elsevier 2010.

Zechlin, L. (2010). Strategic Planning in Higher Education. *International Encyclopedia of Education*. 256-263.

Wit, H. (1995). *Strategies for internationalisation of higher education*. European Association for International Education, Amsterdam.